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**Designing a Data Access and Integration
Workflow for Medical Data Science: a
use case of compiling a reusable data set
for primary tumor discovery at MeDIC
Cologne.**

by

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Abstract

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Recent advances in Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) also led to considerable progress in Medical Data Science (MDS). They enable a better understanding of diseases and treatment responses as well as applying personalized therapy. This results in an improved prognosis for many patients.

Often MDS projects need data from several medical data systems to get enough features per patient for well-founded decision-making. However, this Data Access and Integration (DAI) is complicated by several issues. For instance, clinical data is often not digitized in a structured manner and generally shows a high degree of heterogeneity. Additional challenges include the strict data protection rules following from the high sensitivity of medical data and the multi-actor architecture of data systems. Thus, Data Integration Centers (DIC) like the Medical Data Integration Center (MeDIC) Cologne are currently established to ease the DAI process for researchers making medical data available for MDS all over Germany. However, these DICs still face technical, legal, ethical, and organizational problems.

This thesis aims at supporting MDS teams including DICs to define concrete DAI processes by proposing a DAI workflow for MDS that serves as a basis for discussing concrete DAI project designs as well as optimizing DAI processes at university hospitals. This was done in five steps. Firstly, I performed a literature review on current technical, legal, ethical, and organizational challenges in the DAI process. Secondly, I gained personal DAI experience in a clinical use case of the Center for Integrated Oncology (CIO) Cologne. Thirdly, I used the results of the first two steps to propose a DAI workflow for MDS accompanied by a surrounding DAI framework and a performance estimation guideline. In a fourth step this proposal was assessed by employees of University Hospital Cologne (UHC) in the course of expert interviews. Eventually, I implemented the received feedback into the proposal. The result is a widely applicable DAI workflow for MDS accompanied by a classification of involved roles, system concepts, data security measures and a performance estimation guideline.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADT	”Arbeitsgemeinschaft Deutscher Tumorzentren”
BDSG	”Bundesdatenschutzgesetz”
BMBF	”Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung”
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CA	Calcium
CCR	Clinical Cancer Registry
CFR	Charter of Fundamental Rights
CIO	Center for Integrated Oncology
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPTAC	Clinical Proteomic Tumour Analysis Consortium
CRISP-DM	CRoss Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
CRP	C-reactive protein
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CUP	Cancer of Unknown Primary
CUPLR	Cancer of Unknown Primary Location Resolver
DAI	Data Access and Integration
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DIC	Data Integration Center
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DIFUTURE	Data Integration and Future Medicine
DL	Deep Learning
DPC	Data Protection Concept
DSC	Data Security Concept
DSG	”Datenschutzgesetz”
DT	Decision Tree

EC	Ethics Committee
EHR	Electronic Health Record
ETL	Extract Transform Load
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GBT	Gradient Boosted Trees
GEKID	”Gesellschaft der epidemiologischen Krebsregister in Deutschland”
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GG	”Grundgesetz”
GI	Gastrointestinal tract
HB	Haemoglobin
HiGHmed	Heidelberg-Göttingen-Hannover Medical Informatics
HKT	Haematocrit
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICD	International Classification of Disease
ICGC	International Cancer Genome Consortium
ID	Identifier
IoT	Internet of Things
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
LI(M)S	Laboratory Information (Management) System
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes
LOP	Location Of the Primary tumor
MDS	Medical Data Science
MeDIC	Medical Data Integration Center
MII	Medical Informatics Initiative
MIRACUM	Medical Informatics for Research and Care in University Medicine
ML	Machine Learning
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	Neural Network
NRW	North-Rhine Westphalia
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PCAWG	Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes

PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act
PDMS	Patient Data Management System
PI	Principle Investigator
PID	Patient Identifier
PMD	Project Management Document
RECIST	Response Evaluation Criteria In Solid Tumors
RF	Random Forest
RIS	Radiology Information System
SMITH	Smart Medical Informatics Technology for Health Care
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms
SQL	Structured Query Language
TBS	Tumor Burden Score
TCGA	The Cancer Genome Atlas
TMF	Technologie- und Methodenplattform für die vernetzte medizinische Forschung e.V.
TOAD	Tumor Origin Assessment via Deep Learning
UAC	Use and Access Committee
UHC	University Hospital Cologne
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Current advances in Medical data science (MDS) have demonstrated that this research field carries great potential [1–3]. For instance, it has been shown that applying Machine Learning (ML) on medical data can be used for robot-assisted surgery, virtual nursing assistance, administrative workflow assistance, fraud detection, reduction of dosage errors, integration of data from connected instruments and sensors, identification of potential participants in clinical trials, aiding in the formation of preliminary diagnoses, automated image analysis as well as nutrition support to treatment. Thus, MDS can enable progress in form of increased process efficiency, higher patient safety, reliable risk estimation, performant clinical decision support systems, personalized care and improved healthcare system sustainability [3]. However, the current impact of MDS on healthcare is of rather theoretical nature. Learning health care systems assisting healthcare professionals have not been implemented in clinical practice yet [2, 4–6]. Therefore, the current status of MDS is still in the beginning stages falling short of its possibilities [2].

The international MDS community currently tries to change this by improving the circumstances for MDS, i.e. by developing structured Electronic Health Records (EHRs), enhancing healthcare management and administration, accelerating clinical and research development as well as evaluating documentation [5]. All of this aims at increasing the availability of medical data in higher abundance and quality. Because high-quality data is one of the key ingredients of ML, this fosters progress in MDS [3]. A very central measure to support this endeavour is designing an efficient and legally as well as ethically valid Data Access and Integration (DAI) process [7, 8]. For instance, the German Ethics Council mentions the simplification of data integration as a necessary measure to enable ethical data science because complex processes make it difficult to judge their compliance to ethical and legal requirements [9]. A review of Vuokko et al., furthermore, emphasizes that current literature demands the development of measures simplifying medical DAI but there is still a lack of concrete proposals [5].

This thesis aims to address the mentioned issues and take action by providing a conceptualization of the DAI process at university hospitals. The conceptualization suggests a workflow serving as a template for designing concrete DAI processes as well as standardization and improvement of the DAI process. Furthermore, it provides a DAI framework classifying involved roles, system concepts and data security assurance measures, as well as a performance estimation guideline which can be used to assess the performance of a designed DAI process. Firstly, a preliminary DAI conceptualization was developed. The basis for this were an extensive literature review identifying challenges of DAI at German University Hospitals and personal DAI experience gained by compiling a data set for primary tumor discovery. The data set compilation took place at the Medical Data Integration Center (MeDIC) Cologne in close collaboration with medical student Devina Soenarto who provided necessary domain knowledge. The preliminary conceptualization was assessed by performing an expert interview series with employees of University Hospital Cologne (UHC) who deal with MDS projects in their daily routine. The expert feedback was implemented into the conceptualization eventually yielding the final versions of the DAI workflow, the DAI framework and the performance estimation guideline.

The outline of this thesis is the following. Chapter 2 defines the objective of the thesis, motivates the necessity of designing a DAI workflow and provides further information on the MeDIC Cologne. It is followed by chapter 3 elaborating on related works, i.e. medical research data and its lifecycle, FAIR Data in Germany and the European Union, data protection and workflow design and performance assessment. Chapter 4 introduces the clinical use case in which I gained practical DAI experience. The methodology applied in this thesis is described by chapter 5. Chapter 6 contains the analysis leading to the eventual conceptualization. Analyzed aspects are the challenges in the DAI process identified by literature review, the DAI process in the clinical use case, the preliminary conceptualization as well as the feedback received during the expert interviews including an assessment of the preliminary conceptualization and further challenges of the DAI process from MDS practice. The final results are described and discussed in chapter 7. It starts with evaluating the DAI process in the clinical use case, continues with discussing the current status of DAI at German University Hospitals and describing the main result of this thesis which is the DAI conceptualization. Furthermore, it makes suggestions how the DAI process can be improved in future and outlines the limitations of this thesis. Finally, chapter 8 contains the conclusion of this thesis and an outlook on possible future advancement of the proposed DAI conceptualization.

Chapter 2

Problem Description

The objective of this thesis is to ease future DAI processes in clinical environments and thus supporting the progress in MDS. This is done by designing a widely applicable DAI conceptualization including a workflow that can serve as a basis for discussing the DAI project design in interdisciplinary data science teams and improvements of the DAI process in general. Hereby, I understand the Access of data to be its retrieval from data systems and, using the definition of Mihaylov et al. from 2019, Data Integration to be "a mean to combining data from different sources, creating a unified view and improving their accessibility to a potential user" [10].

The considered setting is an interdisciplinary data science team accessing and integrating structured data from different departments of a single university hospital eventually aiming at creating a FAIR (c.f. section 3.2) but especially reusable data set for MDS. Accessing unstructured or semi-structured data as well as accessing data from external sources like other hospitals or companies is out of the scope of this thesis.

The design of the DAI workflow is based on a literature review, expert feedback and experience from performing DAI for a clinical use case at MeDIC Cologne. Although the use case had specialities which are not given in every DAI project like being retrospective and restricted to already available structured data, it served as an opportunity to gain insights into the DAI processes at UHC. Including the feedback of diverse experts into the workflow development I ensured that it is still widely applicable.

2.1 Motivation

Current literature results show that there is a demand for clinical decision support systems [5, 8, 11]. Due to their high need for explainability such support systems are usually based on classical ML methods providing intrinsic interpretability like Decision Trees. However,

due to their limited complexity their application requires skilful data preprocessing involving domain knowledge [12]. A decisive issue complicating this preprocessing is the lack of standardized data accessing frameworks [13]. Additionally, such frameworks are not available for the second crucial part of creating usable ML data sets which is the integration of data from multiple heterogenous data sets into one data warehouse [7, 8, 14]. It is true that there already exist standards for files, data types and terminologies like IHE XDS, openEHR, SNOMED CT, HL7 FHIR showing that standardization in MDS is possible [15]. However, standardization of workflows is more challenging and complex, because there are a lot of decisions to be taken on a project specific basis requiring to consider the individual research question and the available data [12].

The Medical Informatics Initiative (MII) and its consortia started working on a general standardization for MDS in Germany after the conceptual phase (2016-2017) during which they had identified standardization in several areas as a promising and necessary measure to foster progress in MDS. However, this standardization is currently still in development in the course of MII use cases focussing on subprocesses of the MDS workflow [16]. Therefore, this thesis aims at suggesting a guiding DAI workflow based on which individual data science teams can already now design their MDS projects until the full workflow standardization is completed. Furthermore, the standardization process can use the proposed workflow as a basis for discussion.

2.2 Medical Data Integration Center Cologne (MeDIC Cologne)

The German Medical Informatics Initiative (MII) (c.f. section 3.2) aims at improving the possibilities of medical research and healthcare by simplifying the planning and execution of MDS projects. In the course of this, all four MII consortia launched Data Integration Centres (DIC) at their participating university hospitals [16]. UHC is part of the "Heidelberg - Göttingen - Hannover medical informatics" (HiGHmed) consortium which calls its DICs Medical Data Integration Centres (MeDICs). [15]. MeDIC Cologne is the MeDIC instance at UHC. It is led by Prof. Dr. Oya Beyan and Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer. Further team members are project managers, medical data stewards, technical experts and IT administrators¹. They aim for building a technical infrastructure that integrates the data from the primary clinical systems at UHC and makes it available for patient care, research and new IT applications in a standardized way². Currently most parts of this technical infrastructure are still being developed. Others are already in the test phase. However, during the clinical use case in which I gained practical DAI experience I could not yet access any data through the MeDIC infrastructure but instead I could use the expertise of the MeDIC employees.

¹<https://www.uk-koeln.de/forschung/medical-data-integration-center-medic/medic-team/>

²<https://www.uk-koeln.de/forschung/medical-data-integration-center-medic/>

Chapter 3

Related Work

3.1 Medical Research Data and its Lifecycle

As the name suggests, medical research data is data that is collected in medical examinations and later used for research purposes. In clinical studies the data is often created primarily for the research purpose. This data is then referred to as "primary data" [17, 18]. If the research project uses data that was generated in another context, one speaks of secondary use or reuse [14, 18]. In this thesis, the focus is set on the latter scenario because secondary data is often preferred to increase efficiency and reduce costs [18].

Medical data can be classified according to the format in which it is available, according to the information it carries or according to its current privacy status. Possible data formats are tabular, time series, natural language, image or video [11]. Medical data types, i.e. classes according to the carried information, are demographics, healthcare provider notes, radiological data, laboratory results, genetic testing data, biomarker data, administrative claim records, clinical registries, biometric data, patient-reported data and recordings from medical devices or wearable sensors [4, 17]. According to its current privacy level, medical data can be classified as raw, collected, or anonymized data [19].

The different medical data types are stored in and can be retrieved from various data systems some of which are clinical. These are Electronic Health Records (EHR), Patient Data Management Systems (PDMS), Laboratory Information (Management) Systems (LI(M)S), Radiology Information Systems (RIS), Picture Archiving and Communication Systems (PACS), Administrative Systems and Clinical Registries. Non-clinical systems from which medical data can potentially be retrieved are data bases of insurance companies, Mobile Apps, Internet of Things (IoT) and Social Media [11, 14, 17]. The workflow developed in this thesis only considers clinical data systems. Some data sources, e.g. the EHR, contain more than one type of medical data and integrating them with others requires interoperability i.e. by adhering to standards [13]. An upcoming solution for this

are Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR). It is a data standard developed by the healthcare standardization company HL7 enabling information representation and exchange between different types of systems by encoding the respective medical data in modular, interoperable components called "Resources" [4].

The retrieval of the medical research data from the described system is only one of several steps in the complex research data analysis pipeline, which is often pictured as a lifecycle. In 2018, Cox and Tam provided a critical analysis of nine research data and research lifecycles. They came to the conclusion that research and the associated data analysis are so complex that sequential or circular models like a lifecycle do not capture the whole process [20]. However, they can serve as guidelines and have the advantage that they generalize well. Furthermore they emphasize the potential carried by reusing valuable data. A simplistic but well-structured research data lifecycle was compiled in 2015 by Surkis and Read as an introduction for librarians. It pictures the life of clinical research data in five circular-arranged steps which are data creation, data processing, data analysis, data preservation and giving access to data. In the course of data reuse the data creation step can be skipped, i.e. after giving access to the data it is directly processed again. However, it is also possible to create additional data and integrate it with the reused data [21]. A visualization of the described data lifecycle can be found in figure 3.1 on the left. The data-centric research lifecycle proposed by the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is located next to it. Just as the model by Surkis and Read the DDI lifecycle pictures five circular-arranged steps. In contrast to the former, here the steps data processing and data analysis as well as data preservation and giving access to data are collapsed, respectively. The two slots becoming empty by doing so are filled by the steps discovery & planning on position one and long term management on position five. This results in the following order of steps: discovery & planning, initial data collection, final data preparation & analysis, publication & sharing and long-term management¹.

FIGURE 3.1: Research Data Lifecycles according to Surkis and Read [21] (left) and the Data Documentation Initiative¹ (right).

¹<https://www.eddi-conferences.eu/about/>

Besides the described data-centric lifecycles there are research- or process-centric models. A well-known model representing the research process of data mining is the Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) model (c.f. figure 3.2). It starts with gaining business understanding followed by data understanding. These steps are alternating until the project preparation is finished. Afterwards, the data is prepared followed by building the data mining model. These steps alternate until the data is sufficiently prepared for the model to be build successfully. The trained model is then evaluated with two options to progress. Either the performance of the model is good enough for the model to be deployed or the evaluation reveals that an important point has been missed while gaining business understanding. In the latter case the project goes back to the business understanding step [23]. This thesis aims at creating a widely applicable workflow for all steps prior to building the model.

FIGURE 3.2: The Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) model. Figure taken from Heinrichs [22]

FIGURE 3.3: Preprocessing pipeline for clinical research data. Figure taken from Sun et al. [24].

As described in the research data lifecycles above, medical data needs to be pre-processed after it has been retrieved. One reason for this is that the data must be brought to a format that is suited for the analysis or for training a model. Another reason is that the data must have a certain level of quality for the MDS project to be successful. Poor quality input data leads to poor quality results. Thus, it is important

to also check the data quality after a first round of preprocessing and increase it by further preprocessing if necessary, before the analysis of the data or the training of an ML model

start [24, 25]. The data quality check can be performed by applying data quality assessment frameworks like those of Lee et al. or Weiskopf and Weng [26, 27]. Such guidelines also exist for data preprocessing. According to Sun et al., the standard preprocessing pipeline for structured data starts with data cleansing followed by data integration. It continues with data transformation and data reduction and ends with privacy protection (c.f. figure 3.3). For semi- or unstructured data advanced techniques are needed [24]. These are out of the scope of this thesis.

Typical problems of medical data which are to be overcome during data preparation are the low volume, i.e. small sample sizes, the high sparsity of the data and usually poor quality [12]. These limitations of clinical data result from the inherent heterogeneity of treatments, outcomes, study design, analytical methods and approaches for collecting, processing and interpreting data in the medical field [17]. A further speciality about data mining in medicine is that data scientists cannot work in isolation but need medical experts to understand the highly specialized procedures. Thus interdisciplinary and closely collaborating teams are crucial in MDS projects [12].

3.2 FAIR Data in Germany and the European Union

Data must have certain properties to be especially valuable for research. These properties were described in 2016 by Wilkinson et al. in form of the FAIR data paradigm. It requires data to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable [28]. Making data FAIR is referred to as FAIRification. It is very difficult if done retrospectively. So, ideally it should be done right away when a new data set is created [29]. Originally, the FAIR paradigm was developed by and for the life science research community but it is applicable to all scientific fields [30].

In Germany FAIR data is still not a standard. To improve the situation the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has launched the Medical Informatics Initiative (MII) in 2016. After a conceptual phase, four of initially seven consortia have been chosen to represent MII [7, 16]. These are "Data Integration for FUTURE medicine" (DIFUTURE), "Heidelberg - Göttingen - Hannover medical informatics" (HiGHmed), "Medical Informatics in Research and Care in University Medicine" (MIRACUM) and "Smart Medical Information Technology for Healthcare" (SMITH). Their joint approach is to support MDS in Germany by establishing Data Integration Centres (DICs) and junior research groups. It is validated by selected use cases which aim to proof that the concept results in significant benefits. In general, a special focus is set on supporting interoperability, standardization and harmonization. The consortia have staggered their work into three phases. The first two phases, namely the previously mentioned conceptual phase and the development and networking phase have already come to an end. Results of

the conceptual phase have been published by MII and each individual consortium in form of papers in 2018 [7, 15, 16, 31–33]. Further results, including some of the development and networking phase can be found on the MII website². Most recently the consortia started phase three which aims for consolidation and further development [16].

Another initiative supporting FAIR data in Germany is the "Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.v." which was founded in October 2020 by Germany's federal government and all its federal states [34]. It addresses typical problems of research data sets like decentralized storage, strict project reference and availability being limited to the duration of the respective project [35]. The goal of NFDI is to enable a systematic and sustainable research data management including data retrieval, networking, integration and usage to eventually increase efficiency, effectiveness and societal benefit of research. Compliance to the FAIR data paradigm is in the forefront of this. Hence, development of standards for data and metadata is one of the key efforts of NFDI besides the actual construction of the infrastructure [34, 35]. To achieve its goals the NFDI association currently compiles a collection of interdisciplinary consortia in a three round selection process. The process will end in summer 2022 eventually resulting in 30 NFDI consortia which collaborate to foster FAIR research data management [34]. Besides the German initiatives, there are European efforts to FAIRify research data. For instance, the Gaia-X project launched by Germany and France in June 2019 supports findability and accessibility of research data by creating an open data structure representing European values [36]. Specifically, the project aims at developing an infrastructure which enables secure and trusted data exchange between European partners. Thereby, fostering data sovereignty is the central objective but also privacy, surveillance, transparency, and censorship are considered while scientific progress shall not be hindered [37]. In 2021, Gaia-X and NFDI launched a shared project called "FAIR Data Spaces". Its goal is the establishment of a European shared data cloud with strict compliance to the FAIR data paradigm [35]

3.3 Data Protection

Healthcare data is a form of sensitive personal data. As such it requires special protection to ensure patient privacy [9, 38, 39]. This can be achieved by privacy enhancing measures like encryption of data during transmission processes, access monitoring and control via authentication or de-identification [3, 18, 40, 41]. Because de-identification in form of pseudonymization and anonymization has a central role in current data protection laws (c.f. section 6.1.1) and anonymity of the patients is furthermore a key concern in ethical MDS I will elaborate more on de-identification in the following [6].

²<https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/en/about-initiative/results>

The goal of both pseudonymization and anonymization is to make re-identification of individuals in a data set impossible or at least increase the necessary effort significantly. To achieve this, pseudonymization reversibly replaces identifiers with pseudonyms which can potentially be translated back using a mapping stored by a trusted party. In contrast, anonymization deletes identifiers irreversibly [42]. Since the beginning of this century, a lot of research on privacy preservation through anonymization has been performed. This research identified types of privacy attacks on data sets, created mathematical privacy models and designed privacy-preserving algorithms [38, 39, 42–48].

The European Data Protection Board and its predecessor, the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, defined which privacy attacks are necessary to be prevented when compiling a data set. These are "singling-out", "linkability" and "inference" [49]. Singling-out is the process of identifying all database records belonging to a certain individual without having further knowledge e.g. from other databases. Linkability describes the capability of an attacker to link records in one or more databases belonging to a single individual or a group of individuals. Inference is defined as the deduction of sensitive information about an individual with significant probability [48–50]. Possible consequences of these attacks are the disclosure of an individual's identity (identity disclosure), its attributes (attribute disclosure) or its membership in a database (membership disclosure) [51]. Besides these types of privacy attacks, different types of attacker models have been described in literature because for correctly assessing the risk of an attack it is crucial to consider an attacker's position, capabilities and resources [39]. The attacker models include the prosecutor, the journalist and the marketer attacker model. Both in the prosecutor as well as in the journalist attacker model the attacker tries to re-identify a specific individual. The difference is that in the prosecutor model the attacker knows that the individual is contained in the data set while in the journalist model the attacker does not have this background knowledge. In contrast to that, in the marketer model the attacker tries to re-identify as many individuals as possible without targeting any specific individual [52].

Moreover, in data protection different kinds of attributes are discriminated. Every attribute collected for individuals in a data set is either identifying, quasi-identifying, sensitive or insensitive. Identifying attributes are those directly disclosing the identity of an individual such as the name or any ID (e.g. tax ID). A list of such features can be found in U.S. Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) or in the Policy 007 Implementation Guideline for anonymous sharing of clinical trials data of the European Medical Agency (EMA) [14, 50]. Quasi-identifying attributes are those which can lead to the disclosure of an individual's identity if they are considered simultaneously and background knowledge is applied. A sensitive attribute carries information that could cause harm for the affected individual if it is disclosed. All attributes which are not identifying, quasi-identifying or sensitive are classified as insensitive. Identifying attributes need to

be removed, on quasi-identifying attributes we need to ensure sufficient protection of re-identification and on sensitive attributes, disclosure needs to be compromised. Insensitive data can remain as it is [19, 50, 51, 53]

According to Yu, the mathematical models for privacy protection in databases can be divided into two groups: (1) the theoretical framework of privacy and (2) data clustering. The former uses information theory to assess the possible information gain of an attacker while the latter follows the approach of an individual hiding in the crowd. Yu names ϵ -differential privacy as a model following the theoretical approach. Three models are listed which follow the data clustering approach. These are k -anonymity, l -diversity and t -closeness [19]. To establish k -anonymity the data needs to be altered in a way that when considering all quasi-identifying attributes each record must not be distinguishable from at least $k - 1$ other records. These at least k records sharing the respectively same values for all quasi-identifying attributes build an equivalence class [43]. k -anonymity can successfully compromise singling-out and linkability attacks but lacks the capability of additionally preventing attribute disclosure through inference. To remedy this deficiency, l -diversity was introduced in 2007 by Machanavajjhala et al. It demands that in every equivalence class determined by the quasi-identifying attributes each sensitive attribute takes on at least l different values [44]. Later in 2007, Li et al. have shown that l -diversity cannot prevent probabilistic information gain for attackers in presence of background knowledge [19]. Therefore, l -diversity is not sufficient to fully compromise attribute disclosure. As an alternative, Li et al. proposed the model of t -closeness. It demands that the distribution of each sensitive attribute in every equivalence class differs from the distribution of this attribute in the whole data set by at most t [45, 49]. The Article 29 Data Protection Working Party use the data clustering approach in their data protection advice. In particular, they propose using k -anonymity to prevent singling-out and linkability attacks. Additionally, t -closeness should be established to compromise inference [49, 50].

Making a data set fulfilling the demands of privacy models is part of an anonymization process. To achieve compliance with the demands of k -anonymity, l -diversity and t -closeness, approaches like generalization or suppression can be applied. Generalization refers to grouping single attribute values and replacing these values with the group label. Suppression denotes the deletion of attributes (attribute suppression) or records (record or tuple suppression) [43, 46, 51, 54].

However, altering the data also influences data quality [14, 42]. Fine-tuning of how much the data is perturbed is done by choosing the parameters k , l and t as well as how and to what extent generalization and suppression are applied. These decisions must be made in a way that the risk for affected individuals is sufficiently reduced while the data quality remains as high as possible. The solution for this optimization problem differs

for every data science project and highly depends on the characteristics of the data itself [38]. Besides this project-specificity, another challenge is that systematic assessment of the remaining identification risk is currently only possible for structured data [14].

In 2014 the anonymization tool ARX has been published by Prasser et al. Since then it is continuously improved and extended. It is provided in form of a graphical interface as well as a java library both supporting all outlined privacy models, generalization and suppression. Furthermore, it enables the calculation of risk scores according to different types of privacy attacks [51, 54].

3.4 Workflow Design and Performance Assessment

According to Tschüter et al., a workflow is a conceptual and coordinated sequence of work items or applications accompanied by a description of their dependencies. As a conceptual entity it abstracts from details regarding implementation or resources [55]. In 2003, van der Aalst et al. compiled a list of 20 workflow patterns classified into six groups. These are basic control flow patterns, advanced branching and synchronization patterns, structural patterns, patterns involving multiple instances, state-based patterns and cancellation patterns [56]. The paper has a very high number of citations emphasizing its big influence on the research field of workflow development and analysis.

A workflow is said to be efficient if it exhibits low cost and simultaneously high performance in terms of its results and the time it takes to achieve those [55, 57, 58]. However, the cost of a workflow can also be seen as a performance aspect [59]. To evaluate a workflow's performance two approaches can be taken which are executing or simulating it. In both cases previously specified metrics which are adapted to the workflow requirements are measured [58, 60].

Workflow performance estimation is traditionally a prominent topic in High Performance Computing (HPC). Here, profiling parallel executions as well as determining statistics about runtime and resource allocation play a central role [55, 58]. Furthermore, dependencies between process steps should be examined since delays in one step are propagated to all depending work steps. The typically monitored workflow components in HPC are I/O, communication and computation processes [55]. In HPC it is a well-known fact that changing a single workflow parameter can cause a significant change in performance [58]. Other fields in which assessing a workflow's performance is important are grid and cloud computing. Here, the challenge is to maximize the performance by optimizing job scheduling and resource allocation. Performance metrics for grid or cloud computing workflows can be the job makespan, the aggregated or averaged execution time, the fairness of job scheduling as well as the estimated job cost in terms of needed resources [57, 59]. Moreover, there is domain-specific research on workflow performance assessment. Wratten

et al. provide an comparison and classification of 12 bioinformatics workflow managers. They identify sharability, scalability and reproducibility as the main goals for bioinformatics workflows. To achieve reproducibility documenting data provenance and making the workflow portable are crucial. Furthermore, re-entrancy into the workflow after it was terminated unexpectedly should be possible without re-doing computations [61]. Special about scientific computational workflows is that they typically have to process huge amounts of data and deal with heterogeneous distributed resources [60].

So far, the focus was on only purely computational workflows. However, considering that a high amount of human collaboration and communication is needed in MDS, which was outlined in section 3.1, the DAI process here resembles more a business process than a purely computational workflow. Business process optimization is typically done by modeling the process. A variety of modeling approaches was reviewed by Grabis and Chandra in 2016 [62]. A necessary component in this endeavour is using a modeling language that enables visualization of the created model. For this purpose, the large and feature rich Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) language is widely used in business process modeling [63, 64]. Another crucial part of the modeling process is identifying and describing roles and actors [65, 66].

Now the question remains, how to identify the required components of a workflow and its framework. A well-tried approach for industrial process optimization is the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle proposed by Deming and Shewhart in 1986 [67, 68]. In the first step (Plan) the process is planned based on previously made experiences and review of relevant documents. Afterwards, the process is executed (Do) and evaluated (Check) which constitutes steps two and three. The last step (Act) is to improve the originally designed process based on the evaluation of its actual execution. Because of its simplicity and simultaneous ability to enable informed decision making in process optimization it is still used today [65].

Applying the methodology mentioned above in a scientific field brings special challenges. For instance, data stewardship in science is a heavily evolving field. Hence, developers of workflows which describe scientific DAI processes need to anticipate technological and regulatory changes. This means, continuous reviews and updates are needed [65]. Therefore, it is advisable to develop a workflow in a system-agnostic manner so that it is easier adaptable to changes [60]. Another important criterion for a DAI workflow is that the resulting data set should be usable, i.e. that it has integrity and is FAIR [28–30, 65]. In the course of ensuring this, the result of a DAI workflow should provide information on data provenance, i.e. the workflow should include documenting the whole data set processing in the form of metadata [61, 65].

Coming to workflows in the MDS domain, in 2020, Ismail et al. proposed an evaluation framework for the performance of healthcare records management systems. They identified similar important performance metrics as researchers in other domains (c.f. above). These are the task execution time and the amount of transferred data. However, besides that, they also mention security and privacy aspects like data confidentiality, integrity, repudiation and audit as decisive [69].

Chapter 4

Use Case: Cancer of Unknown Primary (CUP)

I gathered practical DAI experience by compiling a reusable data set for the CUP use case of the Center for Integrated Oncology (CIO) Cologne. The goal of the CUP use case is to develop an AI-based system predicting the Location Of the Primary tumor (LOP) given structured clinical data of cancer patients. This system will eventually be deployed to predict the most probable LOP for cancer patients whose primary tumor remains undetected. These are diagnosed to have a Cancer of Unknown Primary (CUP). By solely using structured clinical data that is gathered for each cancer patient by default the project aims at enabling LOP prediction which neither requires time-consuming advanced preprocessing of data nor costly additional tests and examination (c.f. section 4.2). Thus, it can easily be deployed in daily clinical practice. The research team working on the CUP use case is led by a clinical oncologist. Further involved researchers are two medical doctoral students one of which is the medical part of the interdisciplinary MDS team (Devina Soenarto) while the other manually compiles the data set containing the CUP patients. This is needed because they are not structurally documented yet. The data for the project is provided by the radiology department, the clinical cancer registry and the laboratory archive of UHC.

4.1 Medical Background

A patient is diagnosed with the CUP syndrome if cancerous metastases are found but no primary tumor. The LOP cannot even be determined after extensive diagnostic effort with standard methods [70]. As a result, the treatment of 80 to 90% of all CUP patients is unspecific. It cannot be adjusted to the LOP resulting in an overall poor prognosis and a median survival expectancy of only 4 to 10 months [71, 72]. For 10% - 20% of CUP

patients, however, applying advanced molecular analysis in the laboratory can determine the most probable LOP with an accuracy of 85% to 90% by identifying clinically similarly cancer entities. The clinical similarity of a CUP case to a known cancer entity means that the patient will respond similarly to any kind of treatment. Thus, determining the most probable LOP enables choosing a more specific treatment leading to an increased survival expectancy of 15 to 20 months [72, 73]. Hence, LOP prediction improves the prognosis for CUP patients significantly. The initial inability to find the LOP and the remaining uncertainty even when applying advanced molecular diagnostics may result from the undetectability of the primary tumor with current diagnostic procedures, from the missing distinctiveness of metastases and the primary tumor or from the non-existence of the primary tumor [72, 74]. All these theories could be correct simultaneously in the sense that CUP is an own cancer entity characterized by metastatic spread without any primary tumor ("real" CUP) but some cases are incorrectly diagnosed to be CUP because of diagnostic limitations ("fake" CUP) [75]. This is supported by the fact that the primary tumor is only found in 50%-85% of the autopsies on CUP patients suggesting that a primary tumor only exists for some CUP cases [70, 72, 74, 75]. The vast majority of primary tumors found in autopsies of CUP patients are located in the lung (27%), pancreas (24%), kidney (8%), liver (8%), genitals (7%), colorectal area (7%) or the upper gastrointestinal tract (GI) (6%) [72, 74, 75].

4.2 Previous Medical Data Science Approaches

The previous section made clear that well-working LOP prediction can have significant beneficial influence. Over the last four years, some approaches aiming for LOP prediction it have been developed. In 2017 Kang et al. created the CancerLocator. It is a probabilistic approach using the whole-genome methylation profile of solid tumors as well as the methylation profile of plasma cell-free DNA to perform LOP prediction based on likelihood estimations. Their project data set contained methylation data of 2471 cancer patients retrieved from the public data base "The Cancer Genome Atlas" (TCGA), data of 78 cancer patients from two related cancer studies and data of eight own patients. The Pearson's Correlation Coefficient between the true LOPs and the LOPs predicted by the CancerLocator was determined to be 0.975. The root mean squared error of the system was 0.074 on the test data set. However, they only considered breast, liver and lung cancer samples. Thus, it remains unclear whether the approach also serves well for general LOP prediction [76]. Two years ago Zhao et al. proposed CUP-AI-Dx, a 1-D Inception CNN predicting the most probable LOP as well as the molecular subtype for 11 of the 32 considered LOP classes. As the input data, this neural network (NN) took the whole transcriptional profile of primary tumors consisting of individual expression levels of 20.531 genes. The project data set had a size of 18.217 samples which were exported from

TCGA and the International Cancer Genome Consortium (ICGC). In cross-validation on this data CUP-AI-Dx achieved a top-1 accuracy of 98.54%. On the test set the accuracy was determined to be 96.7%. In clinical validation the NN revealed an accuracy of 86.96% and 72.46% on two data sets from the US and Australia [77]. Last year Nguyen et al. presented the "Cancer of Unknown Primary Location Resolver" (CUPLR). It is an ensemble of 33 RFs each performing the binary classification of distinguishing one of the 33 considered LOPs from all other LOPs. The input for these RFs was the genomic mutation pattern consisting of 4122 features and most of the 6820 samples were taken from metastatic tissue. This increases the usability of the system for CUP cases because in them only metastatic tissue is available. The project data was retrieved from Hartwig Medical Foundation (Hartwig) and Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes consortium (PCAWG) [78].

The approaches described so far all use data that is not generated for cancer patients by default. Thus, they introduce additional tests and costs for hospitals. To overcome this issue, Lu et al. presented "Tumor Origin Assessment via Deep Learning" (TOAD) last year. It is a CNN-based approach predicting the LOP considering the patient's gender and histopathological whole-slide images generated for found metastases. The project data set contained 32,537 images generated between 2004 and 2020 and the respective gender of 29,107 patients. Because it was a purely retrospective study without any patient recruitment, gathering the informed consent of the patients was not obligatory. TCGA, the Clinical Proteomic Tumour Analysis Consortium (CPTAC) and clinical data systems of Brigham and Women's hospital served as the data sources for the project. On data of non-CUP patients, TOAD achieved accuracy scores of 83% and 80% in internal and external validation, respectively. The top-3 accuracy scores are given by 96% and 93%, respectively. On data of CUP patients, it achieved a top-1 accuracy score of 60% and a top-3 accuracy score of 82%. So, applying TOAD narrows the number of candidate LOPs for physicians with an accuracy almost as high as that achieved by the models which apply data that needs to be generated additionally [79].

Except for TOAD, all described approaches solely used data from non-CUP patients for training and evaluation. This approach will not work if CUP is indeed an own cancer entity. However, there still might be "fake" CUP cases due to limitations in diagnostics. Their LOP could be predicted by the proposed models and even for "real" CUP cases, the models could be useful. Applying them identifies clinically similar cancer entities for the cases and the clinical similarity could also be considered when choosing a suitable treatment [80].

Chapter 5

Methodology

The objective of this thesis is designing a DAI workflow for MDS (c.f. chapter 2). The knowledge required for that was acquired by reviewing relevant literature as well as gaining own hand-on DAI experience in a clinical use case. Taking this dual approach as an information source I developed a draft of a conceptual DAI workflow accompanied by a surrounding framework of roles, actors, system concepts and security levels as well as a performance evaluation guideline. This draft was shown to and discussed with employees of UHC in the course of expert interviews. In the first place, their feedback was used to improve and validate my conceptualization. Besides that, I enriched the insights I got during literature review by the valuable insights from the experts to describe the current situation of clinical DAI processes. The following sections describe the individual steps in more detail.

5.1 Identify Challenges in Data Access and Integration

As a basis for the creation of a reliable and adaptable DAI workflow I firstly analyzed the challenges of DAI in a hospital setting. To get a comprehensive overall picture I reviewed current literature examining four different types of challenges: legal, ethical, technical, and organisational challenges. The results of this analysis can be found in section 6.1.

The literature review was performed using the scientific search engine Google Scholar and various combinations of the search terms listed in table 5.1. Furthermore, I applied the snowballing approach described by Wohlin in 2014 according to which not only a found paper is reviewed but also the papers cited by it (backward snowballing) and the papers citing it (forward snowballing) [81].

Concretely, at first I defined the search terms in table 5.1. As recommended by Wohlin, using various combinations of these terms in search queries I then compiled a start set of papers for the snowballing method. In the following iterations I applied forward as well as

backward snowballing with Google Scholar. To support actuality of the results I mainly included papers which have not been published before 2017. Papers which are older than 5 years were only considered if they were identified as highly influential by other papers. Further exclusion criteria were field-specificity when the field was not "medicine", country-specificity when the country was not Germany and non-availability of the full text. All chosen papers were written in English or German and discussed relevant challenges of the DAI process without being too specific about a single disease, project or detail in the process. To support reproducibility of the literature review I signed out of any online accounts and deleted all cookies from the browser before I started searching for papers.

Purpose	Search terms
Domain specification	medicine, medical, clinical, healthcare
Subject specification	data, information
Activity specification	integration, access, collection, compilation
Aspect specification	technical, legal, ethical, organizational
Location specification	Germany, North Rhine-Westphalia, Data Integration Centres
Further specifications	status, review

TABLE 5.1: Search terms used for literature review with the respective purpose for which they were included in search queries.

5.2 Data set compilation in the CUP use case

To gain in-depth knowledge about the DAI processes at UHC I took over the role of a technical data scientist in a clinical use case of CIO Cologne. This was their CUP use case which aims for the development of a primary tumor prediction system (c.f. section 4). I joined the CUP use case while it was still in the early phase of project planning. Together with the CIO team and medical doctoral student Devina Soenarto I developed the project design, initiated the data access and performed data preprocessing. Eventually, I checked the data quality together with Devina Soenarto who provided the necessary domain knowledge.

The steps of project preparation were determined by the project managers of CIO Cologne. The project design decisions were mainly made by the project leader who is a clinical oncologist at CIO Cologne. The project management team, Devina Soenarto and I attended regular interdisciplinary team meetings with the project leader in which the decisions and possible alternatives were discussed.

The data access took place as determined in the team meetings during the project preparation phase. Concretely, I was in close contact with the data providers assisting them to perform the data export as we specified it in the project management document.

The data preprocessing steps were mainly taken from Sun et al. [24] who proposed a preprocessing pipeline for healthcare data in 2018 including data cleaning, integration,

transformation, reduction and privacy protection (c.f section 3.1). However, I reordered these steps according to the needs of the CUP use case. The data reduction was mainly performed in the project preparation already as we defined the features and cases we want to include in the data set in the project management documents sent to the data protection officer and the Ethics Committee (EC). To start the actual preprocessing we firstly added a data inspection step which is necessary to examine the quality of the raw data to afterwards know which transformations are needed [25, 27]. Then we changed the order of transformation and integration to foster data security and privacy. The reason for that is that a fully integrated data set provides more information per patient than the individual data sets which means that not only more sensitive information is present but also that the re-identification risk is higher in a fully integrated data set. Thus, we calculated additionally needed features and deleted the features not needed anymore after this calculation before integration of individual data sets took place. Moreover this means that privacy protection was spread over several other steps instead of being an individual step at the end of the preprocessing pipeline. To check whether further preprocessing is needed we finished the pipeline with a final data quality assessment. Because I used further methodology to ensure data privacy protection and examine data quality I will outline these aspects of the preprocessing pipeline in more detail below.

Privacy Protection To protect the privacy and security of the patients whose data was accessed for the CUP use case, the personal data files were encrypted before they were sent to the data science team. Additionally, the transfer took place via a secure data share platform. After preprocessing the data (c.f. above), Devina Soenarto and me additionally anonymized the patient data which is an important pre-processing step when applying ML in medical research (c.f. sections 3.3 and 6.1.1). At first, all selected input features were analyzed regarding their risk of re-identification. We took the specification of identifying features from the EMA Policy 007 Implementation Guideline [82]. Quasi-identifying features were determined following the approach of Jakob et al. based on the framework of Malin et al. which calculates a re-identification score for every feature based on the aspects replicability, resource availability and distinguishability of feature expressions. Features whose score exceeds a value of 5 are considered as quasi-identifying [50, 83]. The values of these features were generalized in a way that the re-identification risk becomes as small as possible while the usability of the data remains high. TMF as well as the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party suggest to apply k -Anonymity (c.f. section 3.3) to achieve this [49, 84]. We followed this recommendation by aiming for k -Anonymity with k being set to a value such that the re-identification risk is reasonably low. However, our data is only shared with other parties of UHC and also only via secure data paths (c.f. above). Thus, the re-identification risk can be higher as for data sets that are made publicly available. For anonymization I applied the ARX anonymization tool which is recommended and used by the TMF in workshops [84].

Data Quality Assessment In order to assess data quality I checked some of the data quality dimensions proposed by Weiskopf and Weng in 2013 [27]. The proposed data quality dimensions are completeness, correctness, concordance, plausibility and currency. To assess these Weiskopf and Weng propose seven methods which are a comparison with the gold standard, checking data element agreement, checking data source agreement, performing distribution comparison, checking validity, performing a log review and checking element presence. I chose this framework because it was developed especially for the medical domain. Weiskopf and Weng defined it for full EHRs but I use it only for a subset of such namely the clinical data accessed in the CUP use case. Furthermore, due to time constraints I set a special focus on the following two dimensions.

I tested the records for completeness, i.e. I checked whether the chosen input features are available for the majority of cancer cases. As another aspect of completeness I checked how many truly different cases there are in the data set. Considering the low number of chosen input features it was plausible that there may be different cancer cases having the same value for each selected input feature. As a second important dimension, I analyzed the plausibility of the data by checking the variability of each feature and looking for outliers.

5.3 Workflow Design

The workflow developed by this thesis involves a lot of human communication instead of being a pure sequence of computations and information transfer. Hence, it resembles a business process workflow more than a classical computational workflow. For this reason, I used a methodological approach from the domain of business process optimization for designing the conceptualized DAI workflow. Specifically, I applied the PDCA method for business workflow development which has been described in section 3.4.

The "Plan" step was performed by reviewing field-specific relevant literature (c.f. section 5.1) and gaining hands-on experiences in the CUP Use Case of CIO Cologne (c.f. section 5.2).

The "Do" step afterwards consisted of modeling and visualizing a DAI workflow draft. This was done using the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) framework, which is a long established and widely applicable standard for business process modeling (c.f. section 3.4). Concretely, for individual workflow steps as well as for the big picture workflow I created BPMN models using the webtool bpmn.io¹. The models can be found in appendix A. The analysis leading to these results is outlined in section 6.3.4. Moreover, a workflow as a sequence of work items accompanied by a description of their dependencies (c.f. section 3.4) needs a surrounding framework including roles and actors, system

¹<https://bpmn.io/>

concepts and security levels to be fully specified [65, 66]. Thus, I also developed such a surrounding framework based on the knowledge I gained in the "Plan" step. The results are contained in sections 6.3.1, 6.3.2 and 6.3.3. Last but not least, I realized the need for additionally providing a guideline to evaluate concrete instances of the proposed conceptualized workflow. This guideline was created by applying the knowledge from previous work in the domain of process optimization outlined in section 3.4. The considerations leading to my proposal for such a guideline are documented in section 6.3.5. All visual results of the "Do" step can be found in appendix A. They are not contained in the thesis itself to avoid confusion with the visualization of the final results.

The "Do" step was followed by the "Check" step in which I performed expert interviews with employees of UHC to check the quality and realisability of the workflow draft, the surrounding framework and the performance evaluation guideline. Details about the conduct of these interviews can be found in section 5.4. The analysis of the feedback I received is outlined in section 6.4.1.

Eventually, the "Act" step was performed by improving the BPMN models, the surrounding framework and the performance evaluation guideline developed in the "Do" step according to the feedback I received from the experts. The visualization and explanation of these improved conceptualizations can be found in sections 7.3.1, 7.3.2 and 7.3.3.

PDCA Step	Realisation
Plan	Literature review combined with CUP project planning and execution.
Do	Developing a workflow design based on the results from the "Plan" step.
Check	Analyzing the workflow design in expert interviews.
Act	Improving the workflow according to the feedback received from the experts.

TABLE 5.2: Application of the PDCA methodology for designing the Data Access and Integration Workflow.

5.4 Assessment of the Data Access and Integration Workflow

To check the quality and realisability of the DAI workflow draft, the surrounding framework and the performance estimation guideline that were created in the "Do" phase of the PDCA method (c.f. section 5.3) I conducted guided expert interviews with employees of UHC online using the video conference tool Zoom². For each of the four challenge types considered in the literature review (c.f. section 5.1) I chose at least one expert according to the two definitions of "expert" Mergel et al. collected in 2019 [85]. The first is from Bogner et al. stating that an expert is a person with technical, process and interpretative knowledge in relation to their areas of expertise [86]. The second definition stems from

²<https://explore.zoom.us/>

Meuser and Nagel defining an expert to be a person responsible for a concept, an implementation or ability to solve a problem, as someone who has relevant factual knowledge, aggregated or specific knowledge about processes, group behaviors, strategic decisions but also has knowledge, (general) information or privileged access to information [87]. As purely technical experts I invited Feifei Li (Data Scientist at the Institute for Medical Informatics) and Jonathan Okereke (Leader of the technical team at MeDIC Cologne). As technical and organisational experts I chose Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer (Leader of Institute for Genetics, Co-Leader of MeDIC), Scarlett Berressem (Leader of the clinical Cancer Registry), Liliana Lourenco Caldeira (Leader of the radiological Data Science Team), Dr. Ana Grönke (Scientific Project Coordinator at MeDIC Cologne) as well as radiologists Dr. Thorsten P. and Dr. Simon Lennartz. Additionally, I invited A.W. (Operational Manager) as a technical and organisational expert, who indicated the wish to be named with random initials. R.D. (Scientific Manager), who wished to be called not by name but by random initials as well, was invited as an expert in the domain of AI ethics and Dominik Zier (Data Protection Officer of UHC) as an expert in legal matters. An overview of the interview participants and their function at UHC can be found in table 5.3.

Interview participant	Function at University Hospital Cologne
Scarlett Berressem	Leader of the clinical Cancer Registry
Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer	Leader of Institute for Genetics, Co-Leader of MeDIC
Dr. Liliana Caldeira	Leader of radiological data science team
R.D. (random initials)	Scientific Manager
Dr. Simon Lennartz	Radiologist
Feifei Li	Data Scientist at the Institute for Medical Informatics
Jonathan Okereke	Technical Lead at MeDIC Cologne
Dr. Ana Grönke	Scientific Project Coordinator at MeDIC Cologne
Dr. Thorsten P.	Radiologist
A.W. (random initials)	Operational Manager
Dominik Zier	Data Protection Officer

TABLE 5.3: Employees of University Hospital Cologne who participated in the expert interviews.

To prepare the interviews I compiled a list of questions (c.f. appendix B.1) and a summary of my work containing the objective of my thesis, the preliminary surrounding framework, the preliminary workflow BPMN models as well as the preliminary performance estimation guideline (c.f. appendix A). This interview material was sent to all interviewees at least one week before the interview. For the surrounding framework and the performance estimation guidelines the questions concentrated on the correctness and the completeness of my suggested concepts. For the workflow itself the questions concerned improvement potential and realisability. Besides the interview material, a consent form indicating that the participants agree to the interview being conducted online via Zoom, recorded, transcribed and analyzed was filled and signed by all participants prior to the interviews. In

this consent form the interviewees could express wishes regarding the duration of the interview (30 minutes or 60 minutes), the storage of the interview documents, their appearance in this thesis (real name or aliases) and additional check of the interview transcript before its publication in the thesis. All consent forms are available upon request.

Immediately before the interview, the participants could choose the interview language (English or German). During the expert interviews I firstly asked how detailed the respective interviewee looked at the interview material prior to the interview. Afterwards I presented the DAI workflow draft in a level of detail adapted to how detailed the preparation of the participant was. During and after the presentation the participant could ask questions regarding the presented material. Once all questions of the participant have been answered, my preliminary conceptualization was assessed in an interactive discussion between me and the expert. The prepared questions served as additional guidance in these discussions. Each interview was recorded and retrospectively transcribed by use of the automatic transcription software tool happyscribe³. For German interviews happyscribe was additionally used to translate the transcripts to English. The interview transcripts have been manually checked by me and all interviewees that had indicated in their consent form that they want to check their transcript before it is published in this thesis also got the possibility to do so. All interview transcripts can be found in appendix B. Challenges of the DAI process which were described in some interviews were collected in section 6.4.2 and added to those identified by literature review in the analysis of the current status of DAI processes at German university hospitals (c.f. section 7.2). The discussions on the strengths and weaknesses of the proposed DAI workflow were evaluated in section 6.4.1.

³<https://www.happyscribe.com/>

Chapter 6

Analysis

This chapter contains the results of the "Plan", "Do" and "Check" steps of the PDCA workflow development cycle (c.f. section 5.3). Thereby I only describe and analyse. Section 6.1 outlines the legal (6.1.1), ethical (6.1.2), technical (6.1.3) and organizational (6.1.4) challenges of the DAI process identified during literature review. It is followed by section 6.2 in which I describe the DAI process performed in the CUP Use Case introduced in section 4. Finally, section 6.3 contains the conceptualization of the DAI process and its evaluation during the expert interviews. The final workflow which is the result of the "Act" step can be found in chapter 7 together with further discussion.

6.1 Challenges of Data Access and Integration identified during literature review

The main challenges to be addressed in DAI are interoperability, harmonisation, data quality, data privacy, patient consent and data use and access rules [15, 16]. All these high level challenges have different dimensions to be considered which are legal and regulatory, ethical, technical and organizational aspects representing low level challenges themselves. Although I analyzed each of them individually in separate sections it is to be noted that they cannot be considered fully independently because they overlap and influence each other [6].

A summary of the main low level challenges outlined in this chapter arranged by the high level challenge dimension they address can be found in figure 6.1. In the following sections I will elaborate more on these challenges, their origin and possible measures to meet them. All these insights were gained solely during literature review (c.f. section 5.1). In section 7.2 I enrich the findings from the following analysis by personal experiences in the CIO CUP Use Case (c.f. section 6.2).

Legal Challenges	Ethical Challenges	Technical Challenges	Organizational Challenges
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insecurities resulting from a variety of laws and DPCs • Finding a correct legal basis (consent-based vs. scientific exemption) • Ensuring a number of legal concepts and principles • Identifying suitable technical and organizational data protection measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade-off between ethical rights of treated patients and the beneficent of scientific progress • Overprotectiveness of deciding committees • Concerns and insecurities of treated patients, missing trust • Data Bias challenging fairness • Complexity of data pipeline makes checking ethical compliance difficult • Physician should not decide alone on data access and reuse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data quality issues, missing values, sparsity • Inconsistencies leading to lack of interoperability • Lack of structured data • Ensuring data protection and patient privacy • Dealing with data bias 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity and diversity of the DAI process • Managing (big) interdisciplinary teams • Lack of personnel explicitly trained in MDS • Requirement of defining the project plan early, lack of flexibility • Insecurities both of interdisciplinary teams and patients • Ensuring data security and privacy

FIGURE 6.1: Challenges of the DAI process identified during literature review.

6.1.1 Legal and Regulatory Challenges

The current legal and regulatory framework for MDS in Germany leads to high effort and insecurities for researchers, especially if different federal states are involved. In 2017, Krawczak and Weichert analyzed the situation resulting from the new European and German law which was decided on in 2016 and concluded that the German legal framework for MDS is remote from practice and progress inhibiting [88]. In a recent publication Weichert emphasizes this point further [89]. In the following, I outline in more detail which special challenges are to be overcome in the DAI process in Germany and at MeDIC Cologne, in particular.

The Legal and Regulatory Framework

Clinical data carries sensitive health-related and personal information [3, 9, 38, 39]. Therefore, ensuring data protection and security is crucial in MDS projects. From a governance or organisational perspective, it can be facilitated by establishing regulations in form of laws or concepts. Laws affecting DAI at MeDIC Cologne are the constitutions of the European Union (EU) and Germany, data protection laws and the civil and criminal law provisions on medical confidentiality. The relevant data protection laws include the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union (EU), the German "Bundesdatenschutzgesetz" (BDSG) and the "Datenschutzgesetz" of the federal state North Rhine-Westphalia (DSG NRW) [9, 88, 90–95]. Thereby, the GDPR grants rights to the individual EU states to concretize measures or add limitations in their own data protection laws. Similarly, the data protection laws of the German federal states can make amendments to the laws contained by the BDSG [88, 91]. The constitutions of the EU

and Germany are given by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFR) and the Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany (GG), respectively [88].

The laws provide a general legal basis for MDS in Germany without being very specific [88, 90]. More concrete guidelines on how to access, integrate and use personal sensitive data are provided by site- and organization-specific Data Protection Concepts (DPCs). Data protection at UHC is specified in the UHC Data Protection Management Concept and implemented by the UHC DPC. The latter is a set of 32 process descriptions each supporting data protection. These data protection processes define steps to be taken when the respective process is executed. Additionally, DAI at MeDIC is governed by the DPC of the MII because MeDIC is part of the MII consortium HiGHmed (c.f. sections 2.2 and 3.2). In projects which are independent of MII it is not obligatory to consult the DPC of the MII but it is still strongly advisable. For this concept was created in collaboration with the Medical Ethics-Committees in Germany (AK-EK) and data protection oversight agencies for the German federal states and it is based on German data protection templates developed together with TMF [16].

Definitions

Especially interesting for the DAI process and the regulations outlined in the following is how the legal framework defines the terms "personal data", "sensitive data", "pseudonymization" and "anonymization". GDPR and BDSG provide their own definitions in Art. 4 and §46, respectively. Additional definitions are given in GDPR recitals. DSG NRW §4 takes over the definitions of GDPR Art.4 by referencing it and adds a definition for "anonymization".

Personal data According to BDSG §46(1) and GDPR Art.4(1), "personal data" means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person;" (GDPR Art.4(1)). The BDSG §46 (1) is the German translation of this.

Sensitive data The term "sensitive data" is defined by GDPR Recital 51 as "personal data which are, by their nature, particularly sensitive in relation to fundamental rights and freedoms". As such they "merit specific protection as the context of their processing could create significant risks to the fundamental rights and freedoms" (GDPR Recital 51).

Pseudonymization According to BDSG §46(5) and GDPR Art.4(5), "pseudonymization" means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to

technical and organizational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person” (GDPR Art.4(5)). Again the BDSG definition is the German translation of the GDPR definition. In contrast to definitions from previous EU regulations, this definition of ”pseudonymization” in the GDPR improves clarity regarding the status of pseudonymized data by determining that it is personal data [91].

Anonymization Recital 26 of GDPR states that anonymous data is data ”which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable.” It does not differentiate between anonymous and anonymized data [91]. Only DSG NRW specifically defines the process of anonymization. According to §4 DSG NRW, the term ”anonymization” means the alteration of personal data in such a way that the individual details about personal or factual circumstances can no longer be attributed to a specific or identifiable natural person or can only be attributed to a specific or identifiable natural person with a disproportionate effort in terms of time, costs and work effort.

Content of laws affecting the DAI process

Constitutional principles which are to be considered when accessing and integrating healthcare data are the protection of health (GG Art.2(2), CFR Art. 3, 35), the right to informational self-determination (GG Art.2(1) in conjunction with Art.1(1), CFR Art.8), the professional freedom of medical service providers (GG Art. 12, CFR Art. 15) but also the freedom of science (GG Art.5(3), CFR Art.13) [88]. These principles are the basis for the data protection laws of the EU, Germany and North Rhine-Westphalia whose content I will summarize in the following.

In general, the GDPR prohibits the usage of sensitive data (Art.9(1)). However, in Art.9(2) some special conditions are outlined under which this prohibition is lifted [90, 93]. Article 89 of the GDPR states that in these cases suitable guarantees need to be given to affected individuals backed by technical and organizational measures [88, 91]. One of the special conditions is the informed consent of the affected individual allowing the processing of its data. If no informed consent is given, GDPR Article 9(2)(j) allows justifying that a scientific exemption is present, i.e. that the processing of the data has a significant benefit for the society which outweighs possible risks of the affected individual [90, 91]. Both approaches have their shortcomings, though. Getting the informed consent of the patients is especially difficult in retrospective studies, whereas sufficiently justifying a scientific exemption is very difficult in general [14, 90]. In the EU most research projects choose to get the informed consent of the patients [90]. In either way, following the concept of data minimisation or data sparsity is emphasized as an essential measure

by the GDPR Art.89. DSG-NRW additionally demands following the paradigms of earmarking, confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, revisability and transparency when making decisions [95].

A special case of scientific data processing is the retrospective usage of data for another purpose than the original one. This retrospective processing is allowed according to GDPR Recital 50 but GDPR Art.13(3) demands that the affected individuals have to be informed about this further processing. GDPR Recital 62 lifts the notification duty if reaching the affected individual is impossible or requires a disproportionate amount of effort [91].

The BDSG follows a similar approach as the GDPR but eases the restrictions slightly. For instance, it additionally underlines that no informed consent of the affected person is needed if processing the data is scientifically valuable and appropriate data protection measures are taken (§27 (1)). Furthermore, BDSG cuts rights of affected persons granted by GDPR Articles 15, 16, 18 and 21 if these rights hinder research or make progress impossible (BDSG §27(2)). This is allowed by GDPR Art. 89. However, the publication of personal data is still only permitted if the informed consent was given or if it is necessarily needed for the presentation of results (BDSG §27 (4)).

The main challenge I could identify when reviewing the outlined legal restrictions is finding appropriate measures to keep the risk of the involved patients low enough. The laws lack concrete specifications in this respect.

Another challenge are the legal insecurities arising from the need to consider different legal frameworks in projects which transfer and share data between different federal states of Germany, different EU states or even between EU and non-EU states. The supranational GDPR leaves much room for adaptations, limitations and individual interpretations of laws to EU member states [88, 91, 93, 94]. The BDSG allows federal states to restrict or expand individual laws [88, 94].

Measures meeting the legal requirements

As outlined above, the GDPR does not provide concrete measures for data protection but only demands that appropriate technical and organisational measures have to be taken which ensure that the rights of the affected individuals are preserved. On the other hand, anonymized data is not affected by GDPR [90, 91]. Thus, applying the anonymization techniques described in section 3.3 is one possibility to make the data legally usable in a research context.

In contrast to the GDPR, both the BDSG and the DSG NRW provide a list of measures. BDSG §22(2) names as possible data protection measures taking technical and organisational measures, documenting data processing, raising the awareness of those involved, designating a data protection officer, restricting access, pseudonymizing or encrypting the data, ensuring quality and resilience of systems, monitoring the effectiveness of measures

and defining regulations to deal with processing for another than the original purpose. Additionally, the data should be anonymized as early as possible (BDSG §27(3)). DSG-NRW §15 emphasizes that anonymization should always replace pseudonymization if possible and in conjunction with DSG NRW §31, DSG NRW §15 makes the data protection officer an optional measure. The decision which of the outlined measures are appropriate should be made for each project individually considering the current technical state of the art, the respective implementation costs and type, the project scope, circumstances and the purpose of the processing as well as the probability and heaviness of risks for affected individuals (BDSG §22(2), DSG NRW §15).

However, the listed measures still are not very specific. More detailed guidelines about how to choose appropriate measures can be found in the DPCs of MII and UHC. The former contains these guidelines mainly in section 6.2 which is about technical and organisational measures for data protection. The latter is a collection of data protection processes each of which specifies special measures which are to be applied for the respective data protection process. Both DPCs have in common that they do not provide a step for step list of data protection tasks to be done. They rather provide guidance to identify suitable measures. The DPC of UHC additionally places the data protection officer in a central position. Before a new MDS project is launched, the research team needs to describe their project and the individual plan for data protection in a formal proposal to the data protection officer. With this data protection officer, the research team has to agree on a data protection strategy.

Eventually, taking into account everything outlined above, the main legal challenges can be met by thorough project requirements analysis and design combined with intensive communication with the data protection instance. Concretely, the correct legal basis for a project can be found this way. Insecurities coming up in this process due to the variety and unclarity of the legal landscape could be met by data security and privacy teachings for medical data scientists [18, 88]. Last but not least, the challenge of ensuring compliance to the legal principles outlined in this section can be addressed by well-thought project planning specifically considering these principles [88, 91, 95].

Conclusion

The current legal and regulatory framework for MDS in Germany and at MeDIC Cologne, in particular, demands determining appropriate data protection measures for each project individually. Thereby, the personal rights of the affected individuals must be respected and considered just as well as the value of the project for public health. Which safety measures are to be applied is discussed and decided together with the respective data protection officer on a case-by-case basis. These legal burdens are necessary to protect the rights of patients whose data should be processed. On the other hand, they also lead

to a considerable effort for researchers which is not to be neglected when thinking about launching a new MDS project.

Legal challenge	Suitable measure(s)
Insecurities resulting from variety of laws and DPCs	Data security and privacy teachings.
Finding a correct legal basis (consent-based vs. scientific exemption)	Research and discussion with the data protection instance.
Ensuring a number of legal concepts and principles	Develop a well-thought project DPC, anonymize the data as early as possible.
Identifying suitable technical and organizational measures	Discuss options given by laws and DPCs with the data protection officer.

TABLE 6.1: Legal and regulatory challenges of reusing medical data for research purposes indicated in literature and measures suitable to meet them.

As an orientation, Krawczak and Weichert compiled the following list of research regulation principles on the basis of current and previous data protection laws. These should be kept in mind when working with personal data [88]:

1. The data should always be anonymized or at least pseudonymized. If the research context allows it, anonymization is to be preferred.
2. Identifiable personal data may only be processed under appropriate technical and organisational protection measures.
3. If voluntary and informed consent is provided, processing personal sensitive data is always permissible.
4. If no informed consent is provided, processing personal sensitive data is only permissible if the public interest in this processing is big enough.
5. Publishing personal data is only permissible if the respective patient provided informed consent or if the presentation of the research results is impossible otherwise.
6. The protection of personal sensitive data must always be as high as possible in the respective context.

6.1.2 Ethical Challenges

Besides the legal challenges outlined above, there are ethical challenges concerning the DAI process at hospitals. As a central ethical dilemma, I here identified the trade-off between the interests of the patients whose data is to be processed versus those of the patients benefiting from the processing. In the following section I will discuss in more detail how this dilemma arises.

Ethics in Medical Data Science

While ethics has always been a central issue in medicine, it has only gained a lot of attention in AI and thus also in medical AI in recent years. How to conduct ethically good MDS is therefore far from clear and discussions about it are still very vivid [6].

On the one hand, fundamental human rights like the privacy of the patient providing its data need to be protected [3]. Further ethical principles that are to be considered are the ownership of the data, autonomy of the individual, confidentiality, necessity of processing the data combined with its proportionality and non-maleficence [93]. That these are central principles is further emphasized by the IMIA Code of Ethics for Health Professionals demanding to follow the principle of information privacy and disposition, the principle of openness, the principle of security, the principle of the least intrusive alternative as well as the principle of accountability [14]. In the first place, these ethical principles aim for the protection of the patient whose data is to be processed. However, on the other hand, potential benefits of accessing and integrating the data are not to be neglected since beneficence is another central ethical principle [93]. Integration of medical data carries high potential to improve management of healthcare information and eventually healthcare itself. Immediate potential beneficiaries are many, including patients, physicians, hospitals, healthcare authorities, as well regulatory bodies [4]. Progress in MDS can increase healthcare process efficiency, patient safety and clinical risk estimation. Furthermore, it can lead to the development of well-working clinical decision support systems, enable personalized care, and improve healthcare system sustainability [3]. Blindly and strictly protecting privacy at any cost can lead to missed opportunities as it hinders scientists from developing AI systems that can save lives [14]. Hence, the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors concluded that there is an ethical obligation to share and reuse medical data. It is essential to do this in a responsible manner, though [8]. Additionally, to be ethically correct compiled data sets should be as unbiased as possible to ensure that the statistical analyses carried out on these data sets and the prediction models trained on them lead to fair outcomes [3, 6].

The conflict between the protection of the treated patient's ethical rights and scientific progress accompanied by potential benefits for other patients leads to a high ethical complexity when deciding about MDS project proposals. The result of such a decision, which is usually made by ECs, is often a trade-off demanding the preservation of ethical principles while also enabling innovation [4, 14, 32]. However, there is the criticism that most ECs and data protection officers are overprotective as they do not sufficiently consider the benefit DAI would have for the public. Instead they concentrate too much on the risk of the individual patients demanding data protection measures that slow down scientific progress significantly or even make it impossible [96, 97].

Not all but most patients are altruistic allowing the usage of their data if it can help others [14]. A review performed by Skovgaard et al. in 2019 revealed that the majority of EU citizens supports the reuse of medical data for multiple purposes under the condition that it serves further common good. Mentioned concerns include commercialization of data, data security and the use of data against the will of the individual [98]. Furthermore, a central fear of people is to become completely transparent if too much of their personal data is circulated [97]. Mannheimer et al. additionally point out that the data is co-created by the physician and patient. Thus, it is ethically questionable whether the physician may decide to reuse the data without contacting the patient again and getting the informed consent. Moreover, archiving of data and possible later reuse may be uncomfortable for patients and rise concerns regarding anonymity and confidentiality [99]. What reinforces this insecurity is that most people lack knowledge about the actual DAI and data analysis process. This leads to a lack of trust and the fear of misuse. Data about alcohol and substance use as well as data about mental or sexual health was found to be particularly sensitive in this regard due to the stigmatising effect connected with it [98].

A last issue of ethical MDS I found during literature review is that the analysis of the typically very complex MDS data pipelines in terms of their compliance with ethical principles is a major challenge [9]. The complexity of these pipelines results from the variety of clinical data types and formats as well as involved clinical departments (c.f. section 3.1).

Measures enabling ethical processing of medical data

The literature considered in my review proposes several measures for meeting the ethical challenges outlined above. The very central challenge of dealing with the trade-off between a treated patient's ethical rights and the ethical principle of beneficence implemented by reusing medical data can be met by increased planning, research rigor and repeated ethical interrogation [99]. Thereby it is essential to ensure the independence of governing and deciding committees like data protection instances or ECs. Otherwise it cannot be ruled out that projects only get their approval because the execution of the project is in the committees' interest [3].

Another ethical issue concerning these deciding committees is their tendency towards being overprotective. This could be counteracted by increasing their awareness about the beneficial potential of reusing medical data in the course of teachings and trainings [18, 96–98]. Furthermore, such teachings and trainings enhanced by a description of the concrete processes could help to increase the public trust in MDS and the patients' support while decreasing their insecurities [98]. Public presentations of MDS success stories, that immediately demonstrate the possibilities MDS carries, could foster the affected individuals' trust as well [15]. The enhanced trust would help to get the patients' informed consent for reusing their medical data. Having this consent then solves the ethical problem that

the physician should not decide about the data reuse without including the patient [99]. Additionally, the increased patient engagement again leads to a reinforcement of trust [97]. So, we see a self-amplifying effect. However, it should be ensured that the process of obtaining the informed consent is also ethical. If patients feel forced to sign the consent either because they expect positive effects by doing so or negative effects when they refuse to sign, the consent is meaningless [97]. The measures presented so far are more of an organisational nature. For counteracting the issue of data bias leading to ethical unfairness in MDS technical measures are needed, though. These bias mitigation techniques should be applied during data preprocessing [3, 6].

Eventually, to meet the challenge of making the compliance of an MDS pipeline with ethical principles verifiable in the first place, the German ethics council urges that an ease of data integration is needed. This could be facilitated by defining standards for the DAI process and improving the infrastructure at German Healthcare facilities [9].

Conclusion

To conclude, the DAI process carries high ethical complexity due to the conflict between securing the ethical rights of patients whose data is to be processed and the rights of the patients who could potentially benefit from the access, integration and following processing of this data. Moreover, there are several additional ethical pitfalls to be considered even if a decision concerning this trade-off has been made. An overview over the ethical challenges and respectively suitable measures meeting them can be found in table 6.2. Eventually, the ethical correctness of DAI should be decided considering actors involved, followed interests, own risk and opportunity assessments, societal context, beneficiaries and harm bearers. The project should only be executed if the benefits are substantial while harms are tolerable [9].

Ethical challenge	Suitable measure(s)
Trade-off between ethical rights of treated patients and beneficent scientific progress	Increased planning, research rigor and ethical interrogation while ensuring independence of deciding committees.
Overprotectiveness of deciding committees	Increase awareness of the committees by training and teachings.
Concerns and insecurities of treated patients/ missing trust	Offer teachings to impart knowledge about processes, foster patient engagement and provide success stories.
Data bias challenging fairness	Mitigate bias during data preprocessing.
Difficulty to check ethical compliance due to complexity of the MDS data pipeline	Easing the DAI process by defining standards and improve infrastructure.
Physician should not decide alone on data access and reuse	Get the informed consent of the patient.

TABLE 6.2: Ethical challenges of reusing medical data for research purposes indicated in literature and measures suitable to meet them.

6.1.3 Technical Challenges

Some of the legal and ethical conditions outlined above lead to technical challenges in the DAI process. Further technical challenges are caused by the characteristics of clinical research data discussed in section 3.1. In the following I will describe all these technical challenges of the medical DAI process, their origin and possible measures to deal with them.

Challenges of the DAI process requiring technical solutions

As outlined in section 3.1 medical data can have various forms. Heterogeneity of examinations, treatments, outcomes, study designs, data collection purposes and documentation of diseases is a major challenge in the medical DAI process as it leads to heterogeneity of data formats and data availability [4, 15, 17]. In fact, data in the medical domain is more heterogeneous than data in any other field [4].

One consequence of this is the huge amount of observable features per patient [17]. The large size of the feature space in MDS, in turn, leads to high data sparsity due to the so-called "curse of dimensionality" [12, 17]. The sparsity is additionally amplified by the large number of missing values and considerable incompleteness typically found in medical records [7, 12, 17, 24]. The main reason for this is also the above mentioned heterogeneity. Natural variability in diseases leads to different examination and treatment decisions respectively following the medical guidelines for the present disease. Therefore, different patients often differ in which values are available for them. Parameters that are available for one patient may be missing for a second [12, 100]. In 2021 Kindermann et al. examined which data is often missing. Concerning medical features they found that free text fields are usually filled except from "other medication". Numerical fields could be divided into three clusters. Some are never empty, others are sometimes empty and fields of the third cluster are almost always empty. A similar observation was made for the boolean or dropdown fields. Here Kindermann et al. could identify two clusters of fields which are fields with low and fields with high coverage. While a patient's smoking status was almost always available, information about alcohol disorders or depression were only provided for very few patients. Concerning cases Kindermann et al. found that especially higher disease degrees and patients older than 80 years were underrepresented. They suspect the reason for this to be that these patients could not take part in regular examinations due to missing mobility [100].

Another consequence of the high heterogeneity of medical data is its diversity and inconsistencies coming along with that [3, 15, 17, 24]. These inconsistencies include different scales and units for the same parameter, differences in syntax, ontology and terminology as well as whether a parameter is available in a structured manner or not [3, 17]. When considering the latter point, i.e. the availability of features in a structured manner, an observation often made is the general lack of structured data [5, 7, 100]. While free-texts

are more flexible and more efficient in the documentation process structured data enables efficient computation and analyses which is crucial for successful MDS [15]. Furthermore, focusing on the generation of structured data typically results in higher quality, consistency, completeness as well as higher reliability [5]. Due to its advantages for primary care, though, unstructured documentation is currently the standard [15, 97]. To still enable automatized processing of the data the unstructured data is afterwards manually structured in practice. Because this approach is very time consuming and costly structured data is often only available for a small number of patients. Another disadvantage of manual structuring is that data entry errors can occur [14, 100].

The above mentioned challenges lead to a generally very high complexity of medical data that complicates Project Preparation in MDS and the DAI process itself because secondary use needs complete and interoperable data sets [5, 17]. However, besides these challenges arising from the medical data characteristics there are further resulting from the nature of data management systems currently used in clinics. In general these systems are hard to access in a structured way because even if modern EHRs are in place they are still stored in heterogeneous IT systems using different standards like HL7 V2 or DICOM [13, 14, 17]. The data is kept where it is collected and the used data type is determined by the purpose of acquisition [7]. The data that is most easily accessible is the data documented for reimbursement and administration purposes but this is often also biased and insufficiently accurate. So, the purely medical systems should be preferred as data sources [14]. In Germany the situation is further complicated by the fact that instead of fully linked EHRs there are separated inpatient and outpatient care documentations. Both of these consist of several non-connected and function based data bases like registries, biobanks, trial and omics data bases each with their own set of available features, standards and formats [7, 8, 10, 15]. This landscape of isolated data siloes lacking interoperability is a major technical challenge for the data integration process [8, 10]. Partly overlapping sets of stored data additionally lead to redundancies when accessing medical data from several sources [17, 24]. As a significant challenge for the data access itself Haarbrandt et al. identified a lack of openly accessible messaging interfaces complicating assurance of data quality and timely data access [15]. Data transfer and storage are currently still implemented for each project individually making the DAI process inefficiently and prone to errors [32].

The above mentioned challenges mainly arise due to the data systems not being designed for research but for primary care and administrative purposes [7]. Data is created according to specifications of the respectively used data system although it should be the other way round [15]. The system specifications typically state that the data generation and storage occurs transaction-oriented, i.e. data is stored for events like examinations and treatment sessions and tightly coupled to the respective patient. On the other hand, the Extract Transform Load (ETL) process performed when accessing and integrating the

data for research purposes is query oriented, i.e. it aims to access a few certain values for a set of patients. The data systems' transaction orientation conflicts with the query orientation of the ETL process, which typically results in the ETL process having to deal with missing values and inconsistencies [14].

Further technical challenges arise due to the legal and ethical conditions outlined in sections 6.1.1 and 6.1.2. There it has been stated that patient privacy should be ensured by data protection measures like anonymization or encryption. Additionally, the engagement of patients by getting their informed consent should be fostered. Actually implementing this in the DAI process by managing the consents as well as performing data protection poses a major technical challenge clearly recognized in literature [4, 7, 12, 24]. Another ethical aspect requiring a technical solution is the data bias caused e.g. by the missing case groups mentioned above [17, 100].

Technical measures for the above mentioned challenges

To meet the challenges outlined above, the literature suggests several appropriate measures, which I will describe in the following. For instance, to counteract data quality issues thorough data preprocessing including removal of redundancies, dealing with inconsistencies, and imputation of missing values or deletion of cases with missing values is necessary. Which preprocessing methods and eventual pipeline are appropriate needs to be decided based on the characteristics of the data set and the requirements set by the respective project objective [17, 24]. Because especially MDS is a patchwork of highly specialized processes and knowledge backgrounds it is crucial that expert knowledge from different domains is included when deciding on a preprocessing strategy [12]. However, even the best possible preprocessing pipeline may not compensate for missing original values due to the high complexity and variety of medical examinations, treatment and documentation. So, in the long run, the clinical workflows themselves and the documentation process should strive for better data quality and completeness where possible [15]. Furthermore, Prasser et al. suggest to foster data quality and privacy by increasing modularity and extensibility of the data infrastructure at medical institutions. Concretely, this should be implemented by separating data, tasks and responsibilities while still ensuring interoperability. Since also tasks and responsibilities should be separated this measure has an organisational component besides the technical [31],

Another meaningful measure intervening in the data documentation process is standardization and harmonization of data models, formats, terminology and interfaces [5, 7, 15, 31, 33]. It ensures scalability and cost effectiveness of the DAI process by supporting interoperability and counteracting inconsistencies and heterogeneity [15, 31]. Regarding data standardization there are first successes like the introduction of DICOM as a widely accepted data standard in PACS [4]. Furthermore, the HL7 FHIR data standard carries high potential to ease the DAI process in future [101]. However, it is not widely

implemented yet and as long as several standards still exist in parallel there is not real standardization and inconsistencies persist [13, 14, 17, 101]. Besides data formats also terminology of medical data sets should be standardized. Existing approaches are coding systems like ICD-10 used to specify diagnoses, LOINC used to specify diagnostic results or the clinical nomenclature SNOMED CT aiming to make all clinically relevant aspects expressible [5, 33, 101]. However, even though these widely applicable coding systems exist, they are still not standard and implementing systems like SNOMED CT on a national level is very challenging. On the one hand, this is due to their complexity making it difficult to find respectively fitting codes. On the other hand, they are still not comprehensive enough, i.e. some real-world observations or codes from another system are not expressible yet, requiring time-consuming application for the inclusion of these codes in the system [5, 15, 33]. So, it is not only crucial to decide on a standard terminology but there is also the need of optimizing the standard terminology making it applicable in practice. Besides standardized data formats and terminology, conceptual frameworks are another option of fostering interoperability because they support a shared understanding of processes and data requirements [7]. After standards in the above mentioned areas have been developed theoretically, further steps in the standardization process are needed to integrate these standards into existing clinical workflows. These steps include updating the infrastructure and software respectively as well as maintaining the system and continuously ensuring hardware operability [4].

As described in the previous section a major challenge of compiling usable data sets for MDS is the lack of structured data. One possible solution is the automatic structuring of patient data using advanced ML and Natural Language Processing (NLP). However, currently there are unsolved privacy issues and a general lack of openly available annotated training data sets. Manual structuring of unstructured medical data could serve as an interim solution to get structured data sets and additionally would provide annotated data sets to support the development of automated structuring systems [5, 15]. Another option would be to directly structure data but this would increase the documentation effort for clinicians [15]. Moreover, completely dispense with free texts could result in losing important information because it cannot be captured by the fields in the structured format. From the unstructured raw data, though, this information could be made available using advanced NLP algorithms [5].

Another big block of technical measures is needed to implement the data protection measures arising from legal and ethical challenges. These include technically enabling patient consent management and a metadata repository documenting data provenance [33]. Additionally, the infrastructure must be developed or adapted to enable data protection and privacy via data access control, safe data transfer, encryption and de-identification [11]. Furthermore, project specific bias mitigation techniques should be applied to counteract possible bias in a data set [17]. Moreover, the legal and ethical data protection

requirements exceed the capabilities of current data infrastructure standards. This means that risk analysis and minimization needs take place individually for every project always ensuring that the infrastructure is used in a way complying to current data protection requirements [31]. However, in general, the current technical possibilities should repeatedly be evaluated and the best possible option should be applied to always guarantee data processing that is as ethically correct as possible [4, 7].

Conclusion

The technical infrastructure currently deployed at university hospitals significantly lacks research orientation. The main focus in infrastructure design was set on primary care and administrative processes which leads to issues regarding data availability, quality and interoperability in retrospective MDS projects. These, on the other hand, require high quality documentation and structured data to achieve meaningful results. Thus, far-reaching technical measures requiring the support of the hospital management and health care professionals are necessary to enable potent data science in a clinical environment (c.f. table 6.3).

Technical challenge	Suitable measure(s)
Data quality issues, missing values, sparsity	Data quality testing and thorough preprocessing using domain knowledge.
Inconsistencies, lack of interoperability	Realistically applicable standards for data formats, terminologies and conceptual frameworks
Lack of structured data	Structuring unstructured data (if possible in an automated manner using NLP).
Ensure data protection and patient privacy	Implement consent management, data encryption, safe data transfer, access control and de-identification.
Data Bias	Project specific bias mitigation during preprocessing.

TABLE 6.3: Technical challenges of reusing medical data for research purposes indicated in literature and measures suitable to meet them.

6.1.4 Organizational Challenges

The previous sections have shown that the clinical DAI process is complex and divers. These characteristics make it being subject to a number of organizational challenges which will be outlined in the following.

Challenges of the DAI process requiring organizational solutions

On an organizational level the complexity and diversity of the DAI process results in project specific decisions having to be made thoroughly but still fast represents a major organizational challenges [15, 31–33]. For instance, its complexity requires a wide variety of expert knowledge, i.e. there is a substantial need for highly trained and closely collaborating interdisciplinary teams including physicians, data scientists, and healthcare professionals [3, 4]. Besides their role as domain experts the physicians and healthcare

professional usually also need to serve as data providers because often only they have legal access to clinical data systems [7]. One of the main organizational challenges arising from these interdisciplinary teams is the substantial difference between the daily work routine of medical and technical experts making it difficult to arrange meetings and tasks that need to be done together [12]. The second main challenge concerning the interdisciplinary teams is the general lack of personnel explicitly trained in medical data science both on technical as well as medical site [7]. On a larger scale, when shaping the future of MDS or designing big projects these organizational challenges even intensify further because here also patient advocates, regulatory agencies and health insurance organizations must be involved [2].

On the single project level a further organizational challenge is the need for a comprehensive Data Management Plan when applying for ethics before the project starts. This makes later changes in the project design difficult because in that case follow-up requests need to be sent to and checked by the EC leading to further delay in the project [99]. It is true that a good design and definition of a data science project is crucial in general before starting it but it is advised to formulate this design as a framework rather than a strict plan in order to still have flexibility for later changes when data issues are identified [102]. The current organizational structure hinders this flexibility.

Another organizational challenge are the insecurities faced both by data science teams as well as patients providing their data. These insecurities arise from unclear legal and ethical requirements or missing communication. In a data science team another cause for insecurities can be an unclear allocation of responsibilities within the team [7, 16, 96–98]. And even project requirements are clear, they lead to further organizational duties as data security and privacy issues need to be sorted out before a project can start [31].

Organizational measures for the above mentioned challenges

An important organizational measure emphasized by all MII consortia is developing and implementing hierarchies of governance, supervision and expertise to increase the structuredness of the highly complex and diverse medical DAI process [15, 31–33]. Thereby, it is important to develop broad policies and guidelines which consider all contingencies so that they are applicable in all imaginary use cases [31]. Another important measure required due to the complexity and diversity of the DAI process is building interdisciplinary science teams which, in turn, brings organizational challenges with it as outlined above. The substantial difference between the daily work routine of medical and technical experts can be met by intensive communication and collaborative planning of tasks [4, 8]. Furthermore, a clear allocation of responsibilities can help to reduce insecurities in the team and to organize tasks that can be performed independently by individual team members. If the responsibilities are unclear the chances increase for legal and ethical principles to be disregarded or important tasks to remain undone, eventually leading to delays in the

workflow [15, 31–33]. In reality, though, the responsibilities are often not clearly defined to everyone but instead they are as siloed as the medical data resources themselves. This leads to a lot of undone cross-departmental tasks which would actually be important to foster progress [16]. Thus, a clear top-down separation of data, tasks and responsibilities is required in every project. Thereby, the separation itself should not be abolished as the modularity enabled by it can increase data quality and privacy [31]. Instead it must be ensured to openly communicate and clearly define structures and responsibilities [7].

Another challenge concerning the interdisciplinary teams is their initial compilation because educated personell specifically trained in the MDS domain is hard to find [3, 4]. So, for future development it is essential to increase the effort in educating both medical and technical experts to eventually form a cross-trained medical and AI-literate workforce [4]. To achieve that, medical students should already learn about data science in their studies [103]. Besides that purely technical education, healthcare professionals and data scientists should also receive guidance and training in security and privacy preservation since that can counteract insecurities regarding necessary steps in the DAI workflow. By additionally providing such training to the patients providing their data similar insecurities can be counteracted on their site [3]. Another measure decreasing insecurities is the development of conceptual frameworks supporting a shared understanding of processes and data requirements [7]. The eventual challenge of actually enabling data security and privacy on an organizational level can be met by putting administrative data safeguards in place [11]. Together with the technical measures described in section 6.1.3 these administrative safeguards are to be chosen in collaboration with data protection instances in ECs. To enable this and to avoid later delays it is advisable to start such communication with the deciding committees and instances early in the project planning phase [7, 11].

Conclusion

To conclude, the complexity and diversity of the medical data landscape results in the need for significant organisational effort. Especially, due to legal and ethical insecurities or unclear structures and workflows it is crucial to prepare a medical DAI process well by designing a well-thought plan before the actual process starts. An additional help can be the development of guiding hierarchies, conceptual frameworks and educational trainings for the data science teams as well as the patients providing their data. In either way intensive communication and clear as well as open allocation of responsibilities are essential to avoid tasks remaining undone, legal and ethical principles being disregarded and delays in the process workflow. A summary of the challenges accompanied by respectively suitable measures can be found in table 6.4.

Organizational challenge	Suitable measure(s)
Complexity and diversity of the DAI process	Hierarchies of governance, supervision and expertise, creation of interdisciplinary teams
Managing (big) interdisciplinary teams	Intensive communication, clear allocation of responsibilities and specification of strict structures.
Lack of trained personnel in medical data science	Education and cross-training of both medical and technical experts.
Requirement of defining the project plan early, lack of flexibility	Thorough planning considering all contingencies as far as possible.
Insecurities both of interdisciplinary teams and patients	Development of guidelines, conceptual frameworks and hierarchies, clear allocation of responsibilities, education in data security and privacy preservation.
Data security and privacy	Administrative safeguards and early communication with data protection instances and EC.

TABLE 6.4: Organizational challenges of reusing medical data for research purposes indicated in literature and measures suitable to meet them.

6.2 Data Access and Integration in the CUP use case

To enhance the insights I gained during literature research by own experiences I went through the DAI process myself in the course of a clinical use case. The aim was to create a reusable data set for primary tumor discovery in CIO Cologne’s CUP use case (c.f. chapter 4). This use case is especially challenging because a working primary tumor discovery system requires to be trained on sufficiently many cancer entities and medical circumstances (c.f. section 4.2). As a consequence, many clinical departments are involved and the patient cohorts is very heterogeneous.

In the following, I describe the steps I performed during the compilation of the CUP use case data set at MeDIC Cologne. Because revealing the exact names of the data systems used at UHC would cause data security issues I used the functional description of the systems instead. In figure 6.2 I depicted the originally planned flow of data during data set compilation. When actually performing DAI we needed to deviate from that planned data flow, though, because the data access according to the initial plan resulted in an insufficiently large data set and did not follow the export policy of the LIS. Details are described in section 6.2.2. An overview over the actual data flow during data set compilation is provided by figure 6.3.

Since I am not a medical doctor, I am not allowed to see any non-anonymized patient data if the patient did not provide an informed consent explicitly allowing that. This is due to the medical confidentiality. To still enable an active participation in the CUP use case’s DAI process we decided to take the approach that I write python scripts which can then be executed on the real patient data by the clinicians. Problems when executing the scripts were solved by telephone calls or e-mail exchange between me and the respective clinician. Further information about the methodological approaches can be found in section 5.2.

FIGURE 6.2: Planned Data Flow for the DAI process in the CUP use case of CIO Cologne.

FIGURE 6.3: Data Flow for the DAI process in the CUP use case of CIO Cologne.

6.2.1 Project Preparation

Before the practical work on the project could start the CIO team, Devina Soenarto and I needed to coordinate the project plan with deciding instances like the data protection officer of UHC and the EC. In this plan we already needed to specify which data should be accessed, how it will eventually be used and which data security and privacy measures are in place. We agreed on only accessing data that was already present in the files of the clinicians leading the use case when the project started. Thus, the CUP project is purely retrospective ¹.

¹<https://medfak.uni-koeln.de/forschung/forschungsfoerderung/klinische-forschung/ethikkommission/faq>

6.2.1.1 Data Sources

One part of deciding for the data that should be used is choosing suitable data sources. There is a large variety of clinical data sources as several clinical departments have their own systems. Thus, even the project's PI at CIO did not have a full overview. To still enable a well-founded choice of data we, as a data science team, needed to get a basic knowledge of the content and characteristics of the available data systems. For that we had various conversations with data providers that turned out to be very useful measures. In the following I will list the data systems that were introduced to me. For each of them I am going to provide the basic concept, the content and how the data can be exported from them. The system abbreviations that are used here correspond to those introduced in section 3.1.

The central PDMS of UHC contains on-site generated data of all patients that have been and are treated at UHC. This data is present and can be retrieved in form of unstructured documents like discharge letters or reports. The documents are separated by respective clinical departments to enable access control. All health care professionals can only see data that is respectively relevant for them. Besides this very comprehensive data system, there exist further clinical systems containing only subsets of information but in a structured manner. These have been chosen as data sources for the CUP use case by the project's clinical PI.

One of these is the Clinical Cancer Registry (CCR) at UHC which is curated by documentalists of UHC. They retrieve information about cancer cases from the central PDMS of UHC that must be reported to the official Cancer Registry of North Rhine-Westphalia. For each cancer case, at least the data fields required by the ADT/GEKID² basic data set are documented. For some cases additional data like the result of some tumor marker tests are available. The CCR currently uses two separate data systems each of which stores a subset of cancer types. The majority of cancer entities is contained by a data system that provides an SQL interface enabling to query its data base in a customizable way. After such a query the data is exported as an excel file. Gynaecological tumors are some of the few exceptions which are contained by the other system for which currently no systematic data access procedure exists.

The RIS at UHC contains radiological images, metadata, annotations and evaluations. One part of it is the radiological study system that is used by the radiologists of UHC to store data of clinical studies in form of key images from clinical scans and the course of the disease that is documented following the current RECIST criteria [104]. This means that for each cancer case at most two target lesions per organ and at most ten target lesions in total are documented. For non-target lesions only the affected organ is available

²<https://www.gekid.de/adt-gekid-basisdatensatz>

but no number of metastases. The RECIST compliant documentation can be exported by the radiologists in form of excel or CSV files.

The radiologists with whom we collaborated pointed out that in near future the RIS will also contain documentation following the RECIST criteria for regular patients which do not take part in a study.

The third and last clinical data system that was introduced to me as one of the systems containing already nicely structured data was the LIS. As the name suggests it contains results of laboratory examinations. For each patient the laboratory department can export an excel file containing all laboratory results enriched by the date of the blood test and the ID of the respective clinical case this examination was part of.

6.2.1.2 Data Selection

Another part of the Project Preparation, that is interwoven with the previously described choice of the data sources, is the selection of the data itself. This includes choosing which cases should be contained in the data set. To do so the accessed time span and the clinical characterization of cases of interest need to be specified. The second important decision to be made is that about which features to include for the chosen cases. Answers to all of these questions and the respective data sources are to be specified in the project proposal which is then sent to the governing instances for review.

Case Selection

Before I joined the project, the CIO team had already chosen to use data from the last five years, i.e. data from 01.07.2016 to 30.06.2021, and to exclude all cancer cases in which the patient was younger than 18 years old. This is due to the clinical specialities of children and adolescents that would bring a new level of complexity to the project. Initially this additional complexity should be avoided.

When I joined the team and was introduced to the disease profile of CUP, I suggested to only use data of cancer cases for which metastases have been found. Other cases are not comparable with CUP cases because the CUP syndrome can only be diagnosed for cancer patients who have metastases (c.f. section 4.1). As the indicator for metastases, we used the TNM classification available in the CCR data. A classification as cM1 indicates that metastases have been found [105, 106]. Thereby, we did not consider whether the case is assigned to one of the subcategories cM1a, cM1b, cM1c or cM1d which specify the identified metastases further in terms of their clinical characteristics or location. We could ignore these subcategories because we only needed to know whether metastases are present or not. We did not need further information about the kind or the relative location of the metastases. The first histological examination leading to classifying the case as cM1 will be referred to as the decisive histological examination in the following.

Moreover, we decided to only include cancer cases whose short ICD-10 code can be found in table 6.5. This was done because most CUP cases whose primary tumor is detected in an autopsy have one of the listed LOPs (c.f. section 4.1). Unfortunately, the genital cancer are documented in the CCR system for which currently no systematic data access procedure exists. So, we decided to exclude genital cancer patients for now. If the LOP of a cancer patient is neither the genitals nor one of the considered LOPs, a pathologist could identify it with standard diagnostic procedures, according to the clinical PI of the CUP project. So, our system would not be needed in these cases.

LOP class	short ICD-10 code(s) defining this class
Lung	C34
Pancreas	C23, C24, C25
Kidney	C64, C65, C67, C68
Liver	C22
Colorectal	C18, C19, C20
Upper GI	C15, C16

TABLE 6.5: ICD-10 based definition of the considered classes in the multi-class classification problem of assigning the LOP to cancer cases. Each class represents one LOP and is specified by the provided short ICD-10 codes.

Feature Selection The data sources chosen for the CUP use case provide clinical features which partly differ between cancer entities due to different examination guidelines that are to be followed for these entities. As the CUP use case needs data of several entities (c.f. section 4) the CIO team, Devina Soenarto and me needed to decide which of the features available in the chosen systems can be used meaningfully.

Due to the considerations above we decided to only access CRR data that is available for all considered cancer entities (c.f. table 6.5) as well as for CUP cases. Additionally, the the CUP project aims at creating an AI system supporting the physicians' decision on the choice of treatment for a CUP patient (c.f. section 1). So, when applying the system no data about the response to a treatment or the development of the patient is available. Therefore, secondly, we only chose features available at the time of initial diagnosis. Moreover, we excluded features without any clinical and pathological relevance like the name of a patient. All these decisions result in choosing the following input features from the CCR data: the patient's gender, its age at the decisive histological examination (c.f. section 6.2.1.2), the grading of the tumor and parts of its TNM classification (N-, L-, Pn- and V-value)[106].

From the radiological data, we chose to only use the distribution pattern of metastases. After consultation with the radiologists, we decided that the best possible features we can extract from the RECIST evaluations in the radiological study system (c.f. section 6.2.1.1) are Tumor Burden Scores for individual organs whose calculation is depicted in table 6.6. A more fine-grained consideration of the distribution pattern is not possible

having the radiological study system as the only data source for structured information about the location of metastases.

Score value	Description	# target lesions	# non-target lesions
0	no metastases	0	0
1	only small metastases	0	≥ 1
2	one measurable metastasis	1	0
3	two measurable metastases	2	0
4	at least two metastases	≥ 1	≥ 1

TABLE 6.6: Possible scores for the tumor burden of an organ defined by the number of target and non-target lesions documented for that organ in the radiological study system.

Definitions of target and non-target lesions can be found in RECIST v1.1 [104].

From the laboratory data we chose to include blood test values which were identified as good pathological predictors by the clinical PI of the CUP use case. Concretely the chosen analytes are lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), Haematocrit (HKT), Haemoglobin (HB), Calcium (CA) and C-reactive protein (CRP).

6.2.1.3 Organisational Preparation

The results of the data source, case and feature selection were documented in form of a study plan. This plan additionally contained a section about data protection and security measures and explained the objective and methodology of the CUP use case. The study plan was sent to the data protection officer of UHC via E-Mail asking her whether she could check the data protection concept and also offering her a video meeting with the CUP use case team. She answered within three working days asking two questions. We answered these two questions exactly one week later, after we had discussed the answers with the CIO project management. Our reply reached the data protection officer at the beginning of a four week vacation which lead to a significant delay in the process. A replacement for that time was not indicated to us. However, after her return we got her approval for compiling and using the data set according to the outlined plan. This was noted in the project documents before we submitted them to UHC's EC at the end of January via an online submission platform. Besides the already mentioned study plan the project documents contained the official form for retrospective projects provided on the website of the EC ³ and Devina Soenartos doctoral thesis exposé, because the objective of her thesis is the support of the CUP use case as a medical domain expert. Since the CUP project is purely retrospective it did not necessarily need the approval of the EC. The clinicians could decide on their own to use the data contained in their files for research purposes. However, as described in section 6.1.2, it is advisable to ensure ethical correctness by always including the EC in project planning. Thereby, significant project

³<https://medfak.uni-koeln.de/forschung/forschungsfoerderung/klinische-forschung/ethikkommission/antragsverfahren/retrospektive-vorhaben>

delays should be expected as the processing of the CUP proposal by the EC took almost 4 months. We received the official approval in mid may. On request via the clinical PI of the use case the EC pointed out that the reason for this is that they assign proposals of purely retrospective use cases that are not bound to any organizational deadlines (e.g. submissions) the lowest priority. Partly or fully prospective projects are brought forward because they necessarily need an ethics approval. Deadline bound projects are processed earlier to ensure that they can comply with the respective deadline. It is true that theoretically the request to check our project proposal could have been sent to the EC already when we sent this request to the Data Protection Officer but the CIO team already experienced in previous projects that the EC will ask for the Data Protection approval if it is not directly provided before they make their decision. Thus, it would not have accelerated the process to send the request simultaneously to the Data Protection Instance and the EC. Both the Data Protection Officer and the EC emphasized in their project approvals that we should ensure that only the qualified physicians see the raw data while medical student Devina Soenarto and I may only see the data after it had been anonymized.

6.2.2 Data Access

As specified in the project planning documents (c.f. section 6.2.1, especially subsection 6.2.1.1) data was retrieved from the CCR, the RIS and the LIS at UHC. The data sources have been chosen by the CIO CUP use case team because they offer the most comprehensive structured documentation of cancer cases that is currently available digitally at UHC.

To support the access of the CCR data I was given an SQL query generator for the data base behind the CCR data system (c.f. section 6.2.1.1). My access was restricted to the test data base which enabled me to explore the data base structure without having access to real patient data. The generator provided a graphical interface in which I could specify which data I needed by selecting respective check-boxes. Based on my specifications the tool generated an SQL query which was displayed to me but also directly executed on the test data base. I realized that its functionality was too limited for the data export we intended. The generator only used inner joins to combine relations in the data base and, therefore, important data got lost. So, instead I generated several SQL queries and thereby worked out an overview of the data base including names of relations and attributes stored in these relations. With this overview I was able to create customized SQL queries fitting our needs. These queries were sent to the leader of the CCR at UHC where they were executed on the data base containing the real patient data within two days. The resulting excel files were made available to the clinicians of our team via a secure data space of UHC. Using a python script written by me the clinicians pseudonymized

the CCR data by exchanging the original PIDs with new ones. The mapping was stored on the secure data share to enable the same mapping for the data exports from further systems. Other identifying attributes than the PIDs have not been exported from the data base. Later, when all data had been integrated, the data set was fully anonymized (c.f. section 6.2.3.4).

The access of the radiological data was performed twice. At first the chosen approach was to let the radiologist export a set of studies specified by the clinical PI of the CUP use case. They shared the exported excel files with the clinicians of the use case team via a secure data share within 2 weeks. They directly deleted all identifying attributes except the PIDs. These were again exchanged with new ones. For this the clinicians executed another python script that assigned the same pseudonyms to patients whose IDs were already contained in the mapping produced by the pseudonymization of the CCR data. For patients firstly encountered in the radiological data new pseudonyms were generated and added to the mapping. I then wrote a python script that firstly determined which of the cases contained in the CCR data fulfil the clinical specifications for the CUP project described in section 6.2.1.2. These turned out to be 796 out of 15317. From these the script took the PIDs and determined the overlap with the PIDs contained in the radiological data export. This overlap consisted of only 14 patients 12 of which belonged to the class "colorectal". Therefore, we decided that a second data export from the RIS is needed. The new approach was that the clinicians send the list of the 796 PIDs from suitable cancer cases in the CCR to the study registry to get to know which of those participated in a study and should therefore be contained in the study system of the RIS. Within two days the study registry provided the requested list of patients together with the respective study IDs. The radiologists exported the RECIST evaluations of the specified studies which had not been exported yet from the study section of the RIS system (c.f. 6.2.1.1). The exported excel files were again sent to the clinicians and pseudonymized using the script that was already used for the first data export.

The lab data export was initiated simultaneously to the CCR export by which we attempted to parallelize the data access process as far as possible. Based on the specified data time span and ICD codes (c.f. section 6.2.1.2) the MeDIC team compiled a list of patients fitting to our project plan that contained 13540 PIDs. These were sent to the laboratory department requesting the export of the chosen lab values for these patients. However, the big amount of queried PIDs led to a breakdown of the export from the LIS. This information was only provided to us after seven weeks following several requests about the status of the export. In the meantime, we had received the CCR and radiological data so that we could then compile a list of PIDs that are either in the CCR or in the radiological data set or in both. This list was sent to the laboratory department requesting the lab data export for the specified patients. After waiting another three weeks the export was finished and we were told that we have to provide a script that filters the

raw data to only contain the specified lab values and data associated to cancer-related cases. This was necessary to ensure data minimization, i.e. that we only get data that is relevant for our project. The most challenging part hereby was to get the IDs of cancer related cases. In a discussion with the CIO Team, the data providers, Devina Soenarto and me we decided to use the administrative data accessible by the leader of the CCR. All case IDs in this data are certain to be cancer-related as the UHC access control ensures that the leader of the CCR only has access to cancer-related data. I then wrote another python script sequentially reading in all exported lab excel files and compiling the LDH, HKT, HB, CA and CRP values of the cases identified to be cancer-related in one lab data CSV file. Additionally, the actual PIDs were replaced by pseudonym IDs using the mapping created during pseudonymization of the CCR and the radiological data. This already covered all PIDs contained in the lab data because the export was based on the PIDs contained by the previously already pseudonymized data.

6.2.3 Data Set Preparation

After the data access process was finished the retrieved data needed to be transformed, integrated and anonymized. In order to identify necessary transformations these steps were preceded by a data inspection step. All these steps belong to the process of data set preparation that is finalized with a conclusive data quality check.

6.2.3.1 Data Inspection

As mentioned above, the data set preparation was initiated by inspecting the accessed pseudonymized data with the goal to determine how it should be preprocessed. Concretely, the physicians who had access to the exported data sets firstly told me the file names and structures. Based on that I wrote a python script for each of the individual data sets that output the columns names, i.e. which information is contained for the respective cancer case. Furthermore, the scripts identified whether there are patients appearing more than once in a data set. The pseudonymized IDs of such patients were written to a separate file enabling the physicians of the team to manually choose which data to take for these patients. For the radiological data the script additionally output all expressions specifying any metastasis location in any of the exported RECIST excel files.

The CCR data had been exported in form of one data table containing information about diagnoses and one table containing results of histological examinations. The radiological data was present as one excel file per exported radiological study. The lab data came in as a collection of excel files each of which contained the relevant lab results of exactly one patient. The scripts I wrote based on that information were executed on the exported

and pseudonymized data sets by the physicians of the team who reported the output to Devina Soenarto and me.

For the CCR data these results revealed that the diagnoses data contained the pseudonymized PID, the respective birthdate, the gender and the ICD-10 Code of the exported cancer cases. The histology data contained the pseudonymized PID, the date of the examination, the TNM value, the grading and the L, Pn and V values of the exported histological examinations. Furthermore, there were 91 cancer cases having more than one histological examination result. The physicians in the team manually chose which one to respectively take by adding an additional column in the excel files which contains a 1 in rows that should be taken and a 0 in rows that should be discarded. In their decision the physicians preferred examination results with fewer missing values. Thereby, missing T values were ignored as they are not clinically relevant in the CUP project. If two examination results for one case had the same number of missing values, pathological results were preferred over clinical ones as the pathological assessments have higher quality according to the physicians. If even this did not discriminate two or more examination results for a single case, the first, i.e. older the result was chosen. Another important observation about the CCR data that was already made when preparing the lab data export (c.f. section 6.2.2) is that 796 out of 15317 exported cases fulfil the clinical specifications for the CUP project described in section 6.2.1.2.

Executing the data inspection script on the radiological study data revealed a limitation of that data. Per default there is an empty second row in the exported excel files leading to an error when executing the script. So the script needed to be modified so that it ignores the empty second row. Afterwards it was re-send to physicians who again needed to find a time slot to execute the script. This execution has shown that every exported radiological study file contained several rows per patient each of which contained the pseudonymized PID and size measurements for metastases chosen according to the RECIST criteria. The individual rows differed in the time point at which the measurement was carried out. This point in time was provided in each row just as the location and the respective size for each chosen metastasis. By examining the expressions of the metastasis locations appearing in the data we noticed that these are documented on different levels providing the organ as well as the exact location within that organ. In total there were 84 different expressions of locations for which metastases are documented. So, medical student Devina Soenarto grouped the location specifications we found in the data according to higher-level organs (c.f. table C.1). This enabled later having 19 organ-specific TBS per patient instead of 84 scores each of which measures the tumor burden for one of the exact locations. Finally, we realized that there were four patients in the data who participated in two studies. Here, similar as for the CCR data the physicians of our team manually chose which study to take. They respectively preferred the studies with more documented metastases. If the

number of documented metastases was the same they chose the study with the earliest date.

When the data inspection script was executed on the exported and pseudonymized lab data it revealed that every excel file contained the respective pseudonymized PID, the case ID, the letter code of the analyte, the description of the analyte, the measured value itself and two dates. The first date specified the date at which the blood sample was taken and analyzed while the second indicated the date at which the result was presented to the patient. Each row in the excel files corresponded to exactly one analyte value in exactly one blood test. Moreover, some lab data excel files had an additional column providing the respective LOINC code of the measured analyte.

6.2.3.2 Transformation

Individually transforming the single data sets was necessary to eventually make them integratable. For instance, in the data inspection we have seen that there are several blood test results for each patient whereas we aim for one value for each analyte in the final integrated data set. So, I wrote python scripts performing the data transformation individually for one data set each. These scripts were again executed by the physicians on the exported and pseudonymized data.

The transformation of the CCR data started with removing details from the histological values that went beyond the standard values of 0 and 1, 0-2, 0-3 or 0-4, respectively. The only exception was the M value where we kept the information whether it is a clinical (cM) or a pathological (pM) M value. For instance "cM1b" was replaced by "cM1" and "pN0sn" was replaced by "N0" in the histological data table of the CCR data. Afterwards the transformation script deleted histology examinations not marked with a 1 in the column that was manually added in the data inspection step (c.f. section 6.2.3.1). Now that there is exactly one histological examination per cancer case the script was able to join the histology table and the diagnosis table. This, in turn, enabled calculating the patients' age at the respectively decisive histological examination because this feature was chosen as in input feature (c.f. section 6.2.1.2) but it was not available in the raw CCR data. It was computed by subtracting the date of birth from the date of the decisive histology examination. Eventually, the CCR data was filtered so that it only contained cases fulfilling the clinical specifications for the CUP project described in section 6.2.1.2, i.e. a histological clinical M value of cM1 and an ICD-10 Code matching one of the specified cancer types of interest.

Besides the CCR data, also the radiological study data had to be transformed to be usable in a meaningful way. At first, we deleted the data of patients that participated in two studies from the data file of the study that was not chosen by the physicians in the data

inspection step (c.f. section 6.2.3.1). Furthermore, the data inspection had revealed that the radiological data was available for each cancer case at different time points but the entries here only differed in the size measured for the individual metastases. As we were not interested in the size of metastases but only in their location, we could simply take the data from the first assessment, i.e. the base assessment of each cancer case. So, the script read the locations of the target and non-target metastases provided in the data and considering them calculated a TBS for each organ listed in the first column of table C.1 based on the scheme shown by table 6.6.

Just as the metastases size measurements, the laboratory values were available for each cancer case at different points in time. So, for them, we added the constraint that for each combination of cancer case and analyte we only integrate the value determined most closely to the date of the decisive histological examination of that case (c.f. section 6.2.1.2). This way we got one well-defined vector of laboratory values per cancer case.

These transformations concluded the preparation of integrating the individual data sets. Further transformation may be needed depending on the ML approach the CIO team chooses for creating their primary tumor discovery system. This decision has not been made when I created the data set. Moreover, my goal was to create a reusable data set. Thus, it should be as raw as possible to allow for as many types of further processing as possible [29].

6.2.3.3 Data Integration

After the data transformation the individual data sets were integratable. Because all UHC data systems use the same PIDs and for all three individual data sets we had applied the exact same mapping to pseudonym IDs the eventual integration could be performed by simply matching the individual data sets based on pseudonym ID. For this I performed a full join, i.e. taking and merging data of patients contained in both data sets, on the preprocessed CCR data and the preprocessed radiological data, followed by a full join of the resulting data set and the preprocessed lab data. The full join resulted in losing the data of all patients which are not contained in both data sets. After the first join the data set had a size of 63 patients which did not change after the second join.

6.2.3.4 Anonymization

As outlined in section 5.2 we firstly looked for identifying features in our data set which resulted in only one hit namely the pseudonymized PID. Because we only needed this feature for data integration it could now be deleted completely. In a second step we identified quasi-identifying features in our data set as described in section 5.2. Using a questionnaire

six members of the data science team (management, medical domain experts, technical experts) assessed the compiled cancer case features according to the three aspects replicability, resource availability and the distinguishability of different feature expressions. This was done by assigning scores from 1 (low) to 3 (high) to every combination of feature and aspect. The average replicability, resource availability and distinguishability score over all six survey participants was calculated for every feature and the aspect. These average scores were summed up to a final re-identification score for each feature. Features having a score higher than 5 are considered to be quasi-identifying (c.f. section 5.2). In our case these were the gender and the age of the patient. Detailed results can be found in table 6.7.

Feature	Avg. replicability	Avg. resource availability	Avg. distinguishability	Score (Sum)
Gender	3.000	2.667	1.333	7.000
Age	2.833	1.667	2.000	6.500
Grading	2.000	1.000	1.333	4.333
N	2.000	1.000	1.500	4.500
L	2.000	1.000	1.333	4.333
Pn	2.000	1.000	1.333	4.333
V	2.000	1.000	1.333	4.333
LDH	1.167	1.000	1.500	3.667
HKT	1.333	1.333	1.500	4.167
HB	1.333	1.000	1.500	3.833
CA	1.167	1.000	1.500	3.667
CRP	1.167	1.000	1.500	3.667
TBS	1.667	1.000	1.333	4.000

TABLE 6.7: Results of the survey according to Malin et al. where six CUP team members (management, medical and technical experts) assigned scores from 1 (low) to 3 (high) to every combination of feature and relevant aspect (replicability, resource availability, distinguishability). Displayed are the respective average scores over all survey participants rounded to three decimal places and the eventual score (sum of the averages) which is used to determine quasi-identifying features (score > 5). The scores of features determined to be quasi-identifying are displayed in blue.

As outlined in section 3.3 quasi-identifying features are to be protected by generalizing them in a way that k -anonymity is ensured. As the gender is a binary feature the only possibility to generalize it, is to delete the information completely. Therefore, we aimed for setting up k -anonymity by only generalizing the age, i.e. replacing the exact age by age groups. Concretely, we specified the gender and the age as quasi-identifying features in the ARX tool. Additionally, we set the goal privacy model to 10-anonymity and the anonymization strategy for both quasi-identifying features to "Generalization". As mentioned above for the gender there is only one possibility to generalize it. So the generalization hierarchy determining different generalization levels for each feature was fixed for this feature and automatically generated by the ARX tool. The generalization hierarchy for the feature age was created by Devina Soenarto and me. We set up six

generalization levels which are five year groups, 10 year groups, 20 year groups, 40 year groups, 80 year groups and complete deletion of the age feature.

When executing the anonymization as specified above the result was that the highest generalization level for the age, i.e. a complete deletion of the feature, needed to be chosen in either case. So, we lost the whole age information. We identified the reason for this to be the heterogeneity of the cancer cases in the data set combined with the small data set size. However, losing the information about a patient's age was not an acceptable option so we decreased the value of k until the age information was at least preserved in age groups. This was achieved with $k = 2$ leading to a selection of the second generalization level resulting in age groups comprising 10 years each. The results of the anonymization are depicted in figures 6.4 and 6.5 which are overviews generated by the ARX tool. We see that the re-identification risks were reduced significantly from a maximal value of 100% to a maximal value of 50% which directly follows from setting k to 2. Additionally, now only 19% of the patients are at risk to be re-identified while it was 100% of the patients before applying the generalization. So, although we chose k to only be 2 in order to secure data usability the generalization decreased the risk of re-identification significantly which is additionally shown by the drop of the attack success rate from 66% to roughly 14% for all three considered attacker models.

In section 3.3 I mentioned that k -anonymity cannot protect against inference of values of sensitive features. So, usually besides k -anonymity, a privacy model comprising inference attacks like t -closeness should be in place as well. However, the fact that all medical features are sensitive combined with the heterogeneity of the cancer cases in the data set and the small data set size would cause a significant loss of useful information. Thus, we decided to only use k -anonymity here which can be additionally justified by the fact that the data will not leave the UHC infrastructure at any point in the project. Hence, fewer protection measures are necessary.

FIGURE 6.4: ARX results - Distribution of re-identification risks for individual patients according to prosecutor model (c.f. section 3.3) before (left) and after (right) anonymization

FIGURE 6.5: ARX results - Dashboard showing the re-identification risk measured according to the prosecutor, journalist and marketer attacker models before (left) and after (right) anonymization

6.2.3.5 Data Quality Assessment

After the data has been anonymized medical student Devina Soenarto and I could receive it and check its quality as specified in section 5.2. According to the physicians of the CUP project team, we could expect high data quality because we did not include vague data like sonography results or letters. In contrast to such data the retrieved data (CCR, radiological studies, lab) follows high quality standards. However, a remaining error source is the manual data entry e.g. in the CCR. So, we decided to at least check completeness and plausibility of the data.

The completeness was assessed by calculating and plotting the availability of the chosen features in the compiled data set in percent. The resulting bar plot is depicted in figure 6.6. It reveals that the demographic features age and gender, the TNM value, the individual TBSs and the class were available for all cancer cases in the data set. This is a result of the compilation process. Firstly the CCR data was filtered on the M value of the case and it's ICD code. Thus, the TNM values and the class have to be available for all contained cases. Moreover, the three individual data exports were matched using an inner join which means that all contained cases have an entry in the CCR, the radiological study system and the LIS. Since the gender and the age are necessary features for all CCR entries and the TBS were calculated by us based on the available information in the radiological study system, these are naturally available for all contained cases. The unavailability of some lab values can be explained by the fact that patients are contained in the data set if at least one lab value is available for them. However, the LDH, HKT, HB and CA value was still available for 95.3% of the cases and the CRP value for 93.7%. Higher was the number of missing histological values beyond the classical TNM. The histological grading was not available for 55.6% of the cases while the histological L, Pn and V value were even missing for 88.9% of the cases. Besides the feature availability, we checked for redundancies, i.e.

for duplicated cancer cases but there were no. All cases contained in the compiled data set were pairwise distinct in at least one feature.

To check for plausibility I determined statistical values and created at least one plot for every feature. Here I treated the numerical features, which are the age and the laboratory values different, than the remaining features, which are categorical. For the numerical features I determined the mean, the standard deviation (std), the minimal value (min), the maximal value (max) as well as the 25%, the 50% and the 75% quartiles. These statistical values can be found in table C.2. The mean and the quartiles were additionally visualized using a boxplot (c.f. appendix C.1.2.2 and C.1.5.2). Furthermore, I plotted the distribution of the numerical features using a barplot enhanced by a kernel density estimation graph (c.f. appendix C.1). The plausibility of the categorical features, was checked by determining their number of unique values, the most frequent value and the count of that most frequent value. These values are compiled in table C.3. Additionally, their distribution was visualized using barplots (c.f. appendix C.1). Concerning the age feature it is to be noted that after the anonymization step there were age groups instead of exact ages in the data set. To still deal with them as numerical values I assigned to

FIGURE 6.6: Availability of the chosen cancer case features in the compiled data set

each patient the average age of the respective age group, e.g. 45 for the age group [40,50]. The statistics and plots for the age feature were based on this respective average age.

The statistical values as well as the bar- and boxplots were shared with Devina Soenarto who compared them with values from the literature. Identified issues were the over-representation of male patients which is in general not as significant as in our data set (c.f. boxplot in appendix C.1.2.2), the under-representation of the two classes "colorectal cancer" and "liver cancer" (c.f. table 6.8 and left figure in appendix C.1.2.1) as well as the high number of TBSs being 0 for all cases. All these issues are probably caused by the small size of the compiled data set resulting in non-representativeness. So, here a possible solution would be the re-structuring of the data set compilation with the aim to access further cancer cases. Another issue identified by Devina Soenarto was a very high LDH value of 2704 U/l which is significantly outside of the plausible scope considering literature values as well as the LDH mean, standard deviation and the quartiles. We discussed this outlier candidate in the regular data science team meeting and agreed that the high value probably results from a data entry mistake. In particular, the comma was probably set to the wrong position, i.e. the correct value is probably 270.4 U/l. Thus, we changed the respective LDH value to the more plausible one. Figure 6.7 shows the distribution of the LDH values in the data set before this correction (left plot) and afterwards (right plot). All remaining values of the LDH feature and all values of the other features were inside the plausible and reasonable scope of values for cancer patients according to Devina Soenarto. Nevertheless, the boxplots in appendix C.1.5.2 suggest that there is more than one outlier in the LDH values and that there are further outliers in the CRP and the CA values, if you follow the definition of an outlier being a value outside of 1.5 times the interquartile range of the respective feature, i.e. being above or beyond boxplot whiskers [107]. However, these should only be seen as candidate outliers. Especially in the medical domain, where different conditions can cause abnormal values, domain knowledge like that provided by Devina Soenarto is crucial to discriminate real outliers from values lying above or below the whiskers of the boxplot for other, potentially clinical reasons.

Class	Size
Colorectal	2
Liver	2
Lung	27
Pancreas	18
Upper GI	14

TABLE 6.8: Sizes of the classes each of which corresponds to a primary tumor site.

FIGURE 6.7: Barplots visualizing the distribution of the LDH values in the compiled data set before (left) and after (right) correction of the identified outlier.

6.3 Conceptualizing Data Access and Integration

As outlined in methodology section 5.3, I conceptualized the workflow, a surrounding framework and a performance evaluation guideline based on my results from the literature review and the experience I got in the CIO CUP use case. This represents the "Do" step in the PDCA workflow development cycle. In the following, I outline the reasoning behind the conceptualization. Its visualizations can be found in appendix A.

6.3.1 Roles and Actors

As described in section 5.3, a process workflow conceptualization should always be accompanied by a specification of roles and actors which are involved in the process. During literature research and in the CUP use case I noticed that very central actors are the medical experts, e.g. clinicians, physicians and medical students, as well as the technical experts, e.g. computer or data scientists. These two actors build the role of the interdisciplinary data science team which actually performs the MDS project. For the success of such a project it is essential that the team collaborates closely, communicates intensively and clearly assigns responsibilities (c.f. section 6.1.4). Besides the research-focused data science team there are actors in the process operating rather on the governance level. On the one hand, there are the Data Protection Instances put into a central position by currently valid Data Protection laws in the process of choosing suitable data protection measures for MDS projects (c.f. section 6.1.1) and the Ethics Committees (EC) deciding whether the project and its methodology are ethically correct. On the other hand, the MII recently launched so-called Use and Access Committees (UAC) which have the task

to check the data protection measures as well as ethical validity of the project. Besides the project management documents these UAC require an official application form, the data protection approval and the ethics approval to be handed in. If one approval or both are not available this needs to be justified in the official UAC application form. The third group of roles are the data provider which I suggest to divide into the roles of primary data provider and secondary data provider based on the type of data they offer. Primary data providers are the physicians in the respective departments, e.g. radiologists, pathologists, laboratory staff or geneticists capable of exporting the data from their respective data management systems. The secondary data providers are those which retrieved data from the primary data providers and already integrated and potentially also preprocessed it. An example for this role are DICs like the MeDIC Cologne. To conclude, I identified three bigger groups of roles and actors which are the research role of the interdisciplinary data science team, the governance roles which are the data protection instance, the EC and the UAC, and last but not last the data provider roles being the primary and the secondary data providers. The visualization of this conceptualization is depicted in figure [A.1](#).

6.3.2 System Concepts

Besides the roles and actors, different system concepts are another important part of the framework surrounding the DAI process. In section [3.1](#) several types of data sources have been listed. For the sake of generalization, I grouped them into the three classes primary data sources, secondary data sources and external data sources. I define the primary and secondary data sources in accordance to the definition of the primary and secondary data providers: primary data sources are systems like the PDMS, the LIS, the RIS and the PACS which are used by a single department to store their data. Secondary data systems are those storing data that was retrieved from primary or other secondary data systems. So, they serve as a kind of central data collection. Examples for this kind of system concept are the central server at MeDIC Cologne, registries or the digital EHRs. The external data systems are all that are not part of the clinical data infrastructure of a hospital. For instance, these include data bases of insurance companies, of resident physicians and data collected by wearables [\[2\]](#). Because the external data sources are not used in practice at MeDIC Cologne or UHC yet, I could not gain any practical experience using them. Thus, I did not consider them in my workflow in section [6.3.4](#). However, I included the external system concepts in the surrounding framework for in future more and more MDS projects will retrieve their data through them [\[14, 17\]](#). The system concepts visualization can be found in appendix [A.2](#).

6.3.3 Data Security Levels

A third very important part of the surrounding framework are the aspects influencing data security. In section 3.3 I have outlined that there are three essential approaches to protect data security which are authentication e.g. via passwords when using a secure data share, encryption when transmitting the data and storing it in less secure networks as well as de-identification by pseudonymization or anonymization. Which of these measures must or should be in place depends, among other things, on the network connection of the system on which the data is stored, preprocessed and analyzed. While compiling the data set for the CUP use case (c.f. section 6.2) I encountered three types of possible network connections at UHC. These are the patient net (P-net), the science net (S-net) and the Internet. The P-net contains patient data and is the most secure network connection only providing access to the UHC intranet. The S-net provides restricted access to the internet which is why no non-anonymized patient data may be stored here. On the other hand, it still has no full internet connection which ensures a sufficient level of data protection and security for the employees according to the IT department of UHC. The third and least secure network connection is a full internet connection. Besides the chosen network connection and established protection measures, another aspect influencing the data security is the type of data access which can either be open or restricted. This concludes my conceptualization of aspects influencing the data security in the DAI process. A visual overview can be found in appendix A.3.

6.3.4 The Data Access and Integration Workflow

When compiling the data set for the CUP use case I found that the whole DAI process can be divided into three bigger subprocesses framed by an initiating step and a closing step. The whole process is initiated by the project idea being formulated which is followed by the first subprocess. This is the **Project Preparation** in which the project is designed in more detail and necessary approvals are obtained. The second subprocess is the **Data Access** during which the data is retrieved from the respectively chosen data sources. Last but not least, the full data set needs to be integrated and preprocessed which happens during the subprocess of **Data Set Preparation**. Finally, the compiled data set needs to be stored together with some metadata documenting data provenance, i.e. who accessed or edited the data when and how. This is necessary for two reasons. The first is to make the creation of the data set transparent to researchers who may reuse it later. The second is that for ethically correct data processing you need to always be able to provide information on whether and how a person's data was accessed and used (c.f. section 6.1.2) [18]. A BPMN model visualizing the whole high-level DAI process can be found in figure A.4. The individual steps to be performed within the subprocesses are outlined in the following.

Project Preparation

Once the broad project idea has been formulated the Project Preparation subprocess can start. The first step here is that the data science team exactly specifies the research questions the MDS project aims to answer. Based on these, the data science team can continue with analyzing the project requirements and specifying the project design. The requirements analysis includes the analysis of available data sources, the compilation of a list of data features needed for the project, the specification of a clinical case profile suitable to answer the research questions as well as deciding on a legal and ethical foundation. The subsequent design of the project consists of the choice of the data sources, the choice of data features to be accessed, the selection of clinical cases by specifying a case profile as well as formulating the planned project process in form of a study plan. All these decisions are noted in the Project management documents as well as the project metadata. When the project design is finalized, suitable data protection measures for the project should be compiled by the data science team in form of a data protection concept (DPC) which is added to the Project management documents and noted to the project metadata. As outlined in section 6.1.1 this DPC needs to be coordinated with the Data Protection Officer. So, the data science team requests the Data Protection Instance to check the formulated DPC. The Data Protection Instance receives this request, checks the DPC and either approves it or requests a revision of the DPC. The latter case would cause the data science team to go back to the step of developing the DPC followed by requesting the check of the new DPC by the Data Protection Instance. If the Data Protection Instance approves the DPC, either directly or after revision, the subprocess of Project Preparation is finished if the previously chosen legal and ethical foundation of the project specifies that no approval of the EC is necessary. For instance, purely retrospective projects like the CUP use case do not necessarily need an approval by the EC. However, as outlined in section 6.1.2 letting the the EC check the project proposal is advisable in any case to ensure that the project is ethically correct. So, if the data science team has to or decided to ask for an EC approval of the project, a request to check the Project management documents is sent to the EC. At UHC this can only be done after the approval from the Data Protection Officer has been obtained (c.f section 6.2.1.3.). After receiving the request, the EC checks the Project management documents. If they decide that the project proposal is ethically correct, they send an approval back to the data science team. If they find aspects in the project plan that are ethically questionable or not okay they request a revision of the project proposal. In that case, this request is received by the data science team which goes back to the step of requirements analysis and project design this time considering the feedback of the EC and adapting the project design accordingly. The DPC needs to be adapted to the new project plan and again checked by the Data Protection Officer. After the DPC has been approved the new project plan is re-submitted to the EC for a second check. If the data science team receives the approval, either directly or after adapting the project design, the subprocess

of Project Preparation is finished if no data is to be accessed via a DIC of the MII. If, however, the plan is to access data via a DIC of the MII it is additionally required to get the project approval from an MII UAC. For this, the Project management documents including the already obtained approvals are submitted with the request to check them. After receiving this request the UAC evaluates the project proposal judging it's legal and ethical validity. If this check is positive, the UAC sends its approval to the data science team and the subprocess of Project Proposal is finished. If the check is negative, i.e. the UAC identifies ethical or legal issues in the presented project plan, a revision of the project plan is requested from the data science team. Receiving this request, the data science team goes back to the step of requirements analysis and project design this time considering the feedback of the UAC and adapting the project design accordingly. The process is the same as in the case of receiving a negative feedback from the EC with the only difference being that here also a new approval of the EC is needed. Because the UAC requires the approvals of the Data Protection and the EC to be available, their check of the project proposal cannot be parallelized with the checks of the other governance instances. The BPMN visualization of the Project Preparation subprocess as it is described here can be found in appendix [A.6](#).

Depending on the respective medical site at which the MDS project is carried out it may be necessary to attach filled forms to the requests to the governance instances. At UHC the EC provides templates for these request forms on their website⁴. The Data Protection Office does not provide such forms. The UAC of the UHC MeDIC currently provides forms on request but they will soon be available on their website⁵. Another thing that should be considered in this first subprocess is that delays in the communication with the governance instances should be expected which either result from the contacted person's being on holiday or from the high load of project proposals. The former happened in the CUP use case, when we replied to the questions of the Data Protection Officer. The latter was the case for the approval request sent to the EC in the CUP Use Case where the low priority of purely retrospective projects delayed the progress even more.

Data Access

The Data Access subprocess has two possible starting points. The upper one is the one taken after the Project Preparation is finished. The lower one is taken if the data science team realizes in the Data Set Preparation subprocess that further data is needed to reach a data quality that is sufficient for the respective project. However, both starting points lead to the data science team having to decide whether they want to access data through a primary or a secondary data provider or both. Regardless of which option is chosen, a data export is requested from the respective data provider or data providers. After receiving this request, the respective data provider firstly has to check the legitimacy of the

⁴<https://medfak.uni-koeln.de/forschung/forschungsfoerderung/klinische-forschung/ethikkommission/antragsverfahren>

⁵<https://www.uk-koeln.de/forschung/medical-data-integration-center-medic/dokumente-formulare/>

data export, i.e. whether all necessary approvals and consents are available. If anything necessary is missing, an error is caused and the Data Access subprocess is aborted. If all necessary documents are available, the data provider exports the data from the clinical data system which is a primary or secondary system in case of the primary or secondary data provider, respectively. After the data has been exported a primary data provider can annotate the data with further information because the primary data provider is a domain expert in the medical field in which the data was generated. Secondary data providers do not necessarily have enough domain knowledge to offer further data annotation, especially because they have a variety of different medical data types in their data bases. Instead of the domain knowledge, though, they have technical expertise. Thus, they can offer a first data preprocessing which is modeled by calling the Data Preprocessing subprocess. This is particularly true for the MeDIC which can only provide data that is at least pseudonymized. In other cases, the steps of further data annotation or data preprocessing, depending on the kind of data provider, are optional. Finally, the respective data provider will make the data available for the data science team which can then access the data for further preprocessing. A final note on the choice of the data provider is that the data science team should always prefer Data Access via the secondary data providers as this means you can get pseudonymized or even anonymized data right away. Furthermore, it reduces the number of necessary steps if data of different departments is accessed via a single data provider. If the needed data is not available at the secondary data provider site, though, e.g. because the ETL route for that particular data has not been set up yet, the data can be accessed via a primary data provider. The BPMN visualization of the Data Access subprocess as it is described here can be found in appendix [A.7](#).

Data Set Preparation

Once the data can be accessed by the data science team, they need to compile the eventual data set by integrating individually accessed data sets and preprocessing them. I called this subprocess of the DAI process "Data Set Preparation". It starts with making the individually accessed data sets integratable, i.e. clean and transform it in a way that the individual data sets can be integrated afterwards. This is done by individually preprocessing them for which the Data Preprocessing subprocess is called. Then, the data sets are integrated into one full data set. This step is documented in the project metadata and followed by another call of the Data Preprocessing subprocess which now aims for increasing the data quality of the integrated full data set. To check the success of this step, the data quality is to be assessed afterwards as suggested by Kubben et al [11]. For this the data science team should use a data quality estimation framework like that of Weiskopf and Weng which I applied in the CUP Use Case (c.f. section [5.2](#)). If the data quality is sufficient, the subprocess of Data Set Preparation is finished. If there are still quality issues, the data science team has to decide whether they need further data to meet these issues. If that is the case, the Data Access subprocess is called again. Once it

finished the additional data access is documented in the project metadata and the newly accessed data needs to be made integratable by calling the Data Preprocessing subprocess another time. Afterwards, the newly accessed data can be integrated into the former fully integrated data set which is followed by another call of the Data Preprocessing subprocess. If no further data is needed to meet the identified quality issues, this call can take place directly. Then, the data quality is checked again after which the Data Set Preparation is finalized or another loop of data quality improvement is initiated. Just as the access and integration of data every action performed during data preprocessing in the Data Set Preparation subprocess is to be documented in the project metadata. The BPMN visualization of the Data Set Preparation subprocess as it is described here can be found in appendix A.8.

Data Preprocessing

In the subprocesses Data Access and Data Set Preparation another subprocess referred to as "Data Preprocessing" has been called. On the full workflow level this is a subsubprocess. It is carried out by the role that calls it. The first step is inspecting the data with the aim to identify data quality issues. Depending on which quality issues have been found, the data inspection can be followed by feature reduction, numerosity reduction or data transformation. All necessary changes are made to the data. Hereby, it should be strictly ensured that the changes are necessarily needed because the eventual data set must be as raw as possible to be reusable [29]. before the respectively preprocessing role has to decide whether it is still needed to identify individuals in the data set. If that is the case, nothing is done. If pseudonyms are sufficient for the further course of the project, the data should be pseudonymized and if no identification is needed at all anymore, the data should be anonymized. This ensures compliance to the legal conditions outlined in section 6.1.1. This data de-identification concludes the Data Preprocessing. All changes that are made to the data set during this subsubprocess should be documented in the project metadata. The BPMN visualization of the Data Preprocessing subprocess as it is described here can be found in appendix A.5. Other than the other BPMN models it does not show lanes specifying which role takes over the respective steps because this depends on the role that calls this subsubprocess. If it is called in the Data Access subprocess the tasks are carried out by the respective secondary data provider. If it is called in the Data Set Preparation subprocess the tasks are carried out by the data science team.

6.3.5 Performance Evaluation

What remains to be analyzed is how the performance of individual instances of the proposed workflow, i.e. project-specific executions, can be evaluated. In section 3.4 it was stated that the performance assessment can be done by executing or simulating the workflows. Because the simulation of workflows is outside the scope of this thesis, I assume

in the following that the performance evaluation is based on executing the respective workflow instance. Besides the evaluation approach, performance metrics for workflow evaluation in different domains have been listed in section 3.4. Some of them like the execution time and the number of used resources can directly be applied to assess executions of the proposed workflow. The only necessary consideration is the identification of resources used in the DAI process. I argue that classical data communication or data exchange resources are never the limiting factor in a process that needs as much human collaboration as the DAI process. Thus, I identify the number of people involved as the main limiting resource in this process. An increased number of participants in the workflow immediately increase both the duration of the execution due to increased need for communication and the cost of the project because the people involved need to be paid. Another cost factor that is to be considered when evaluating a workflow instance is the risk for the patient regarding data breaches because a good workflow execution should aim for minimizing this risk by establishing suitable data protection measures. Last but not least, the usability of the resulting data set is an important quality aspect of the DAI workflow. In section 3.2 I have described that FAIR datasets are especially usable. Therefore, I propose to measure the usability of the resulting data set by assessing its FAIRness. Furthermore, as indicated by Prof. Beyan in an advisory meeting during this thesis, the FAIRness of the compiled data set should be assessed twice. At first, it should be checked whether the data set is FAIR in the own research data network which would be the MII network in case of DAI processes at MeDIC. Secondly, a global or external FAIRness should be determined, i.e. evaluating whether the data set resulting from the DAI process is also findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable from or respectively by other research data networks like Gaia-X or the NFDI network mentioned in section 3.2. Further possible evaluation metrics partly used for workflow performance assessment are sharability and reproducibility (c.f. section 3.4). However, the reproducibility is given for every instance of the proposed workflow due to the thorough documentation of the process in the metadata. In contrast to that, the scalability is not given for any instance of the proposed workflow because the process is mainly based on manual analyses, inspections, decisions and actions leading to a significant increase in workload when the amount of accessed data and data sources increases. Thus, these aspects do not need to be evaluated for individual workflow executions. To conclude, I suggest the relevant metrics for evaluating the performance of a DAI workflow instance to be the duration as a time metric, the number of involved people as a time and cost metric, the risk for the individual patients as a cost metric and the internal as well as the global FAIRness as usability metrics. A visualization of this DAI workflow performance estimation guideline can be found in appendix A.9. As described by Tschüter et al. these single metrics should be assessed at different levels, i.e. first on the workflow level and if an issue is identified there the metrics should be determined on the subprocess or subprocess level. This enables an efficient but simultaneously targeted identification of performance bottlenecks

[55].

6.4 Expert Interviews

As described in section 5.4 I performed guided expert interviews with employees of UHC. The main purpose of these interviews was assessing the workflow, the surrounding framework and the performance estimation guideline proposed in section 6.3. The expert feedback on these aspects is documented in the interview transcripts in appendix B and analyzed in section 6.4.1. During the interviews some of the experts mentioned additional challenge of the DAI process which have not been covered in section 6.1 or examples illustrating the challenges outlined there. These are analyzed below in section 6.4.2. An overview of the interview participants and their function at UHC can be found in table 5.3.

6.4.1 Assessment of the Conceptualization

During the expert interviews I generally received positive feedback. The statements of the interviewees say that the workflow accurately reflects the DAI process. Partly, the interviewees expressed wishes for extending or changing the workflow based on their experiences. Furthermore, radiologist Simon Lennartz pointed out that the workflow will most likely be subject to changes once it is applied in practice. In the following I will summarize and analyze the comments I received on my proposed workflow, the surrounding framework and the performance estimation guideline.

The first questions of the interview asked the interviewees to which of the roles shown in figure 6.3.1 they would assign themselves to. The only role that was not mentioned was that of the "Ethics Committee" while the other two governmental roles, i.e. the "Data Protection Instance" and the "Use and Access Committee" were present. Furthermore, one of the interview participants is an expert in AI ethics. Thus, also the ethical part was represented. Hence, all fields of relevant expertise have been covered by the choice of interviewees.

Surrounding framework

Just as the workflow itself also the surrounding framework was generally approved by the experts. Concerning the "Roles and Actors" of the process (c.f. section 6.3.1) Feifei Li raised the question why I use both words "roles" and "actors". She suggested to decide on one to avoid confusion. Besides that, Dr. Ana Grönke proposed to add the role of the patient to the data providers since patients could provide data via apps, by using wearables or by filling forms. Prof. Beyer also said that the patients can be seen as some kind of data providers but he would see their role more in the governance category as

they can provide or recall their informed or broad consent affecting whether their data is used in the project. Another role, Dr. Ana Grönke and A.W. identified to be missing in the category "Governance" is that of the "Data Security Instance". According to them, the Data Protection Instance focuses on checking who can access the data. Their work is complemented by that of the Data Security Instance dealing with issues of technical data security. Moreover, Dr. Ana Grönke suggests to add the data science team itself to the data providers because in the course of compiling FAIR data sets they should also provide these to another research teams. Further comments regarding the role of the data science team included that it should be visibly more apparent that there are medical and technical experts forming this team. Dr. Simon Lennartz suggested to put them in two separate boxes within the big box of the data science team. Furthermore, according to Jonathan Okereke, I should consider adding also pure researchers to the members of the data science team because not all members of a data science team could be clearly assigned to be a technical or medical expert. Similarly, Dr. Thorsten P. pointed out that the PI of the data science team should get its own subrole within the data science team enabling to model the workflow in a way strictly assigning the responsibility for the organisational tasks to the PI.

Moreover, I received expert feedback for the System Concepts classified in section 6.3.3. R.D. suggested to add the term "Clinical" to the names of the system categories "Primary" and "Secondary" to ensure a clearer discrimination from the external non-clinical data systems. Similarly, Dr. Thorsten P. expressed that the clinical system categories should be separated visually from the non-clinical categories, e.g. by adding a line in the visualization that symbolizes security preserving firewalls between the clinical systems and external ones. Regarding external system concepts, Dr. Simon Lennartz, Jonathan Okereke and Scarlett Berressem expressed that the concept "Other hospital" should be added to the category "External" because accessing data from other hospitals brings other legal and organizational challenges with it. According to Dr. Thorsten P., also companies should be added as another concept in the category "External". Besides that, there were comments concerning the names of the system concepts. Firstly, Dr. Ana Grönke suggests to replace the term "wearables" by "health enabling technology" which covers a broader field of data sources including health apps. Secondly, Dr. Simon Lennartz pointed out that the term "Resident Physician" may be misleading as it is used to describe assistant physicians in the USA. For the same reason, Jonathan Okereke suggested renaming "Resident Physicians" to "Primary Healthcare Providers". He stated that the meaning of the latter term is clearer and broader also covering non-physicians like carers or therapists. Dr. Ana Grönke pointed out that that another misleading component is the definition of the "Primary Data Systems" as a system only containing data of a single department because the MeDIC also accesses primary data systems containing data from several departments. An example of this is the PDMS described in section 6.2.1.1. Thus,

she suggests to redefine this category in a manner that it also covers systems like the PDMS. Regarding the overall completeness of the classification, Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer made the comment that there will be edge cases like the NRW cancer registry whose assignment to one of the categories may not be clear but in general, the classification covers the most important system concepts, according to him.

During the interviews I additionally received expert feedback on the third part of the surrounding framework which are the aspects influencing data security described and analyzed in section 6.3.3. In almost every interview I was told that the visualization and naming of this framework component are misleading as it does not become clear that the mentioned aspects are not security levels themselves. Moreover, there was the criticism that the visualization either suggests that the aspects can be combined arbitrarily or that aspects displayed below each other belong together. This should be fixed according to the majority of interviewees. Another recurring criticized point was the aspect category "Access". Dr. Simon Lennartz, R.D. and Dr. Liliana Caldeira pointed out that the preliminary visualization gives the impression that the decision between an open and a restricted data set is purely binary although it is actually gradually. Thus they suggested to use a scale rather than two blocks. Jonathan Okereke additionally emphasized that considering authorization and defining access roles is crucial to enable granularity regarding data access. Similarly, Prof. Andreas Beyer pointed out that authentication and authorization are both needed to manage data access. Hence, he suggested that I should only list "Encryption" and "De-Identification" in the "Data Protection" category while defining the "Access" category to be controlled by "Authentication" and "Authorization". Besides the authorization, Scarlett Berressem and Dominik Zier mentioned that the category of "Documents" is missing in the overview. By that they understand contracts and guidelines guarding the assurance of data security. Moreover, Dr. Ana Gundert and A.W. identified the Demilitarized Zone (DMZ) as missing in the list of network connection options. Regarding security it is to be placed between the P- and the S-Net, allowing for running applications and scripts but still having no internet connection. Further aspects that could be considered when judging data security are the data integrity, availability and the vulnerability, according to Jonathan Okereke. For instance, the availability should be restricted for every component of the data set individually. Additionally, Jonathan Okereke suggested to rename some concepts. Firstly, the category "Protection" should be called "Privacy and Protection" as the mentioned aspects indeed are data protection measures but they ensure data privacy. Secondly, Jonathan Okereke proposes to rename the category "Network Connection" to "Network Segment Domains". Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer also suggested renaming that category. However, he would prefer the term "Network Security". Regarding the network concepts contained by that category Dr. Liliana Caldeira pointed out that P-Net and S-Net are only in uniclinics. She suggested choose more general levels.

Workflow

As mentioned above, I generally received positive feedback about the conceptualized workflow described in section 6.3.4. Those who have practical experience in the DAI process at UHC validated that it accurately reflects the necessary steps in the setting considered by this thesis (c.f. section 2). Dr. Simon Lennartz additionally validated my methodological approach of using literature and personal experience as a basis for the workflow development. According to him, including hands-on experience fosters realisability of the resulting workflow. Partly the workflow was criticized for its lack of agility, i.e. for being too rigid while others said it cannot be rigid enough and deadlines should be strictly enforced to enable progress. On the other hand, Dr. Liliana Caldeira noticed that there is latent agility in the workflow by sub-processes calling each other and loops. Further agility can and should be introduced in the Project Preparation step as outlined below.

The first subprocess of the workflow, the Project Preparation, was criticized by Feifei Li because of its complexity making it hard to understand it. However, the leader of the CCR at UHC Scarlett Berressem validated that the process actually is very complex and that the proposed BPMN model visualizes it very well. From the legal perspective, data protection officer Dominik Zier validated the correctness of the Project Preparation subprocess. Moreover, he suggested me to mention that the data science team should use the "Orientierungshilfe Krankenhausinformationssysteme" (OH KIS) as a guideline when designing the DPC. Furthermore, according to Dominik Zier, important principles to be considered are the data minimization, i.e. only access data you essentially need, and Privacy by design. He also suggests me to make clear that a proper DPC contains an exact specification of the planned project, the legal basis of the project, i.e. how is the processing of the data legally justified, the project's purpose, the data types, deletion periods and information about possible service providers including the exact contractual arrangements with them. A.W. and Dr. Ana Grönke, however, pointed out that besides developing such a DPC that is checked by the Data Protection Officer, additionally a Data Security Concept (DSC) containing technical specification of how the data security will be ensured needs to be developed and approved by the Data Security Officer. This step is currently missing in the workflow of the Project Preparation subprocess. Furthermore, Dr. Ana Grönke urged for adding an optional step of getting missing informed consents of patients after the requirements analysis. This step should be performed if during project design the data science team decides to use the informed consent of the patients as the legal basis for the project while noticing in the requirements analysis that this consent is not available for at least one patient. In contrast to that, Dr. Liliana Caldeira pointed out that some of the obligatory steps in the workflow should actually be optional. For instance, the check of the DPC by the Data Protection Officer could be skipped if only data of the own department is accessed and only people from that department process the data. She sees further optimization potential in already requesting the check of the

project proposal by the UAC when the EC has only just received the request to check the proposal. She indicated that the EC assigns a process number to every submitted project proposal which should already suffice to request the check by the UAC. Regarding sending the requests to the governance instances, Dr. Thorsten P. underlined that this falls into the responsibilities of the project PI while the rest of the data science team takes on a more advisory role. He suggests to make this visually apparent in the BPMN models by introducing a separate lane for the project PI. Furthermore, Dr. Thorsten P. indicated that the communication with external partners like companies is missing in the BPMN model of the Project Preparation step.

The second subprocess, the Data Access, was criticized less than the first and even named as a positive example for a well understandable workflow by Feifei Li. Still Dr. Simon Lennartz found an aspect that could be optimized which was the label of the first branching being "Choose suitable data provider". Instead he suggests to use "Request data from chosen data providers" because the data providers are already chosen in the Project Preparation subprocess during the project design step. Moreover, Dr. Thorsten P. pointed out that each time data is accessed via a secondary data provider the original primary data provider should be asked for approval because the data was generated in the department of that original data provider so he should at least be informed that his data is now reused for research. On the other hand, Dr. Thorsten P. expressed that the legitimacy check before data access is not feasible or useful at the site of the primary data provider. Instead each project should get the "approved" stamp after a through Project Preparation that can be quickly checked by the data provider. Dr. Ana Grönke, moreover, pointed out that I should add the possibility to access data from other data science teams who created a FAIR and therefore reusable data set before.

Concerning the last subprocess, the Data Set Preparation, Dr. Thorsten P. pointed out that it is important to here consider which member of the data science team is allowed to see the respective data and which tasks can be performed by which members. These information are to be taken from the specifications made in the Project management documents that were approved by the governance instances in the Project Preparation subprocess. Additionally, A.W. suggested to add a step of providing feedback to the data providers in case of severe data quality issues in the individually accessed data sets which are preprocessed at the beginning of the Data Set Preparation subprocess. The data provider could use the feedback to improve the data management system or the data collection procedure in the long run. Furthermore, Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer found an issue at the access of further data in the case of insufficient data quality. Here, the Data Access subprocess is called again. However, Prof. Beyer argues that instead the Project Preparation subprocess should be called so that another requirement analysis can identify whether the desired features and cases are actually available. Furthermore, this way it is assured, that the governance instances are informed about the additional data access.

Besides the three subprocesses the modeled DAI process contained the subprocess of Data Preprocessing for which three remarks were made during the expert interviews. Firstly, Scarlett Berressem underlined that the Data Inspection step should be done by a medical expert to ensure, that relevant data quality issues are identified. This is only possible with sufficient domain knowledge. Secondly, Dominik Zier stated that he cannot think of any use case in which the data cannot at least be pseudonymized. Thus, he suggests to remove the path that completely skips the de-identification. Thirdly, A.W. expressed that a data cleaning option should be added parallel to the feature reduction, numerosity reduction and data transformation.

Performance estimation guideline

The third and last part of the conceptualization is the performance estimation guideline developed in section 6.3.5. Just as the surrounding framework and the workflow it was presented to the experts. R.D. and Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer criticized the choice of the term "man power" to describe how many people have been involved in the DAI process that is to be examined. They suggest to instead use a more general and neutral term like "person months". Regarding the number of people involved, Dr. Simon Lennartz expressed that it is not only influenced by the workflow itself but also by confounding aspects like the respective environment and the project type. Hence, he suggests to also consider the number of steps taken. When asked about the completeness of the proposed performance metrics, many interviewees pointed out that costs for hardware and software are missing. R.D. additionally made the remark that the "risk for the patient" should be broadened to "societal risks". For instance, also the risk for the hospital whose reputation would suffer greatly from a data breach could be considered in the framework of societal risks, according to Dr. Ana Grönke. Further criticism was expressed regarding my proposal to check the usability of the data set resulting from the DAI process by assessing its FAIRness. Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer pointed out that the FAIRness of the data set helps to examine the technical usability of the data set but not the semantic usability. So, he suggests to additionally check whether the resulting data set suffices to answer the initially defined research questions of the project. Also regarding the semantic usability of the data set, R.D. pointed towards the paper "Datasheets for datasets" by Gebru et al. [108]. It compiles a list of questions which should be answered by the data set creators to increase the usability and reusability of the data set. Regarding the technical usability of the eventual data set, Jonathan Okereke added that the data model chosen to represent it and the choice of the persistence technology have a significant impact as both aspects affect the effort needed for following queries on the compiled data set.

6.4.2 Challenges of Data Access and Integration

Besides the feedback on the DAI process conceptualization analyzed in the previous section, the experts provided insights into current challenges of the DAI process at UHC. The main challenge mentioned by the interviewees was the fulfilment of the organizational and technical requirements resulting from assuring compliance to the legal and ethical requirements of MDS projects which brings significant delays with it and sometimes even makes projects impossible. To start with, Dr. Thorsten P. reported a case where the EC suggested that the treating physicians choose the CT data for the doctoral thesis of a medical student that has a contract with the departments including a confidentiality agreement. Such a prior choice of the CT data however, would make the doctoral thesis redundant in that case and is not possible for the treating physicians in their daily clinical practice in terms of time. So, here there is a clear conflict between the legal requirement of medical confidentiality and practical feasibility of MDS projects. The partly occurring overprotectiveness of the EC hindering practical progress has been validated by Scarlett Berressem who additionally pointed out that the IT department of UHC tends to be even more over-protective. In the past it had happened that the IT department cancelled projects which were already approved by the data protection and the EC. Moreover, for security reasons, they do not allow to execute scripts in the patient network without special permissions, according to Dr. Liliana Caldeira, and these permissions are hard to obtain. This special protection is necessary to assure security of the patient data but makes preprocessing the data e.g. anonymizing it or getting first statistics for data inspection very challenging. Besides the IT department also the EC sometimes makes questionable decisions, as indicated by Dr. Thorsten P., who reported that the EC once rejected a project proposal due to data protection concerns although the proposal was already approved by the data protection office. According to him, this is only one example for the insecurity regarding legal and ethical requirements for MDS projects as well as the partly non understandable decisions by governing instances. Besides that Dr. Ana Grönke and Scarlett Berressem criticize the long time taken at the Data Protection Office and the EC to check and evaluate project proposals. The current project delays resulting from these checks are a significant obstacle in recent MDS projects also lead to high personnel costs for the research departments, according to Dr. Thorsten P. From the other perspective, the data protection officer Dominik Zier reported that he often receives incomplete project specifications making it impossible for him to judge whether the respective data protection concept is sufficient. Repeated enquiries to the data science team about the exact project plan cause the significant delays criticized by the other interviewees, according to him. Furthermore he expressed that the incomplete project specification and therefore also the delays in approving the DPCs probably result from the researchers' lack of knowledge and training in the area of data privacy and protection. So, both sites, the researchers as well as the governance instances, would benefit from clear definitions of the

legal and ethical requirements. In this regard, Dr. Liliana Caldeira suggested to provide forms for all necessary approval processes. Even if not all fields could be filled in every project it would still be a great guidance for the researchers who often simply do not know what they need to provide to the governance instances. Another challenge, which is mainly faced by the developers of the technical MDS infrastructure and the data science team when designing the project, is to always base design decisions on the principles of data minimization and privacy by design. This was pointed out by Dominik Zier. Furthermore, every data science team has to deal with the extremely limited time windows of the medical experts who are usually additionally involved in clinically treating patients. Besides the time limit the clinical involvement leads to team meetings regularly being cancelled. Thus, MDS projects are only possible if the data science team members which are not involved in the clinical practice offer sufficient flexibility, as outlined by Scarlett Berressem. Dr. Thorsten P. expressed that hereby, however, it has to be ensured that the data science team is not exploited by a clinical project PI as there are tasks which clearly fall into the responsibilities of the clinical PI. These are e.g. the application for approvals which are not to be performed by the data science team even if the clinical PI does not find the time for them besides caring for patients. Here it is important to clearly assign responsibilities at the start of the project as described in section [6.1.4](#).

Chapter 7

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the results of the analysis performed in the previous chapter 6. Section 7.1 discusses the DAI process in the CUP use case followed by a discussion of the current DAI challenges in section 7.2. The eventual DAI process conceptualization improved based on expert feedback is described in section 7.3. It is based on the current legal, ethical, technical and organizational conditions at German University Hospitals, especially at UHC. Suggestions for improving the DAI process by optimizing the conditions are discussed in section 7.4. Eventually, section 7.5 elaborates on the limitations of the results presented in the following.

7.1 Evaluating the data set compilation in the CUP use case

A very central characteristic of the CUP use case is that it was the first MDS project for all involved parties including the CIO team, medical student Devina Soenarto and me. Due to the lack of experience both regarding organizational and technical aspects mistakes have been made and the DAI process was far from ideal. On the other hand, we as an interdisciplinary data science team gained a lot of experience which, firstly, I could use for developing the DAI workflow and, secondly, will help in further MDS projects at CIO Cologne.

The most apparent consequence of the inexperience was that the DAI process resulted in compiling a data set containing only 63 patients and additionally exhibiting a significant class imbalance (c.f. table 6.8). Such a data set is not suited for a well-working CUP classification system considering the data set sizes of successful primary tumor discovery systems described in section 4.2. Thus, another DAI process has to follow to compile a useful CUP data set. To enable avoiding the mistakes made in the first DAI process, I will

discuss the identified bottlenecks in the following. Firstly, the strict focus on only using already structured data significantly limited the choice of the data sources. Currently, the majority of clinical data is only available in unstructured reports or images requiring the application of NLP or image recognition approaches to make the contained information accessible for ML systems. As a result of the focus on structured data we used the CCR as the source for demographic and histological features. This means that we only include patients who got their primary diagnosis at UHC because the documentalists at CCR only document patients which legally must be documented. The reason for this are personnel limitations. Thus, we cannot get any structured documentation of recurrent cases or patients who come for further treatment to UHC from the CCR. The second system that was accessed was the study system of the RIS which provides structured information on the distribution of metastases in the form of RECIST evaluations. This data source choice led to only including study patients into our data set. Furthermore, we only got a subset of the metastases for each cancer case which are chosen according to the RECIST criteria. In an optimal case a full list containing all metastases should be accessed. However, other parts of the RIS have not been used as data sources as they only contain unstructured reports or images. The second mistake made in the CUP use case was assuming that for all patients for which metastases have been found these metastases have also been documented in the accessed time span. For some patients, though, the medical report used to document them in the CCR may have not been clear about the existence of metastases. These may have only been found in a later examination.

A very central consequence of the small data set size was the increased difficulty of anonymizing the data. As described in section 3.3, data anonymization follows the principle of hiding the individuals in the crowd by slightly changing the data such that re-identification becomes sufficiently hard. Thus, a small data set means that the data needs to be changed more. To not lose the information of the patients' age completely, we could only establish 2-anonymity. Furthermore, usually, there is a lot of room for optimizing the result of anonymization, i.e. significantly higher data usability with only slightly higher or even the same risk [14]. This can be achieved by fine-tuning the generalization hierarchies or limits such as the suppression limit [51, 54]. Due to given limitations regarding the data set size and the time to finish this thesis such an optimization was not performed in the CUP use case. However, ideally the risk should be at least below 10% which we failed to achieve in the given situation. On the other hand it should be considered that the data will not leave the UHC infrastructure at any point in the project. Thus, it will only be accessible for employees of UHC all of which signed confidentiality agreements. Hence, we deem this level of protection as sufficient also having in mind that with further generalization the usability would decrease significantly. Moreover, t -closeness was not established although it is advised by the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party to prevent inference of sensitive attributes which medical features certainly are (c.f. section

3.3). This was also due to the small data set size. Establishing t -Closeness here would have significantly reduced usability of the data here.

Another part of the DAI process in the CUP use case that could be optimized is the Data Quality Assessment. It was by far not exhaustive due to timing limitations only covering a check of completeness and basic plausibility. Before actually training an ML model on a data set a more thorough analysis would be needed which additionally controls for data bias to ensure fair classifications (c.f. section 6.1). Furthermore, we only checked the data quality but did not improve it, which would be a necessary step before actually using the data set.

Besides possibilities of optimizing the DAI process technically, there are also organizational aspects which could be improved. For instance, the CUP use case was designed to only access project specific data following the principle of data minimization. Additionally, we needed to provide a date at which the data set will be deleted in the project management document. Thus the resulting data set is highly project-specific and cannot be used in other projects. Now after performing the expert interviews I know that for getting a truly reusable data set that can be used in by several parties in a research data network a broad consent of each contained patient is needed. Furthermore, the pre-processing should not make any project-specific assumptions like only including patients with specific ICD-10 codes. Without such assumptions the data can be adapted to fit individual use cases. However, creating such a reusable data set requires a much more intense project preparation whose most challenging step most likely is obtaining the broad consent of all contained patients. On the other hand, once investing this effort can be worth it if the data set is actually reused which avoid duplicated efforts.

Furthermore, we encountered significant delays in the CUP project preparation which were caused my many people being involved in the communication pipeline, low priorities being assigned to retrospective use cases by the EC and absence of people due to holidays. Retrospectively, the process could have been accelerated by investigating who replaces the data protection officer during her absence. However, it was not indicated to us that she will not be available for as long as she was. So, I can validate the finding from section 6.1.4 that a clear communication and assignment of responsibilities is essential in practice.

7.2 Status Quo of Data Access and Integration

Medical data scientists in Germany face a significant number of insecurities when accessing and integrating medical data. Project-based decisions have to be made thoroughly considering relevant legal, ethical, technical and organizational aspects and measures outlined in section 6.1. Eventually, the governing instances have to be convinced that all relevant aspects have been considered sufficiently. How this is to be done concretely is

not specified but I identified a number of central trade-offs which are to be discussed when developing the project design. Additionally, these trade-offs also illustrate the complexity of the DAI project design. The first trade-off which is a present part of all data protection laws is that between patient privacy and scientific progress. As described in section 6.1.1 and 6.1.2 risking an individual patient's privacy by accessing, integrating and analyzing its data is only permissible if the beneficence of the MDS project is sufficient. At the same time, not using patient data hinders scientific progress, e.g. the development of treatment interventions that can significantly improve the health status of other patients. So, a pure focus on ensuring patient privacy should be avoided. Both sides are to be considered. This is also true for the second trade-off I identified. It is that between the reusability of the compiled data set and the principle of data minimization mentioned in section 7.1. The principle of data minimization demands that the researchers only access and integrate data that is necessarily needed for the project while a truly reusable data set does not make any assumptions about its future use. Thus, when compiling a truly reusable data set data minimization cannot be implemented. A third trade-off which became apparent during working on this thesis is that between information content and anonymity. When aiming for anonymizing the data set in the CUP use case (c.f. section 6.2.3.4) we saw that establishing 10-anonymity which is specified as a minimum requirement for anonymizing data (c.f. section 3.3) would lead to losing the age feature completely. This loss of information content can significantly reduce the usability of the compiled data set and when compiling a data set that is not usable any re-identification risk, no matter how small, is too big. Thus, especially for small data sets full anonymization sometimes does not make sense.

All three trade-offs outlined so far can be classified as trade-offs between the usability of the compiled data set and patient privacy protection. Besides that there are trade-offs which have the patient privacy on both sides. One of them is that between data minimization and anonymity. When only accessing data that is necessarily needed in a use case the compiled data set tends to become small which challenges data anonymization having the goal of hiding individuals in the crowd (c.f. section 3.3). The second such trade-off is that between anonymity and patient empowerment that was pointed out to me by Dr. Ana Grönke in the expert interview. The data protection laws referenced in section 6.1.1 demand that personal data should be anonymized as soon as possible. On the other hand, in the course of improving patient empowerment, it is essential to enable all patients to withdraw their consents allowing researchers to use their data at any point. However, once the data is fully anonymized it cannot be checked anymore whether the patients withdrew their consent.

Last but not least there is the technical trade-off between having many features per patient (wide data) or having many patients in the data set (tall data). One of the results from section 6.1.3 is that the variety of clinical examinations leads to only a small set of features

being available for all patients. Thus, the more features are to be accessed and integrated the fewer patients are there for which all these features are available. At the same time the heterogeneity decreases. Just as all formerly mentioned trade-offs this one needs to be made carefully considering the individual project's requirements. However, even if this trade-off is decided the heterogeneity of non-connected clinical data systems some of which cannot be accessed without having special software installed complicates the DAI process in any case on a technical level.

To assist researchers in dealing with the insecurities in the project design guidance and support is provided by initiatives like the MII (c.f. 3.2) or the TMF¹. Furthermore, especially the MII aims for promoting the ease of DAI processes at German hospitals. One of the challenges they face hereby is the patient-centricity of the existing clinical data systems. Historically, it was needed to quickly obtain all clinical data of a single patient for treatment decisions while MDS only needs a subset of the available clinical features for a large amount of patients, i.e. data-centricity. Currently, the DAI process is therefore usually done manually just as we did it in the CUP use case (c.f. section 6.2). The completely manual DAI is very error-prone, though. Furthermore, the clinical data systems lack structured information as outlined in sections 6.1.3 and 6.2.1 and the systems which actually contain structured clinical data only cover values which are necessarily to be documented in a structured manner due to personnel limitations. Another challenge is the high complexity of the Project Preparation subprocess requiring the exact specification of the project due to the sensitivity of the processed data. The processes of obtaining necessary approvals are mostly tailored towards prospective clinical studies which legally and ethically need a very strict project plan. For retrospective MDS projects which partly do not have a narrow objective but are of more exploratory nature this procedure design is highly obstructive. Moreover, Dr. Ana Grönke indicated in the expert interview that obtaining the patient consent is a great practical challenge but following the statements of Dominik Zier the broad consent of the patient is necessarily needed to compile truly reusable data sets. So, this effort cannot be circumvented. Another current challenge in the MDS Project Preparation is that there is no standard DPC or guideline as among other things the trade-offs mentioned above need to be considered individually for every project. Until the DPC is approved and ready for submission to the EC with the other Project Management Documents there is possibly a lot of communication with the data protection officer. In the CUP use case (c.f. section 6.2.1) fewer communication was necessary because the data does not leave the UHC infrastructure but this may be different for other projects.

Once the Project Preparation is finished further challenges arise when actually compiling the data set. One of them is that different departments deal differently with ethical principles like data minimization. In the CUP use case a whole export of demographic and

¹<https://www.tmf-ev.de/>

histological data from the last five years was possible without restrictions whereas the export from the LIS, which was already based on a prefiltered list of PIDs, needed to be filtered further on case IDs and lab values to make sure that we only receive data we actually need. Although deemed important intense data protection and security measures are named as substantially hindering the progress by various experts in the interviews which again alludes to the above mentioned trade-off between patient privacy and scientific progress. An execution of the DAI process fully compliant to legal and ethical requirements leads to significant delays because all tasks performed on non-anonymized data including the export of data can legally only be performed by treating physicians who are mainly occupied with treating their patients. They only sporadically find time to work on MDS projects. Moreover, some of the mentioned tasks already require technical expertise. In the CUP use case we solved this issue by me providing python scripts to the physicians based on information about the data I got from them. This approach, in turn, leads to a lot of necessary communication between the physicians and the technical experts especially when the scripts do not work as they are supposed to. After communicating the respective misbehavior of the script, the technical expert needs to fix it and afterwards the physician again needs to find the time to execute the fixed script. All these complications eventually make it very tempting to implement the process in a way that is not fully compliant to legal and ethical requirements. This situation is exacerbated by the fact that already approved concepts are re-evaluated and rejected by instances which are not responsible for the respective concept in the first place. In the expert interviews Scarlett Berressem reported that the IT department once rejected a project execution due to ethical and data protection concerns although the EC and the data protection office had already approved the project. Dr. Thorsten P. added that an employee of the radiological department similarly rejected projects after they had been approved by the governance instances leading to the cancellation of the projects. So, realisability of the MDS projects often suffers from overprotectiveness of different instances and in general from the high ethical and legal requirements in the medical domain.

To conclude, the sensitive nature of medical data combined with the ethical significance of MDS progress means that decisions and a number of trade-offs have to be made on a project-specific basis. This, in turn, results in a lack of concrete specifications and standardization eventually leading to insecurities and the risk of researchers not fully complying to legal and ethical requirements. Further challenges in the current DAI process for MDS at university hospitals are introduced by the technical infrastructures and procedural designs being tailored towards primary care and prospective studies and not for MDS. Suggestions of how the situation can be improved in future are outlined in section 7.4.

Aspect	Situation	Notes
Trade-offs in project design	Usability vs. patient privacy Patient privacy vs. patient privacy Technical	Patient privacy vs. scientific progress, Data minimization vs. reusability, Anonymity vs. information content. Data minimization vs. anonymity, Anonymity vs. patient empowerment Wide data vs. tall data
Data Systems	Patient-centricity, primary care focus Lack of structured data	MDS needs data-centricity, Manual DAI (error prone) needed Due to personnel limitations data is only structured if necessary e.g. CCR or billing data
Project Preparation	Complexity Lack of flexibility Broad consent (necessary) High project specificity	Due to sensitivity of medical data, and technical and organizational circumstances Process is mainly designed for prospective clinical studies Otherwise data set can only be used for a specified project, Often not available and hardly obtainable retrospectively Possibly a lot of communication with DPI and DSI necessary
Data Set Compilation	Overprotectiveness Inconsistencies Re-evaluation of approved projects	High legal and ethical requirements to protect privacy and security which is leading to delays or makes projects infeasible. E.g. different handling of ethical principles in different departments There are project which have been cancelled after the actually responsible instance had approved it

TABLE 7.1: Status Quo of the DAI process at German University Hospitals.

7.3 Data Access and Integration Process

This thesis aims at designing a Data Access and Integration Workflow for Medical Data Science at German university hospitals. As outlined in section 5.3 this was done by firstly creating the workflow, a surrounding DAI framework and a performance estimation guideline based on information gained by literature review and hands-on experience in a clinical use case (c.f. section 6.3 and appendix A) and secondly improving it by including feedback received on it during expert interviews. Thereby, I only implemented suggestions that fit within the setting of this thesis (c.f. section 2). The resulting workflow conceptualization can be found in the following. Section 7.3.1 contains the DAI framework, section 7.3.2 the DAI workflow and section 7.3.3 the performance estimation guideline. These are the results of the "Act" step of the PDCA workflow development cycle.

7.3.1 Data Access and Integration Framework

The DAI framework characterizes the landscape in which the DAI workflow operates by classifying roles involved in the process (7.3.1.1), system concepts that can serve as data sources (7.3.1.2) as well as measures to assure data security (7.3.1.3).

7.3.1.1 Roles

Section 6.3.1 describes the preliminary classification of "Roles and Actors" involved in the DAI process which I developed prior to the expert interviews. Following a suggestion by Feifei Li, I decided to only use the term "Roles" as a title for the classification to avoid confusion about the meaning and difference of the two terms "Roles and Actors". Because I received only positive expert feedback regarding the role categories "Research", "Governance" and "Data Provider" I kept the grouping of roles into these categories. The only role representing the "Research" category is the interdisciplinary "Data Science Team" consisting of the subroles "PI", i.e. the project leader, "Medical Experts", i.e. physicians, medical students and further healthcare providers, "Technical Experts", i.e. computer or data scientists and "Researcher", i.e. every MDS researcher that is primarily neither a medical nor a technical expert. The subroles "PI" and "Reseracher" had been added based on feedback of Dr. Thorsten P. and Jonathan Okereke. Following a suggestion of Dr. Simon Lennartz I chose boxes to depict the subroles which visualizes better that these are separate subroles than the bullet point visualization I chose previously. The "Governance" category contains the roles of the "Data Protection Instance", the "Data Security Instance", the "Ethics Committee", the MII "Use and Access Committee" as well as the "Patient". The "Data Security Instance" was added after Dr. Ana Grönke and A.W. had told me about it in the expert interviews. Adding the role "Patient" was proposed by Dr. Ana Grönke and Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer the latter of whom convinced me to add it to the category "Governance". I agree to Dr. Ana Grönke that patients can also act as data providers but I argue that they would then fall into the role of an "External Data Provider". This role of the "External Data Provider" was added because external data systems are contained in the preliminary classification of system concepts but the "External Data Provider" was missing in the "Data Provider" roles. It here comprises patients, other hospitals, companies, further healthcare providers as well as health enabling technology like wearables or health apps. Another suggestion was to add the "Data Science Team" as a "Data Provider" as they could and when aiming for FAIR data should make their compiled data sets available to other researchers. However, I argue that in this case the "Data Science Team" would act as a "Secondary Data Provider" and is therefore already contained in the classification. The eventual classification of roles involved in the DAI process is depicted in figure 7.1.

FIGURE 7.1: Classification of Roles involved in the DAI process.

7.3.1.2 System Concepts

The preliminary classification of system concepts outlined in section 6.3.2 was shown to the experts. R.D. suggested in response that the term "Clinical" should be added to the first two categories "Primary" and "Secondary" to separate them clearer from the external data systems. I implemented this and argue that this suffices as a differentiation from the external data systems because the purpose of this figure is to visualize a classification and not a technical specification. So, I did not implement further visual separation which was suggested by Dr. Thorsten P. The first category contains all "Primary Data Systems", i.e. those containing raw unprocessed data that is generated in primary care. Examples for such systems are the PDMS, the LIS or the RIS. Following a suggestion by Dr. Ana Grönke I redefined these "Primary Data Systems" here because the original definition did not include the PDMS which is, however, a primary data system. The second category contains all "Secondary Data Systems" which are systems providing data that was accessed and integrated from primary data systems. Possibly it is also already preprocessed. An example for such a system are the Data Servers of the MeDIC which are currently set up. The third category of system concepts are the external systems. Based on expert feedback from Dr. Simon Lennartz, Jonathan Okereke and Scarlett Berressem I added the category of "Clinical Partners" that was not present in the preliminary classification. Furthermore, I renamed the other categories. Dr. Thorsten P. suggested to include data bases of business partners like Philips while Dr. Simon Lennartz and Jonathan Okereke pointed out that "Resident Physicians" should be renamed because this term can be confusing and is not broad enough. Dr. Ana Grönke suggested to rename the category "Wearables" to a broader term as well. Taking over the experts' suggestions, the category of "External" system concepts now comprises the four concepts "Companies", i.e.

business partners and insurance companies, "Primary Healthcare Providers", i.e. general practitioners, caregivers or therapists, "Health Enabling Technology", i.e. wearables and health apps, as well as "Clinical Partners", i.e. data systems of other hospitals. The eventually resulting classification of system concepts is depicted in figure 7.2.

FIGURE 7.2: Classification of System Concepts that can serve as data sources in the DAI process.

7.3.1.3 Security Assurance Measures

Regarding the preliminary classification of "Security Levels" described in section 6.3.3 I received the expert feedback that both the visualization and the naming were misleading. Thus, I changed the naming to "Security Assurance Measures" which additionally is more fitting after the changes outlined below have been applied. Furthermore, after applying these changes I argue that also the visualization is clearer. Based on feedback from Dr. Liliana Caldeira, Dr. Ana Grönke, A.W. and Jonathan Okereke the "Network Connection" category was re-structured with the goal to be more general not focusing on the infrastructure of UHC. This made renaming the category necessary where I chose to use the suggestion by Prof. Beyer as it suited the new structure of that category best. So, the category now is called "Network Security" and cover the two security assurance measures of choosing the respectively right "Network Domain Segment", e.g. the very secure P-Net, the slightly less secure S-Net or the DMZ, and implementing "Restricted Executions" of e.g. scripts or applications in the respective domain. The second category has been renamed to "Privacy & Protection" following a suggestion by Jonathan Okereke. It now comprises the measures of "Encryption", "De-identification", i.e. pseudonymization or anonymization, and "Documents", e.g. contracts regulating

data processing by external partners and documentation of data accesses, transformation and usage. Adding "Documents" was proposed by Scarlett Berressem and Dominik Zier.

FIGURE 7.3: Classification of measures that can be used to ensure data security in the DAI process.

The third category "Access" was re-structured following the suggestion of Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer who pointed out that the two main measures for access control are "Authentication", e.g. check the identity of the accessing individual via secure passwords and "Authorization", e.g. defining strict access roles. This new structure also fulfills the wish for more granularity in that category pointed out by Dr. Simon Lennartz, Dr. Liliana Caldeira and Jonathan Okereke. Jonathan Okereke additionally suggested to consider data integrity, availability and vulnerability when determining the security assurance measures. So I mentioned that they are to be considered in the project design step in the Project Preparation subprocess described in section 7.3.2.1 and when checking data quality in the Data Set Preparation subprocess outlined in section 7.3.2.3. The eventual classification of Security Assurance Measures can be found in figure 7.3.

7.3.2 Data Access and Integration Workflow

Considering the status quo of DAI at UHC and state of the art data preprocessing pipelines for AI-driven data analysis, I developed a Data Access and Integration Workflow for MDS (c.f. section 6.3.4) which was validated and improved by collecting expert feedback on it (c.f. section 6.4.1). The workflow is a flexible but guiding collection of DAI steps providing a discussion basis for the design of concrete project workflows. It starts with the project idea being formulated after which the first of three subprocesses, the Project Preparation, is initiated. In the course of it the project is designed and necessary approvals

are obtained. Once the Project Preparation is successfully finalized the subprocess Data Access is started during which the data export is requested from and executed by the data providers. The third and last subprocess is the Data Set Preparation which covers the integration of individually accessed data sets, the preprocessing of the data as well as data quality assurance. The second and the third process each call the subprocess Data Preprocessing that provides the possibility to mitigate data quality issues, fit the data to the requirements of the respective project and de-identify the data to protect it. During the whole workflow all access and data transformations are to be documented in the Project Metadata that eventually serves as a source for data provenance information. In an interview AI Ethics expert R.D. pointed out that Gebru et al. published a paper in 2021 that can provide orientation for creating useful Metadata [108]. The last step of the DAI workflow is storing the compiled data set and the Project Metadata such that it is accessible for all researchers that may access it. The visualization of this workflow can be found in figure 7.4. Detailed descriptions of the subprocesses can be found in the following sections.

FIGURE 7.4: Data Access and Integration - Full Process Workflow modeled with BPMN.

During the expert interviews I received the feedback that the workflow seems to lack agility. I agree that the high-level process depicted in figure 7.4 seems very rigid but this because it specifies which subprocess or step is to be called once the previous step or subprocess has been completed successfully. When looking at the models of the individual subprocesses it becomes apparent that there are branches and loops enabling agile project design. Furthermore, the third subprocess again calls the first subprocess in case of missing data. Thus, even on the upper process level agile decisions throughout the project are

possible. The presence of this latent agility was verified by radiological data scientist Dr. Liliana Caldeira in the expert interviews.

7.3.2.1 Project Preparation

The Project Preparation subprocess has two start points. The first is taken at the beginning of a DAI process after the project idea has been formulated ("Project idea is formulated"). Then the exact research questions are specified followed by analyzing the project requirements and designing the project. The second start point is taken when the data science team realizes in the third subprocess that further data needs to be accessed ("Access further data"). Because the research questions were already specified in that case this step can be skipped here and the data science team directly goes to the step "Analyze requirements and design project". This is necessary since the project design might have to change when further data is accessed. Also the governing instances have to approve the access of further data.

Especially if the first start point was taken the step "**Analyze requirements and design project**" is very intense including a thorough analysis of the project goals and methodology as well as a well-thought project design. Aspects that should be chosen within the project design are the legal and ethical foundation of the project, e.g. retrospective use case, patient consent or scientific exemption, the data features, a characterization of suitable clinical cases, the methodology, the data sources, data models and the eventually used data persistence technology as well as measures to ensure data security like encryption, de-identification or access control. To choose these measures the "Orientierungshilfe Krankenhausinformationssysteme" (OH KIS) which summarizes should and can criteria can serve as a valuable guideline. As outlined in section 6.1.1, the de-identification should in any case be implemented as strict and as soon as possible. On the other hand, the trade-offs listed in section 7.2 should be considered as well. Further security related principles to keep in mind are data integrity, availability and vulnerability as well as data minimization and privacy by design. Besides, the ensuring data security another essential part of the project design is a clear assignment of responsibilities (c.f. section 6.1.4). If, furthermore, the legal foundation of the project is the consent of the patient, this consent must be available or obtained. Dr. Ana Grönke had expressed that the process of obtaining patient consent should be added to the workflow due to its complexity. However, for now I left it out to avoid complicating the workflow even further. All results of the requirements analysis and project design are documented both in the Project Management Documents (PMD) and the Project Metadata. All questions coming up in the remaining workflow should be answered using the results now documented there.

Once the project design is finalized, based on the PMDss the Project PI has to decide whether an approval of the Data Protection Instance (DPI) or the Data Security Instance

FIGURE 7.5: Project Preparation subprocess modeled with BPMN.

(DSI) is needed. If an DPI approval is needed the PI develops a **Data Protection Concept (DPC)** whereby the other members of the data science team act as advisors. This DPC should include an exact specification of the planned project including who will access the data at which point, the legal basis of the project, i.e. how is the processing of the data legally justified, the project’s purpose, the data types, deletion periods and information about possible service providers including the exact contractual arrangements with them. Then the content of the DPC is documented in the Project Metadata and the PMDs, after which the DPC is sent to the DPI who either approves or rejects it. If it is rejected, the PI receives a request to revise the DPC and together with the other data

science team members implements the feedback of the DPI into the DPC. Afterwards the DPC is sent to the DPI again for another check. If the DPI accepts a DPC, the PI receives an DPC approval. Besides that, a project potentially needs an approval of the DSI. For that the PI advised by the other data science team members develops a **Data Security Concept** (DSC) which contains a description of technical and organizational data security measures. The content of this concept is documented in the Project Metadata and the PMDs after which the DSC is sent to the DSI who either approves or rejects it. If it is rejected, the PI receives a request to revise the DSC and together with the other data science team members implements the feedback of the DSI into the DSC. Afterwards the DSC is sent to the DSI again for another check. If the DSI accepts a DSC, the PI receives an DSC approval. Every received approval is documented in the PMDs. Following the feedback of Dr. Liliana Caldeira that MDS projects only using the data of the own department do not need an DPC or DSI approval, the two approval processes described above are now optional in the workflow model.

Once all necessary approvals regarding data security and data protection are obtained, the PI needs to check whether an approval from the EC is needed. For instance, purely retrospective use cases do not necessarily need one. If an EC approval is needed, the PI requests a check of the Project Proposal from the EC which will examine the PMDs possibly including the DPC and DSC with the respective approvals regarding their compliance to ethical principles. If they reject the project proposal, they send a request to revise the project design to the PI whereupon the data science team will go back to the step of analyzing the project requirements and designing the project. This time a possibly necessary check of the DPC or DSC is less complex because there already exists an acceptable DPC or DSC, respectively. The DPI or DSI only need to approve the changes. If the EC accepts the Project Proposal an EC approval is sent to the PI and documented in the PMDs. Then the PI needs to consult these PMDs checking whether an approval of the Project Proposal by an MII UAC is needed. If that is the case, the PI sends a request to check the Project Proposal to the UAC. This committee then examines the PMDs including all approvals obtained so far checking whether the project is overall legitimate. If they reject the Project Proposal, they send a request to revise the project design to the PI. Just as in the case of receiving such a request from the EC the data science team will go back to the step of analyzing the project requirements and designing the project. Also similarly a possibly necessary check of the new DPC or DSC is less complex. If the UAC accepts the Project Proposal, an UAC approval is sent to the PI and documented in the PMDs. In that case or if the check by the UAC was skipped, the subprocess Project Preparation is completed sending the end message "Project Design is finalized and accepted" to the high-level workflow. So, eventually, the roles "Data Science Team", "Data Protection Instance", "Data Security Instance", "Ethics Committee" and "Use and Access Committee" are involved here. Additionally, the "Patient" participates

in the subprocess, if the legal foundation of the project is the patient consent. The BPMN model of the Project Preparation subprocess is depicted in figure 7.5.

It is to be noted that the workflow above describes the optimal process. If the project urgently needs all approvals, the approval of the UAC can already be requested when the EC had assigned a process number to the Project Proposal sent to them. This process number can be submitted to the UAC instead of the EC approval number.

7.3.2.2 Data Access

The Data Access subprocess starts after the Project Preparation has finished. Then the data export is requested by the data science team from the data providers specified in the PMDs. The first step for each data provider is checking the legitimacy of the data export, i.e. checking whether necessary approvals and consents are available. As pointed out by Dr. Thorsten P., especially the primary data providers do not have the personal capacity to perform an in-depth legitimacy check. Thus the data science team should enable an easy check already providing necessary approvals and consents in the data export request. Simply skipping the check is not acceptable, though. This is particularly true if the legal basis of the project is some kind of consent (informed or broad) in which case the availability of the consent has to be checked prior to any data access because such a consent can be withdrawn by the patient at any point in time. If any necessary approval or consent is missing, the Data Access subprocess ends with an error message. Otherwise the data can be exported from the respective clinical system which is documented in the Project Metadata. If this export is performed by a secondary data provider the original primary data provider who once made this data available should be informed prior to the export. This way the primary data providers stay up to date about the usage of the data created in their departments so that they can inform the patients upon request and can possibly get into contact with the data science team offering scientific report in the respective project. After the data has been exported a primary data provider can offer further data annotation, i.e. segmentation of radiological images or labeling of clinical cases, because the primary data provider is usually a domain expert. This does not hold for a secondary data provider but those may need to e.g. pseudonymize the data before making it available for the data science team. At least this is the case for the MeDIC in Cologne which is part of the MII and therefore has to follow its data protection regulations requiring the pseudonymization. So, instead of the data annotation the secondary data provider can offer Data Preprocessing which represents a subsubprocess in the DAI workflow. Both the data annotation and the Preprocessing are to be documented in the Project Metadata if they are carried out. Eventually the data is made available to the data science team who can access it. This completes the subprocess Data Access which now sends the end message "Data is available". So, the roles involved in this second subprocess are the

”Data Science Team” as well as the ”Primary Data Provider” and the ”Secondary Data Provider”. The BPMN model of the Data Access subprocess can be found in figure 7.6.

FIGURE 7.6: Data Access subprocess modeled with BPMN.

7.3.2.3 Data Set Preparation

The Data Set Preparation subprocess starts when the Data Access is completed. It integrates the data sets individually accessed by the data providers. Thereby it is already possible to perform the first step of this subprocess once the first data set was made available by one of the data providers. This first step is to make the individual data sets integratable by calling the Data Preprocessing subsubprocess on them. Afterwards

the original Data Provider is contacted in the case that severe data quality issues have been encountered during the Preprocessing. This enables the Data Provider to adapt the data collection, documentation or persistence technique which eventually improves the data quality in the respective data system. Once all accessed data sets have been made integratable, they can be integrated into one full data set which is most likely done by joining them on the PID or the pseudonym by which the PID has been replaced in the course of pseudonymization. Then the data science team adapts the fully integrated data set to the project requirements by calling the Data Preprocessing subprocess on it. This is followed by assessing the data quality using a data quality assessment framework like that of Weiskopf and Weng [27]. The experience from the CUP use case has shown that the domain knowledge of the medical experts in the data science team is crucial to perform this Data Quality Control meaningfully. Furthermore, the quality check could assess data integrity. If the data quality does not suffice, the data science team needs to decide whether further data is needed. If that is the case, the Project Preparation subprocess is called again with the goal to access further data. This corresponds to starting that first subprocess at the second starting point (c.f. section 7.3.2.1). Once the further data is available it is made integratable by calling the Data Preprocessing subprocess on it. Afterwards the additionally retrieved data is integrated into the originally fully integrated data set followed by Preprocessing this new fully integrated data set. Then another Data Quality Check takes place. If the data quality suffices the Data Set Preparation subprocess is completed sending the end message "Data Set is prepared". All changes that are made to the data set throughout this subprocess are documented in the Project Metadata. Figure 7.7 shows the BPMN model of the Data Set Preparation Process.

FIGURE 7.7: Data Set Preparation subprocess modeled with BPMN.

7.3.2.4 Data Preprocessing

FIGURE 7.8: Data Preprocessing subprocess modeled with BPMN.

What remains to be discussed regarding the workflow is the subprocess Data Preprocessing. It is called by the Secondary Data Provider in the Data Access subprocess or by the Data Science Team in the Data Set Preparation subprocess. In both cases it starts with inspecting the data set on which it was called. In the expert interviews Scarlett Berressem pointed out that the inspection should be done by a medical expert because domain knowledge is essential to find true data quality issues. After the data inspection the data is treated according to the identified data issues. If there are too many features, feature reduction is to be performed. If there are too many clinical cases, Numerosity reduction is needed. If there are redundancies or wrong values like outliers, a data cleaning step is to be included. If the identified issues requiring advanced data transformations the Data Transformation step is taken. Possible transformations which are executable here are calculating features from others, normalization, bias mitigation or imputation of missing values. However, I argue that only those transformations should be implemented which are necessarily needed as for the creation of a truly reusable data set that can be used in many and diverse projects the data should be as raw as possible making as few assumption about its usage as possible [29]. The four mentioned options to treat the data are repeated until there are no data issues left. If there have not been any initially the data does not have to be treated at all. All changes made to the data are documented in the Project Metadata. The Data Preprocessing is completed with executing necessary de-identification measures, i.e. pseudonymization or anonymization. Which measure is to be taken or whether any measure is necessary at all is to be taken from the PMDs. The BPMN model of the Data Preprocessing can be found in figure 7.8. It does not contain

any pools or lanes like the other BPMN models because this subprocess can be carried out by both the Data Science Team and a Secondary Data Provider.

7.3.3 Workflow Performance Estimation Guideline

The workflow proposed by this thesis should serve as a guideline supporting the design of concrete DAI processes in MDS. To enable assessing the performance of these concrete processes I came up with a workflow performance estimation guideline in section 6.3.5 which was evaluated by employees of UHC in expert interviews and afterwards improved based on that feedback. It suggests a number of performance metrics for each of which I will provide a way to measure it in the following. The first category of performance metrics assesses the complexity of the process. These metrics are the "Duration" of the process, i.e. how long did it take to compile the data set, the "Number of Steps", i.e. how many steps were necessary to perform the DAI process and the "Person Months", i.e. how many people have been involved for which period of time. The higher the value of each of these metrics the higher is the complexity of the DAI process. The metric "Number of Steps" was added following a suggestion by Dr. Simon Lennartz and the metric "Man Power" was renamed to "Person Months" as proposed by R.D. and Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer. After these changes I decided that "Complexity" is a better title for this category than the original title "Time". The second category of performance metrics is the "Cost" of the DAI process. On the one hand, there is the "Societal Cost" including the risk of data leakage which at the first place is a risk for the patient whose data is leaked but also for the hospital whose reputation would suffer from such a data breach. By renaming the metric from "Risk for the patient" to "Societal Cost" it was made more general which was a wish expressed by R.D. and Dr. Ana Grönke. The "Societal Cost" could be assessed by calculating the re-identification risk for the individuals in the data set considering the attacker models described in section 3.3. On the other hand, there is the "Monetary Cost" including costs for personnel, hardware and software needed for the DAI process. This cost was added because the majority of interviewees had pointed out that costs for hardware and software were completely missing in the preliminary performance estimation guideline. The "Monetary Cost" can be calculated by summing up all individual costs. The third and last category of workflow performance metrics is the "Usability" of the resulting data set. After Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer and R.D. had pointed out that the semantic usability is missing in the preliminary classification of metrics, this category now comprises the "Technical Usability" as well as the "Semantic Usability". The former can be evaluated by assessing the FAIRness of the compiled data set (c.f. section 3.2). As outlined in section 6.3.5, I here follow a suggestion by Prof. Beyan and specify that the FAIRness of the data set should be assessed internally within the own research data network, i.e. MII, as well as globally also considering other research data networks, e.g. Gaia-X or NFDI. Jonathan Okereke expressed that the choice of the persistence technology and the data

model used to represent the data set have a crucial influence on the "Technical Usability" as well. However, I argue that the choice of the data model and the persistence technology influence the data set's FAIRness. So, assessing the FAIRness already considers them. As indicated by Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer, the "Semantic Usability" could be evaluated by checking whether the compiled data set suffices to answer the initially specified research question. The visualization of the metrics classification is shown in figure 7.9. Table 7.2 provides an overview over the proposed metrics and suggestions to evaluate them. As described in section 6.3.5, the evaluation should firstly be performed on the whole workflow level and in case of performance issues being identified, the metrics are to be assessed on subprocess or even subprocess level.

FIGURE 7.9: Classification of metrics applicable to estimate the performance of a DAI workflow instance.

Metric	Evaluation suggestion
Duration Number of Steps Person Months	Checking how long the compilation of the data set took. Counting how many steps were necessary in the DAI process. Checking how many people were involved in the project for which period of time.
Societal Cost Monetary Cost	Calculating the re-identification risk for individuals in the compiled data set. Summing up all costs the process introduced for e.g. personnel, hardware and software.
Technical Usability Semantic Usability	Assessing whether the compiled data set is FAIR within the MII network or other research data networks as well as the Checking whether the compiled data set suffices the answer the original research question(s).

TABLE 7.2: Metrics applicable to estimate the performance of a DAI workflow instance accompanied by a suggestion for evaluating them.

7.4 Suggestions for Improvement and Challenges

The discussion of the current DAI process at German University Hospitals in section 7.2 revealed that there is a lot of room for making the process faster, cheaper and more effective. However, this requires legal, ethical, technical and organizational changes. In the following, I will provide suggestions for improving the DAI process with regards to the performance metrics listed in section 7.3.3. An overview over the improvements suggestions is contained by table 7.3.

Measure	Submeasures
Improve patient consent management	Integrate obtaining consent in routine Digitalization
Increase accessibility and interoperability of data (systems)	Standardization Increase data-centricity New legal basis for data access in MDS Simplify system access approval process
Reduce insecurities in the DAI process	Provide support in project design Provide education Standardization
Simplify project approval processes	Avoid overprotectiveness Templates and forms Create a central governance instance
Increase quality and reproducibility	Automation of the DAI process Thorough documentation Standardization

TABLE 7.3: Suggestions for improving the DAI process at German University Hospitals with respect to the metrics listed in section 7.3.3.

Due to the high sensitivity of personal data and especially personal medical data the legal foundation of an MDS project is very crucial. The easiest way to justify processing of personal medical data is having the informed consent of the patient. If the data is to be processed by somebody else than the treating physician this is in fact the only way to justify the processing. However, the consent of the patient is often not collected in daily routine and obtaining it retrospectively for an MDS project is very cumbersome or even impossible if the patient has already passed away or moved without communicating the new contact information. So, the DAI process could be simplified greatly if the patient consent would already be obtained when the patient is treated. Especially useful is a broad consent like that of the MII² with which the patients can consent to their data being processed in research in general not only in a specific project. Additionally, the consent management could be improved by digitizing it, i.e. making the information whether a patient provided an informed or broad consent digitally in a data base. So far, most consents are only available on paper or as scanned pdf files.

²<https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/de/mustertext-zur-patienteneinwilligung>

Current technical issues of the DAI process mainly relate to the heterogeneity, lack of connection and patient centricity of the clinical data systems. Additionally, legal restrictions of the raw data not being available for researchers which are not simultaneously treating physicians result in organizational complexity significantly increasing all "Complexity" metrics and thereby also the "Monetary Costs". So, a first suggestion for improving the DAI process is making the data and data systems more easily accessible and more interoperable. For without data MDS is not possible. This measure has two dimensions which are re-designing the clinical infrastructure, on the one hand, and the organizational structure, on the other hand. The technical re-design should include counteracting the missing connection of the clinical data systems and the heterogeneity by standardization. Another aspect is actually making the data more accessible by increasing the data-centricity of the system, i.e. making it easier to look up a restricted set of values for a large amount of patients, which significantly reduces the time and complexity of identifying suitable cases and features in the data systems. The current data system architectures mostly do not allow this. So to conclude here, the technical infrastructure is currently designed for primary care and necessary documentation while the requirements of MDS and secondary data use are still mostly ignored. This should change. Thereby, the principle of privacy by design and still enabling a fast access to all data of a single patient for primary care is to be kept in mind. The second dimension of making the data more accessible is adapting the organizational structure. Firstly, I suggest to introduce a legal basis, something like a medical confidentiality, for technical experts in MDS and medical students working with patient data. I found that currently the only possibility to make raw data available to these groups of researchers is to have the consent of the patient which is however challenging (c.f. above). Legally enabling technical experts and medical students to see the medical raw data in the absence of patient consent but protecting the data with confidentiality agreements would decrease the amount of communication necessary between these researchers and the treating physicians in projects justified via retrospectivity or scientific exemption. This decreases the process duration significantly and enables the treating physicians to invest more time into primary care. Furthermore it would increase the practical feasibility of many MDS projects significantly. Secondly, the approval process for accessing medical data systems should be simplified. Some medical employees of the MeDIC Cologne are legally allowed to access the primary clinical data systems. From them I know that for each data system a separate application had to be filled out each of which required the specification of the exact system sections. This is not possible for someone who does not know the system because system documentations are not provided for security reasons. Here, my suggestion would be to make the process project- or scientific-centric instead of system-centric, i.e. the medical researcher should only specify which kind of data is needed while the selection of data systems and sections within them is made by an employee knowing the clinical data infrastructure completely. Besides reducing the workload for the medical researcher this would also increase privacy

because the access is only granted to sections actually needed by the researcher and not to all sections the researcher thinks he needs to access.

Additionally, insecurities of any kind are currently a big issue in the DAI process. To reduce them I firstly suggest that university hospitals should provide guidance in MDS project design. The decisions that are to be made by the Data Science Team in this step (c.f. section 7.3.2.1) are manifold and often the Data Science Team lacks expertise in some relevant areas. This leads to insecurities and eventually mistakes in the project design as additionally the collection of relevant information regarding processes and systems is cumbersome due to the high security standards and missing documentation. Thus, I suggest to establish a central place providing information about relevant project requirements and possible data sources. A second possible measure against insecurities is offering educational workshops on correct data privacy protection and data handling for new employees. For when I started in the CIO CUP use case the whole Data Science Team needed to put a lot of effort into finding respective documents and collecting relevant information. Not all researchers may do this which can result in insufficient data protection and security. A third measure counteracting insecurities is standardization and documentation which is also one of the main goals of the MII (c.f. section 3.2).

A fourth major issue of the current DAI process is the complexity of obtaining necessary approvals during Project Preparation. The majority of experts I interviewed and the reviewed literature mentioned the overprotectiveness of governing instances often making it infeasible to execute projects compliant to their decisions. Sometimes they even cancel projects completely. On the one hand, such overprotectiveness leads to a lot of missed opportunities because researchers may not even propose a project because they expect the proposal to be rejected in any case. On the other hand, other researchers may not fully comply to ethical and legal requirements to still perform a project although the requirements specified by the governing instances make it infeasible. So, overprotectiveness should be counteracted e.g. by raising awareness that it can also have unethical consequences to be too strict. A second measure to simplify the project application process is creating templates and forms for obtaining approvals from the governing instances. Furthermore, this supports the researchers in saving time and skipping steps. Dr. Liliana Caldeira pointed out in the expert interviews that even if not all fields in such a template or form are applicable to the respective project it still helps greatly to know what information is required. Furthermore, creating a central governance instance like the UAC judging legal and ethical compliance of a project proposal would simplify the Project Preparation subprocess significantly. The data science team would have to submit a project description and necessary filled forms to such a central instance instead of communicating with DPI, DSI, EC and UAC. This would reduce the Project Preparation duration, cost and complexity. The UACs currently do not fully take this suggested role because they still require approvals from DPI, DSI and EC to be provided.

Last but not least, based on the expert feedback by Prof. Dr. Andreas Beyer I suggest to automate steps in the DAI process where possible. For instance, the data inspection could partly be automated calculating standard statistics and information regarding the data that enable the technical experts of the data science team to already take first decisions before the treating physicians find the time to look at the data. Furthermore, the automation itself already saves a lot of time and reduces workload for the data science team. Accompanied by a thorough documentation of processes e.g. in form of metadata (c.f. section 7.3.2) and increased standardization which was already mentioned above, automation can help to increase the quality of the compiled data sets and the reproducibility of the DAI process.

All five outlined suggestions for improving the DAI process carry the potential to reduce the Duration of the process and the number of necessary steps. By doing so, they also decrease the Person Months which, in turn, reduces the Monetary Costs. Moreover, the proposed measures simplify the compliance to legal and ethical requirements which increases the chances of sufficient data privacy protection and therefore decreases the risk of data breaches. Additionally, some suggestions reduce the workload on treating physicians enabling them to spend more time on primary care. Hence, also the Societal Cost is reduced, resulting in the fact that implementing any of the mentioned measures enables improving the DAI process performance in terms of all Complexity and Cost metrics. Furthermore, the Technical Usability, i.e. the FAIRness of the resulting data set, can be improved after the accessibility of the data systems and the reproducibility have been increased. An improvement of the Semantic Usability is enabled by all mentioned suggestions because they either simplify the organizational part of the project, the technical or both. So, it will be easier for the Data Science Team to compile a data set that can be used to answer the originally specified research questions.

To conclude, generally the secondary use of medical data has to move more into the focus at university hospitals to enable DAI processes or make them faster, cheaper and more effective, respectively. The key measures needed for this are improving the patient consent management, increasing the accessibility of the data and the data systems, reducing insecurities in the DAI process, simplifying the project approval process and increasing data quality and reproducibility. Implementing all of them corresponds to enabling optimization of the DAI process in terms of all performance metrics listed in 7.3.3. Eventually, this, in turn, enables successful MDS projects which will improve health care significantly in the long run. Initiatives like the MII are an important factor accelerating this process but I argue that the clinics themselves must also become active in order to create a real change.

7.5 Limitations

A main limitation of this thesis is that the proposed conceptualization including the DAI workflow has not been tested in practice yet. This is because the DAI process in the CUP use case already took very long so that a second DAI process could not be initiated within the scope of a master thesis. As pointed out by Dr. Simon Lennartz in the conducted expert interviews the conceptualization will probably have to be adapted to individual projects once it is tested in practice. Thus, as described in section 2, the proposed workflow should be taken as a guiding basis for project design discussions and further improvements rather than a strict process specification. Another consequence of not being able to execute the proposed workflow in practice was that I instead validated it by collecting expert feedback on it.

The feedback from the expert interviews revealed limitations introduced by the information sources I used to gain practical DAI experience. For instance, the main information source for the designed workflow was my experience from the DAI process in the CIO CUP use case at UHC. So, I only got to know clinical data storage systems used at UHC and due to the setting of the use case additionally only those containing structured data. Other systems may provide the same or even more information in different formats but these systems may not be captured by my conceptualization. Additionally, only considering structured data resulted in the workflow not covering the preprocessing of unstructured data. Furthermore, the CUP use case was purely retrospective and accessed data from different clinical departments of only one university hospital. No external partner nor another hospital were involved in the use case. Thus, I did not gather experience in prospective use cases, in use cases accessing data from only one department or in use cases integrating data from several hospitals. Moreover, I obtained a lot of information from employees of the MeDIC Cologne which belongs to the MII. Resulting from that the thesis has a focus on processes in the MII network. Performing DAI in other research networks like Gaia-X or NFDI may require small changes like obtaining approvals of committees other than the UAC but these changes should be rather small because I aimed for designing the workflow as broad as possible.

The limitations mentioned above resulted in several experts pointing out aspects and steps missing in the DAI workflow, the DAI framework or the performance estimation guideline. Since I implemented that feedback into the final version of the conceptualization I argue that it now covers the vast majority of MDS projects although preprocessing of unstructured data and communication with external partners including other hospitals is still omitted. This decision was made because I lack personal experience in these areas which could not be compensated sufficiently with the received expert feedback and the results from the performed literature review. Thus, it remains future work to add these aspects to the conceptualization.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

The access and integration of medical data is an essential task to initiate projects in MDS. However, this thesis identified several challenges complicating the DAI process be it legally, ethically, technically or organizationally. Besides listing these challenges the thesis additionally collected and suggested measures to encounter them in sections 6.1 and 7.4. Furthermore, as a first step for practically improving the DAI of real-world data from university hospitals, this thesis proposed a widely applicable DAI process conceptualization including a surrounding DAI framework, a generic DAI workflow and a performance estimation guideline. The conceptualization serves as a discussion and working basis both for DAI project design by medical data science teams and for standardization and improvement of the DAI process by MDS researchers or initiatives like the MII.

The proposed workflow operates in the first part of the research data lifecycle. In terms of the CRISP-DM model described in section 3.1 it covers the phases of Business Understanding, Data Understanding and Data Preparation. Thereby, it not only describes a series of successive steps and their dependencies but also provides advice on individual steps. For instance, it suggests to take the OH-KIS as a reference for identifying suitable data protection measures, it lists relevant questions to be answered by a Data Protection Concept and suggests a frameworks for data quality assessment. The workflow conceptualization was validated in guided expert interviews with employees of UHC. The feedback received by them was implemented into a preliminary version of the conceptualization which eventually led to the final version proposed by this thesis.

Besides developing the DAI process conceptualization this thesis examined the current challenges in the DAI process. As a very central result I found that the whole process is not clearly defined but based on vague requirements and subjective decisions by governing instances. The researchers often lack an overview of the requirements which can lead to them failing to comply to these requirements. On the other hand, the governing instances are often overprotective mostly considering the ethical rights of the patients whose data

should be processed and thereby ignoring the ethical rights of the patients who could benefit from such processing. This, in turn, leads to some promising projects never becoming reality because executing them according to the requirements of the governing instances is simply infeasible. These circumstances hinder progress in MDS significantly. One reason for the subjectivity in project design and approval processes is the complexity of the DAI process resulting in a lack of standardization. A majority of project design decisions needs to be made project-specific carefully considering the respective objective and circumstances. These decisions include the choice of several trade-offs concerning patient privacy, scientific progress and technical requirements. These were listed in section 7.2. For instance, in MDS the general approach of data science generating knowledge by analyzing huge amounts of data meets the ethically justified approach of data minimization in medical research.

In the long run a major challenge for improving the situation for DAI of real-world clinical data is the strong focus on primary care both of organizational processes as well as technical infrastructures. Secondary use of such data in MDS projects was mostly ignored by the designers of the processes and data systems which results in a lack of necessary flexibility in the former and a patient-centricity hindering the access of large data sets in the latter. As outlined in section 7.4 re-designing the processes enabling more flexibility for MDS projects and changing the systems' implementation aiming for more data-centricity are promising measures which could ease the DAI process, reduce costs and hence foster MDS significantly. Thereby, the new designs should consider the challenges of MDS on real-world data and still enable high-quality primary care of patients. Thus, a major improvement of the circumstances for DAI in the medical field requires governing instances, legislators, ethical and technical experts to collaborate. In the short term, medical data science teams can encounter the challenges by thoroughly organizing their projects, e.g. by clearly assigning responsibilities and clarifying project requirements early with the respective governing instances. To achieve this, intensive communication in the team and beyond is necessary which may seem cumbersome but the earlier mistakes are identified the easier they can be corrected or even avoided.

8.1 Future Work

Section 7.5 revealed that the DAI conceptualization proposed by this thesis is comprehensive but not complete. A very central task that remains as future work and probably requires minor changes in the conceptualization, is executing and testing the workflow in practice. Furthermore, security assurance measures beyond de-identification that have been listed in the surrounding framework could be integrated into the workflow e.g. by using Privacy Enhanced BPMN (PE-BPMN) for modeling the process. PE-BPMN is a BPMN extension developed to enable modeling of privacy enhancing technologies in

BPMN models [64]. Based on PE-BPMN models the PLEAK tool¹ can be used to identify data leakages in the process [109, 110]. Moreover, the current version of the workflow does not cover the usage of external data sources although MDS needs a holistic approach using data from companies, several hospitals and health enabling technology to be successful in the long run [15]. Thus, such data sources are to be added in the Data Access subprocess which may additionally require changes in the other subprocesses. Examining this also remains as future work just as answering the open question of whether changes in the workflow are needed if unstructured data is accessed and integrated. Certainly the data preprocessing subprocess would have to be adapted such that it also covers NLP techniques. A further aspect that is currently not covered by the workflow is a subprocess of obtaining patient consent in the subprocess of Project Preparation. I did not design such a subprocess yet because I lack practical experience in this regard. However, I identified the availability of the patient consent as an important measure to enable the compilation of a truly reusable data set. So, future improvements of the workflow should add a model describing how to obtain it.

Furthermore, the proposed conceptualization and the suggestions for future improvement of the DAI process leave some open questions. For one thing, I suggested to automate the DAI process to reduce costs and improve data quality as well as reproducibility. Thereby, it remains to be examined which steps could be automated and how. Some steps may be easily automatable in the short term while others need more advanced automation solutions or are not automatable at all. For instance, the DAI project design requires a careful consideration of many aspects and communication with several instances. Automating this is very challenging if not even infeasible. A second issue that has not been examined yet are the dependencies of concepts listed in the surrounding DAI framework. The listed roles involved in the DAI process are not mutually exclusive e.g. a researcher can be part of the data science team and simultaneously act as a data provider. Potentially such dual roles can lead to ethical problems. Besides that, the listed security assurance measures are interrelated. For instance, choosing a less secure network domain segment is accompanied by the requirement to de-identify the patient data. Hence, future work could discuss the dependencies between concepts listed in section 7.3.1 and identify possible effects of them on the DAI process. Moreover, in section 3.4 I mentioned that for workflow performance estimation it is important to consider dependencies of individual workflow steps. The current performance estimation guideline does not cover this. Thus, future work could also examine the dependencies of the workflow steps and their influence on the workflow performance. Another interesting aspect influencing the performance is the complexity of communication that takes place in the multi-actor environment of the DAI process. For instance, the communication of a physician with a technical expert is usually more complex than two technical experts communicating with each other. Future work on

¹<https://pleak.io/home>

this aspect could suggest a conceptualization of DAI communication processes on top of the conceptualization proposed by this thesis. Different communication types could be defined to each of which a numerical weight is assigned. Eventually such accompanying mathematical conceptualizations would enable mathematical modeling of the DAI process that was described as a pure business process for now.

To conclude, the identification of challenges in the DAI process and the proposal of a generic DAI conceptualization by this thesis was only the first step. Starting from here a lot of future work is possible and even necessary.

Appendix A

Preliminary conceptualization results

This chapter contains the results of the "Do" step of the PDCA workflow development cycle (c.f. section 5.3). The reasoning behind the conceptualizations visualized in the following is outlined in section 6.3.

A.1 Roles and Actors

FIGURE A.1: Roles and Actors. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.1.

A.2 System Concepts

FIGURE A.2: System Concepts. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.2.

A.3 Aspects to determine the security level

FIGURE A.3: Security Levels. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.3.

A.4 The Workflow

FIGURE A.4: Data Access and Integration - Process Workflow. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.4.

A.4.1 Sub-sub-process Data Preprocessing

FIGURE A.5: Data Preprocessing. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.4.

A.4.2 Sub-process Project Preparation

FIGURE A.6: Project Preparation. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.4.

A.4.3 Sub-process Data Access

FIGURE A.7: Data Access. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.4.

A.4.4 Sub-process Data Set Preparation

FIGURE A.8: Data Set Preparation. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.4.

A.5 Workflow Performance Guideline

FIGURE A.9: Workflow Performance Guideline. Further explanation can be found in section 6.3.5.

Appendix B

Expert Interviews

This chapter contains the interview questions used to guide the expert interviews as well as the transcripts of the conducted interviews. Please note that the interview transcripts are complete. The "..." does not mean that something has been left out but that the sentence was not completed by the speaker.

B.1 Interview Questions

Regarding roles and actors shown in figure A.1:

1. Is there a role you feel you belong to? If so, which one?
2. Are important roles and actors of the DAI process missing?

Regarding system concepts shown in figure A.2:

1. How well are the categories "primary", "secondary" and "external" chosen? Would you prefer another classification?
2. Could you think of additional categories or concepts?

Regarding security levels shown in figure A.3:

1. Do you agree that the mentioned aspects are relevant to judge data security?
2. Are all relevant data security aspects captured here?

Regarding the workflow performance estimation guideline shown in figure A.9:

1. Do you consider all listed workflow performance metrics to be relevant?
2. Can you think of further workflow performance metrics that should be added?

Regarding the workflow itself depicted in appendix A.4:

1. Is the proposed workflow realistically realisable?
2. What needs to be changed in practice to enable/ improve the execution of the proposed workflow?
3. Where could the proposed workflow be improved concerning consumed time, cost, and usability of the resulting data set?

B.2 Transcripts of the interviews

Available upon request

Appendix C

CUP use case

C.1 Plots for Quality Assessment

C.1.1 Classes

C.1.2 Demographics

C.1.2.1 Barplots

C.1.2.2 Boxplots

C.1.3 Histology

C.1.4 Tumor Burden Scores

C.1.5 Laboratory Values

C.1.5.1 Barplots

C.1.5.2 Boxplots

C.2 Tables

Organ	Assigned metastasis location specifications
Lymphnodes	Lymphknoten iliaca externa rechts, Lymphknoten, Lymphknoten axilla links, Lymphknoten Lungenhilus links (10L), Lymphknoten infraclavikulär links, Lymphknoten iliaca communis rechts, Lymphknoten paratracheal rechts, Lymphknoten infraclavikulär rechts, Lymphknoten paratracheal links, Lymphknoten axilla rechts, Lymphknoten mediastinal, Lymphknoten coeliacal, Lymphknoten inguinal links, Lymphknoten paraaortal rechts, Lymphknoten Lungenhilus rechts (10R), Lymphknoten supraklavikulär links (Level V), Lymphknoten supraklavikulär rechts (Level V), Lymphknoten retrokrural, Lymphknoten zervikal tief unten rechts (Level IV), Lymphknoten paraaortal links
Kidney	Niere rechts, Niere, Niere links
Adrenal Gland	Nebenniere, Nebenniere links, Nebenniere rechts
Urinary Bladder	Harnblase
Heart	Herz, Perikard
Oesophagus	Ösophagus, Ösophagus Pars thoracalis, Ösophagus Pars thoracalis, Ösophagus
Stomach	Magen
Pancreas	Pankreas, Pankreas Hals, Pankreas Processus uncinatus, Pankreas Kopf, Pankreas corpus, Pankreas Schwanz'
Liver	Leber Segment IVa, Leber Segment VII, Leber Segment V, Leber Segment III, Leber, Leber Segment Ivb, Leber Segment VIII, Leber Segment VI, Leber Segment II'
Omentum	Omentum
Bones	Knochen Wirbel lumbal, Knochen Beckengürtel links, Knochen Wirbel zervikal, Knochen Beckengürtel links, Knochen Wirbel thorakal, Knochen
Lung	Lunge Unterlappen rechts, Lunge Oberlappen rechts, Lunge Oberlappen links, Lunge rechts, Lunge links, Pleura, Lunge Unterlappen links, Lunge Mittellappen rechts, Lunge
Skin	Haut
Spleen	Milz
Brain	Gehirn Kleinhirn Hälfte links, Gehirn Basalganglien, Gehirn Kleinhirn Hälfte rechts, Gehirn, Gehirn Frontallappen rechts, Gehirn Parietallappen links, Gehirn Occipitallappen links
Breast	Mamma rechts
Intestine	Colon sigmoideum
Thyroid Gland	Schilddrüse
Others	Andere, Weichteil, Mediastinum, Peritoneum, undefiniert, Becken, Perineum

TABLE C.1: Specifications of metastasis locations found in the radiological data grouped by higher level organs (work of Devina Soenarto). The original specifications of the metastasis locations are provided using the German terms from the RIS.

Feature	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max
Age	58.333	10.000	35.000	55.000	55.000	65.000	75.000
LDH	329.033	343.137	125.000	204.000	246.500	318.250	2704.000
HKT	38.300	5.958	22.000	34.000	39.000	42.000	49.000
HB	12.933	2.195	7.300	11.475	13.150	14.375	18.000
CA	2.351	0.130	2.060	2.260	2.350	2.413	2.680
CRP	29.057	38.338	1.100	5.250	13.500	37.550	212.3

TABLE C.2: Statistical values determined for numerical features in the compiled data set. The values are rounded to three decimal places. The age variable is given by the mean age of the age group assigned to the respective patient.

Feature	unique	most frequent value	count of most frequent value
Gender	2	M	42
T	10	3	21
N	6	0	16
M	4	1	37
L	3	nan	56
Pn	3	nan	56
V	3	nan	56
Grading	4	nan	35
TBS Lymphnodes	5	4	28
TBS Kidney	3	0	61
TBS Adrenal Gland	5	0	52
TBS Urinary Bladder	1	0	63
TBS Heart	2	0	61
TBS Oesophagus	1	0	63
TBS Stomach	2	0	61
TBS Pancreas	3	0	44
TBS Liver	4	4	28
TBS Omentum	1	0	63
TBS Bones	3	0	35
TBS Lung	4	4	23
TBS Skin	1	0	63
TBS Spleen	1	0	63
TBS Brain	4	0	50
TBS Breast	1	0	63
TBS Intestine	1	0	63
TBS Thyroid Gland	1	0	63
TBS Others	4	0	35
Class	5	Lung	27

TABLE C.3: Statistical values determined for categorical features in the compiled data set.

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